

Investigating Consumer Attitude Towards Adoption of Cryptocurrencies

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Declaration

I, Khushboo Mirchandani, hereby declare that this thesis is my own original work, composed as a result of my original research. This thesis has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification.

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Abstract

Cryptocurrencies that are based on the blockchain technology are rapidly gaining considerable interest as an innovation that is disruptive and possibly historic for the financial industry on a worldwide scale. The literature review strongly suggests that there is dearth of research that looks into the adoption of cryptocurrencies from the multidisciplinary perspective. This research delves into developing a far-reaching model comprising of socio-technical factors to give a comprehensive perspective on the reception of cryptocurrencies. The aim of this research was to investigate the factors affecting the perceptions, opinions, and emotions of both users and potential users towards the adoption and usage of cryptocurrencies. This was examined through the lens of technology adoption frameworks supplemented with ideas from consumer psychology and trust and risk theories. This study observed a quantitative methodology, with the data being collected through a questionnaire. This data was then used to determine the reliability, validity, as well as the fit of the model proposed in this thesis using Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Structural Equation Modelling. The primary contribution of this research is a novel multi-criterion model that incorporates various factors from consumer psychology, including the social factor of Bandwagon effect, a hitherto unstudied concept in the context of cryptocurrency adoption. This research model is capable of explaining a significant portion (67%) of the variance in the intention to adopt cryptocurrencies. The findings indicated that the consumer's attitude towards cryptocurrencies and their perception of its usefulness as well as bandwagon effect had a strong impact on their intentions of adopting it. Personality traits of the individual as well as their perception of the trustworthiness of cryptocurrencies and the legal risks associated with them were also found to be significant factors in the study. In contrast, technology anxiety regarding cryptocurrency usage and the associated privacy risks were not found to be significant factors. Expanding on the limits of existing literature to fill the gaps, the insights made in this study regarding the constructs and the relationships identified can be utilised for studying adoption of various technologies. From the managerial point of view, the research will aid in understanding the requirements of users as well as potential users, thereby assisting in development of creative and productive ways to deliver the paramount cryptocurrency services. The key proposal is to put resources into the improvement of the

usability of the crypto services and delivery of those important features that increase trust to a significant level.

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Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Overview of the Chapter

This introductory chapter begins with explaining the background to the research and providing a brief overview of literature associated with cryptocurrencies, their potential and the factors that contribute to its adoption. It further elucidates the aims and objectives of the research. Subsequently, this introductory chapter then throws more light on the motivations of the researcher for conducting this research and the gaps and contributions associated with this research topic. It also provides theoretical and managerial implications of this study. The following section produces a brief outline of the research methodology adopted in the research. The final section of this chapter brings forth a layout of the arrangement of this thesis.

1.2 Background to the Research

1.2.1 Introduction to Cryptocurrencies

Modern technological era has brought about spectacular changes in the financial services industry. From instant connectivity to mobile banking, innovative technologies have turned into a crucial piece of the advanced financial world. The world recently has seen a large number of innovative evolutions like digital payments, e-commerce, mobile banking etc. Impressions of these advancements can be found in the way individuals communicate and the manner in which they deal with monetary transactions. From these technological developments in the financial services industry, which dates back into the most recent twenty years wherein economies are gradually moving from conventional paper notes and coins to digital currencies, another type of currency, known as cryptocurrency has come into existence (Abbasi et al., 2021). This financial technological product has the potential of disrupting the modern financial world and banking industry and could possibly bring about a paradigm shift.

Cryptocurrencies are considered to be a significant innovation in the financial industry and serve as virtual currencies that intend to substitute the existing paper and coin currencies

(Alzahrani and Daim, 2019). Similar to the ways in which internet facilities and/or products have transformed the current state of communication, it is thought that cryptocurrencies can radically transform the way humans and businesses engage in daily transactions. Cryptocurrencies take several formats, prominent among which are the Bitcoins, Ripples, Litecoins, Etheurems, etc. (Arias-Oliva, Pelegrín-Borondo and Matías-Clavero, 2019).

In general terms, cryptocurrency is considered a digital currency that is built on techniques of cryptography for carrying out a number of transactions (Mazambani and Mutambara, 2019). In terms of functionality, cryptocurrencies work with an electronic peer to peer cash system and they permit electronic payments without the need for any financial intermediary (like the financial institutions) since payments are made directly to the party concerned. This is different from other available financial instruments as cryptocurrencies do not have any link with any superior supervisory or regulatory institutions, do not exist physically, and are infinitely divisible (Corbet et al., 2019). Cryptocurrencies have significant advantages of using them including real time transactions, peer to peer transactions, low transaction costs, security and transparency, cross border usage, etc. (Nadeem et al., 2021). Furthermore, the intrinsic values of cryptocurrencies are not dependent on tangible assets and the economy of the countries; instead, cryptocurrencies are grounded on the algorithms from which all the transactions can be traced (Corbet et al., 2019).

1.2.2 Potential of Cryptocurrencies

At present there are more than 9000 cryptocurrencies with more than \$2 trillion of market capitalisation, primarily dominated by Bitcoin which accounts for more than 50% of the market capitalisation (CoinmarketCap., 2021). Bitcoin was one of the first cryptocurrencies to be launched in the market and the growth percentage it provided is much more than any other asset (Corbet et al., 2019).

The Economic Times (2021) mentioned that India has been increasingly adopting cryptocurrencies and has become a booming market for cryptocurrencies. It further stated that cryptocurrencies have outshone gold and it was expected that they would become the go-to reserve asset. Both long term and short-term investors in India have progressively shown attraction towards investing in cryptocurrency markets specifically in bitcoins due its credibility, feasibility and reliability factors. Major industry experts have even termed it as

“Money 2.0”. Inadvertently, due to the recent covid-19 pandemic, bitcoins in India saw a fall in market prices; however, it later turned out to be a windfall for the industry even through the lockdown and regardless of all its associated ambiguities (The Economic Times, 2021).

In a related study, the World Economic Forum (2021) expressed that cryptocurrencies have seen significantly higher rates of adoption in developing countries like Turkey, Vietnam and South Africa. For example, Nigeria has started using cryptocurrencies for the purposes of buying and selling goods or services as well as remitting funds to people living across borders (WeForum, 2021). Twenty of the largest economies of the world along with the international financial bodies are developing standards in order to regulate and issue sovereign virtual currencies. They would be different from bitcoin in a way that they will maintain visibility and access into the Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDC) payments as well as identities. Also, the Bank of Japan (BOJ) and the European Union Central Bank (ECB) have mentioned that they would be considering issuing CBDC. BOJ further stated that they would be bringing in the experiments for digital Yen and an effort would be made for matching the digital yuan from China which is considered the most widespread digital currency under trial (Coindesk, 2020).

Corroborative evidence has indicated that the Bahamas is the only country that has this type of CBDC to support its payments and receipting systems (Business Standard, 2021). In addition, Sweden has disclosed that by 2026 they would have their own virtual currency and the European Union Central Bank announced that they would have their digital currency “electric euro” that can be brought into existence in four years’ time. Similar to the above, financial reporting and regulatory bodies have waded into the arguments of streamlining cryptocurrency transactions. For instance, the IFRS is considering a financial reporting standard on the digital, block chain and crypto currencies in order to regulate its impact on corporate reporting practices (IFRS, 2021).

A survey by a U.S. Financial group pointed out that young British investors are twice as prone to purchase cryptocurrencies like bitcoin as they are to purchase stocks. The Covid-19 pandemic has brought this surge in online trading. In that survey, 51% of investors aged in the range of 18 and 37 exchanged or possessed digital currencies which is twofold the quantity of those, 25%, purchasing or holding equities. Bitcoin has absorbed almost 90% as large investors like Goldman Sachs, Morgan Stanley, Tesla Inc. in the year 2021 (US News, 2021). Authorities of Britain like the Bank of England and the Treasury will be working together

towards creating a Central Bank digital currency like the other countries and it could be called as “Bitcoin”. It could be used by household units as well as businesses as legal tenders which could be coexisting with the traditional bank and cash deposits. It would be different from bitcoin since the issuing party here would be the State authorities (Business Standard, 2021).

In view of the fact that cryptocurrencies have become popular among users, investors, regulators and media, they have also drawn the attention of academic researchers. Definitely, the acceptance level of cryptocurrencies has grown over the last few years and this can be established through various indicators such as increased market capitalisation, rising transaction volumes and potential increase in the estimated number of users. There are many factors or drivers that have an influence on consumers’ adoption of cryptocurrencies (Alzahrani and Daim, 2019). To understand the growth and predict future scenarios of such new and disruptive innovations, it is imperative to explore the nature of such factors that influence the behaviour of consumers towards cryptocurrencies.

1.2.3 Factors and Theories Influencing the Adoption of Cryptocurrencies

The unique technological turn of events and financial matters have raised the call for cryptocurrencies and has boosted trust among individuals from one side of the world to the other. Cryptocurrencies could be appealing because of their technological and financial benefits (Nadeem et al., 2021). Since people are the basic segment of this digitalised financial framework, individual and corporate perceptions and opinions about cryptocurrencies will determine the product’s future market scenario (Shahzad et al., 2018). The maximum capacity of cryptocurrency can be accomplished when it has far and wide adoption by users without which its effect stays negligible. An increase in institutions who invest resources into cryptocurrencies is an impression of positive possibilities of interest. In any case, such a supposition could be pointless without anticipating users’ intentions, tastes and preferences to adopt the products. Online traders have begun to acknowledge cryptocurrency as a mode of exchange even though its use by consumers is restricted. Consequently, an exhaustive comprehension of the drivers behind cryptocurrency adoption is central as the endurance of cryptocurrency innovation is intensely reliant upon the acceptance by users (Mazambani and Mutambara, 2019).

Recent research on the adoption of technology has endeavoured to recognize, predict and elucidate the variables and factors that influence the behaviour of individuals towards accepting and using new and innovative technologies. This has led to the advancement of conceptual frameworks to investigate the relationships between those variables with the intention to adopt (Salahshour Rad, Nilashi and Mohamed Dahlan, 2017). There are diverse models and theories which have been introduced by scholars for the purpose of understanding the behavioural intentions of consumers towards technologies. These include the theory of Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) proposed by Rogers (1995); Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) introduced by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975); Theory of Planned behaviour (TPB) formulated by Ajzen (1991); Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) proposed by Venkatesh et al. (2003); Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1986); Davis (1989); Technology Readiness presented by Parasuraman (2000); Task-Technology Fit and Individual Performance theory formulated by Goodhue and Thompson (1995) and many more. Also, there are other theories from the field of behavioural psychology and social psychology that are considered important in understanding the consumer adoption.

Besides the constructs from these theories and models, there are several other studies that have brought up other important variables that are needed to be considered for understanding the user adoption behaviour. These include different types of risks, perceived trust, self-efficacy, personal innovativeness, anxiety, user satisfaction, performance expectancy, perceived enjoyment, service quality, perceived cost, system quality, privacy, etc. (Salahshour Rad, Nilashi and Mohamed Dahlan, 2017).

Prior literature has observed that technology adoption theories and models have also been used for understanding the behaviour of consumers towards cryptocurrencies. There are a large number of constructs or variables that have an impact on the intention of adopting the cryptocurrencies by users. Arias-Oliva, Pelegrín-Borondo and Matías-Clavero (2019) have used variables from the UTAUT model and have also added Perceived Risk and financial literacy for the purpose of analysing the acceptance of cryptocurrencies.

A comparative study conducted by Schaupp and Festa (2018) deployed the Theory of Planned Behaviour for investigating the factors that have an effect on the intent to use cryptocurrencies. Another popular study by Mendoza-Tello et al. (2018) have deployed the

variables from TAM, social support theory and social commerce to examine the way social media is accumulating trust and intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies for e-payments.

Baur et al. (2015) have adopted Technology Acceptance Model using the constructs perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as well as subjective from the Theory of Planned Behaviour as well as a separate construct know as future potential for studying the disruptive and widely studied cryptocurrency i.e. Bitcoin. A large portion of prior literature suggests that TAM is one of the most widely and strongly recommended model for investigating the consumer acceptance of innovative technologies. Many studies also show new models that integrate the constructs of TAM for examining user adoption (Albayati, Kim and Rho, 2020). The above theoretical frameworks that drive the adoption of cryptocurrencies will be critically examined in the literature review section of this thesis.

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives

1.3.1 Aims of the Research

The main resolution of this study is to understand the behaviour of consumers towards cryptocurrencies. Through the lens of various technology adoption frameworks along with theories of trust, risk and other social psychological constructs, the research aims to investigate those factors that lead to adoption of innovative financial technologies, primarily cryptocurrencies. This research intends to understand the perceptions, opinions and emotions of both users and potential users towards the adoption and usage of cryptocurrency. The research draws literature from various fields including information systems, social psychology, and marketing and consumer behaviour studies. The research aims to use the existing research on technological acceptance model, risk and trust theory, and socio psychological variables to develop a multi criterion model consisting of the most crucial constructs for understanding the behaviour of consumers towards cryptocurrency. The aim of this research is to investigate the constructs or variables and the relationship among those variables influencing the acceptance of cryptocurrencies.

1.3.2 Research Objectives

- To review the existing literature on adoption of technology and consumers' intentions towards buying and investing in cryptocurrencies.
- To understand the concept of cryptocurrencies and the attitude of consumers towards cryptocurrencies.
- To develop a multi criterion model presenting the relationships among the most crucial constructs that have an impact consumers' perceptions of cryptocurrencies.
- To identify the significant factors that play a role in consumers' adoption of cryptocurrencies.

1.4 Research Question

The central research question that this thesis seeks to answer is this:

How do the behavioural patterns and other exogenous factors determine consumers' adoption of cryptocurrencies?

1.5 Research Motivation

Within the span of a few decades, the internet went from being a fringe subject in textbooks to an omnipresent topic that permeates every inch of the social fabric. In today's world, everyone owns handheld devices that possess computational abilities that were once achievable only by enormous machines and reserved for scientific or military purposes. Having grown up in the midst of this technological revolution, the thing that has been fascinating for the researcher was seeing the reaction of people towards new technologies. It was always very intriguing to observe what were the specific factors, ideas and incidents that drove people to accept new technologies.

The researcher is very keen about this research because of her significant interest in consumer and behavioural psychology. The researcher is passionate to learn more about new

and innovative technologies and their future growth prospects. It motivates the researcher to understand how technologies like the internet become part of our lifestyle and why some technologies are not accepted by society.

Looking at the digital revolution it can be said that the new technologies have saved the modern world by their application in various industries like healthcare, telecommunications, banking and financial services, automotive, etc. Similarly, cryptocurrencies and blockchain products have the potential to shape the future of the society. The researcher is fascinated to learn about the cryptocurrencies that can bring about such a paradigm shift as well as understand how people respond to them while they are still in the early stages of innovation.

Since cryptocurrencies are not just financial products but also technological innovations, there are several factors like government regulations, risks and socio-psychological aspects that might have an influence on their adoption. The researcher is extremely motivated to understand the behaviour of consumers towards cryptocurrencies since people have become extremely enthusiastic about this potentially disruptive technology which can possibly substitute the existing currencies. The knowledge of the researcher in the field of information technology project management and experience in organisational adoption of innovative technology further stimulate her curiosity to conduct a study on this particular topic.

1.6 Research Gaps and Contributions

Recent evidence suggests that several studies have been conducted on blockchain and cryptocurrencies over the last few years. Various studies like Presthus and O'Malley (2017), Gunawan and Novendra (2017) have been conducted using different theories like Innovation of Diffusion and UTAUT to analyse the users' motivations and barriers towards the cryptocurrencies. Folkinshteyn and Lennon (2016) have used TAM for analysing the elements of accepting the technology for Bitcoin in terms of a currency and blockchain in terms of technology. Gao, Clark and Lindqvist (2016) conducted qualitative research studying the perceptions of users and non-users towards Bitcoin. Research by Krombholz et al. (2017) conducted surveys and some interviews for examining the experience of the users of bitcoin with respect to the factors including privacy, anonymity and security. While extensive

literature exists on bitcoin, there is a dearth of research on various facets of cryptocurrency from a multidisciplinary point of view. Bitcoin is shown to have been studied in numerous domains including technical fields, policy and law, accounting, finance, economics, etc but there still remains many unexplored areas (Holub and Johnson, 2018).

Reviews of present literature on cryptocurrency and fintech bring up the need for cross-disciplinary studies utilising technology and psychology (Cai, 2018). A study by Baur et al. (2015) explains that there is lack of research regarding drivers of user adoption. It further elaborates that academic literature neglects the perceptions of the users that connect the technological structure with the economies. Studies have also suggested that there are meaningful contributions on financial aspects of cryptocurrencies including hedging, capital control, disruption in foreign markets, etc. Even though there are a large number of people investing in cryptocurrencies, there is not much research surrounding the aspect of demand and consumer adoption of cryptocurrencies (Jung et al., 2018).

Comparatively, Alzahrani and Daim (2019) in their study provided a literature on the factors influencing the adoption of cryptocurrencies including some technical factors, economic factors, social factors and personal factors. Here they mentioned the need for extension of research in varied directions by proposing a multi criterion decision model in order to understand the factors affecting the adoption of cryptocurrencies in a clearer manner. They further stated that the TAM or UTAUT model could be used for designing a survey that can test the implication of such factors. Mendoza-Tello et al. (2018) in their study have postulated the need to explore some new theoretical paradigms from the social perspective that will help in further understanding the acceptance of cryptocurrencies in the society as a whole. In the literature, the authors highlighted that, even if there is evidence from prior research that discloses the importance of cryptocurrencies in general, there still remains inadequate systematic research on acceptance and adoption of cryptocurrencies at the international level (Saiedi, Broström and Ruiz, 2020).

It can be observed that the research associated with cryptocurrencies is still at an evolving stage and the adoption of cryptocurrencies in the consumer behaviour domain is a sparsely researched topic. Looking at the global popularity of cryptocurrencies in recent times and considering that they are increasingly being accepted as an alternate investment and payment option, there is a lack of research that explores the important factors affecting

adoption of cryptocurrencies. For instance, the role of social influence in the context of cryptocurrency adoption has gained widespread coverage in news and media (Santander, 2021), but data backed academic research has not yet examined the role of social phenomena such as bandwagon effect in the adoption of cryptocurrencies. Similarly, personality traits and emotional attributes such as openness to new opportunities, fear of missing out etc are also suspected to play a role in adoption of cryptocurrencies (Delfabbro, King and Williams, 2021; Kim et al., 2020). Despite this, there is very limited research that looks into the contribution of such psychological factors. It is apparent that cryptocurrencies are not just a financial technology, but are also to a large extent part of the sociocultural fabric. Therefore, there is a need to conduct research encompassing constructs from various domains to better understand the factors that drive consumers to engage in cryptocurrencies. Hence, this research delves into developing a model that includes factors from technology adoption, social psychology, trust and risk domain, etc. and also looks into the interactions among these constructs to understand the consumer behaviour towards cryptocurrencies.

1.7 Theoretical and Managerial Implications

The researcher aims to expand the limits of existing literature to fill the gaps through the assimilation of a large number of ideas and views from inside and between the fields of consumer behaviour and adoption of new technologies. The integration of models and theories coordinated across various associations will permit the researcher to see new causal relationships among the constructs under examination. The insights made in this research regarding the constructs and the relationships identified can be utilised for studying adoption of various technologies.

This research is significantly important for the consumers, investors as well as the corporates that are interested in understanding the cryptocurrency landscape. The study can offer valuable insights for the users and potential users of cryptocurrencies by identifying the factors which are important for their acceptance and adoption. The companies would be able to understand the success factors of launching the cryptocurrencies in a better way by understanding the intentions of the consumers. It would also be beneficial for the financial institutions and information technology companies for exploring the market scenario regarding the adoption of new and innovative financial products. Furthermore, it will also

help shed light on how risk and trust factors interact with socio-psychological factors for cryptocurrencies.

1.8 Research Design and Methodology

This research will adopt a positivist approach and a quantitative methodology which is highlighted by a deductive approach and insists that reality is constructed by deploying statistical techniques to produce quantifiable results. The research adopts a positivist approach since it aims to identify the variables that have an impact on the adoption of cryptocurrencies. The researcher here would like to take into account the views of a number of people and measure them collectively. In ages past, in the sphere of marketing and consumer behaviour research, a large number of studies have been known to use statistical methods based on market related responses; thus, the research will adopt a quantitative methodology following the deductive approach to the research. The data collection will be taking place using a structured questionnaire through purposive sampling backed by snowballing sampling technique.

1.9 Structure of the Research

The study is split into seven major sections and chapters. The current chapter highlights the introduction and overall outline of this research. The second chapter delves into the review of related and relevant literature. Here, among others, the literature review chapter will define key terminologies, consider history of cryptocurrencies, the types of cryptocurrencies, technologies and tools associated with them and their features and uses will also be discussed. The literature review will then focus on the key concepts and theories used in the research. A comprehensive literature associated with cryptocurrencies and their adoption by consumers is provided in this chapter. Prior to concluding the literature review section with an overt explication of the research gap based the various underlying theoretical frameworks will be considered. The mapping of variables and development of hypotheses then takes place

in the third chapter. The third chapter then concludes with a description of the conceptual framework of the research model.

The fourth chapter looks at the research methodology section wherein the researcher makes a case of her research strategy, plan, and field work. As earlier mentioned, a positivist research philosophy was used for the study and the use of structured questionnaires were adopted for the quantitative analysis. The thesis then considers an in-depth statistical analysis using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modelling (SEM) to test the research model and the hypotheses developed. The discussions and interpretations of the analysed data and the ensuing findings are enshrined in the sixth chapter of the thesis. In the final part of this thesis, conclusions and recommendations are discussed. In addition, the theoretical contributions, and managerial and social implications are discussed in chapter seven of the thesis. Figure 1.1 below is a graphical representation of the exposition and arrangement of the thesis for reference.

Figure 1.1 Exposition and Structure of Thesis

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2.1 Overview of the Chapter

This chapter is concerned with the extensive and in-depth review of literature discussing the key concepts of cryptocurrencies, their features and uses, and the technologies and services associated with them. It also briefly reviews some popular cryptocurrencies. It then delves into the technology adoption frameworks and socio-psychological factors that have a significant impact on consumer behaviour. Then a comprehensive literature review regarding cryptocurrency adoption and consumer behaviour was conducted. Finally, based on the review of literature, research gaps are clearly identified.

2.2 Concept of Cryptocurrencies

In a white paper, “Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System” dated 31 October 2008, Satoshi Nakamoto laid the foundation of blockchain technology with the introduction of the first ever cryptocurrency named Bitcoin (Nakamoto, 2008). However, the research shows that the history of computerised currencies dates way back in 1990 with the initiation of Digicash by Chaum. It was thought that Nakamoto gave new life to Chaum’s ideas of secrecy of transactions through cryptological algorithms and procedures by including the concepts of P2P networking and raising funds on internet without the control of a central body (Phillip, Chan and Peiris, 2018). Contemporary studies show that cryptocurrencies are understood differently by various scholars.

In their influential study of cryptocurrencies, Mukhopadhyay et al. (2016) noted that currency units generated digitally through cryptography and used as a medium of exchange without the involvement of a controlling central authority can be termed as cryptocurrency. Comparative research by Akar and Akar (2020) considered cryptocurrencies as self-governing autonomous digital exchange medium that are the product of cryptography via the use of independent computers that have given birth to a new technology called blockchain which

facilitates digital online transactions between two parties. These technologies are being continuously approved and accepted as a replacement of paper currencies across the globe.

Härdle, Harvey and Reule (2020), coined a term DAO (Digital Autonomous Organization) and according to these scholars, cryptocurrencies can be considered as DAO or an independent system of furnishing capital created online on a peer-to-peer network by following certain set of protocols or algorithm for which the code of transactions is available to the public. On the other hand, Inci and Lagasse (2019) have labelled cryptocurrency as “cash for the internet”. In their seminal study into digital currencies, they consider cryptocurrency as a section of information that has some value in which case the individual who possesses the information also possesses its value for the given holding time, until someone else gains control over that information or the key rendering value to that information. Inci and Lagasse (2019) further stated that cryptocurrencies are a result of craving for cash on internet paired with the want of these transactions to be undisclosed. Conversely, Giudici, Milne and Vinogradov (2019) consider cryptocurrencies as the non-physical values or online fiscal possessions whose execution and verification are performed by the underlying software using the blockchain technology.

2.2.1 Technology and services involved in the cryptocurrencies

It has been widely reported that the technology that enables cryptocurrencies is the blockchain technology. Due to the combination of various important concepts like peer-to-peer network, cryptography, distributed/decentralised system, blockchain proves to be powerful in ensuring the fortification of data and transactions of cryptocurrencies and hence proves useful in an assortment of arenas (Sriman, Ganesh Kumar and Shamili, 2021). The blockchain technology and other tools, mechanisms, and trading services associated with cryptocurrencies are further discussed below.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Ghimire, S. and Selvaraj, H. (2018) A Survey on Bitcoin Cryptocurrency and its Mining. In: 2018 26th International Conference on Systems Engineering.

Figure 2.1 Working of the Bitcoin Blockchain (Ghimire and Selvaraj, 2018)

2.2.1.1 Blockchain technology

As earlier stated, the Blockchain technology supports cryptocurrencies. Blockchain technology is a peer-to-peer system of maintenance of transactions in the form of an open ledger that is available to the public and serves as a disbursement database. It is not a centralized system. It is dispersed across a large set of computers over the globe via the internet (Lee, 2019). When Satoshi Nakamoto elaborated the application of blockchain technology in the form of Bitcoin, it boosted the emergence of different cryptocurrencies and several other uses of blockchain (Härdle, Harvey and Reule, 2020). The data stored in this system or environment is converted to nodes. Each system engaged and connected is termed as a node. No individual owns a blockchain, thus it works on the element of trust among all nodes. Frauds or manipulations with a blockchain are virtually not possible as all transactions are recorded and updated on each node following the receipt of consensus from every node involved in a particular blockchain. Hence, even if some nodes fail or are removed from the chain, the system continues to function. This covers the demerits of a centralised system

where failure of a central node could cause an entire network to collapse (Mohanta et al., 2019; Swan, 2015).

Apart from being used in the implementation of cryptocurrencies, blockchain finds its use in all possible sectors of modern society, viz. finance (Treleaven et al., 2017), insurance (Raikwar et al., 2018), healthcare (Mettler, 2016), digital identity management (Haddouti and Kettani, 2019), e-voting (Hjalmarsson et al., 2018) and the energy sector (Andoni et al., 2019). Due to a combination of various important technologies like P2P network, cryptography, distributed/decentralised system blockchain proves to be powerful in ensuring the fortification of data and transaction processing of cryptocurrencies. This proves useful in an assortment of arena including supply chain (Saber et al., 2018), Internet of Things (IoT) (Wang et al., 2019), healthcare (Zubaydi et al., 2019), and finance (Sriman, Kumar and Shamili, 2020).

The Figure 2.2 gives an idea about the structural design of the blockchain model. At the first layer, there is a signed transaction between two peers. A transaction here is considered to give a coin or to finish a job etc and it should be signed by at least one of the two members involved. The information of this transaction is broadcasted to other nodes in the network. These nodes pack up the transactions into one block and are also responsible for the validation of these transactions. Only valid transactions are assimilated in the blocks, rest are discarded. To avoid deviations and faulty transactions, all nodes must reach a common accord on which transactions to keep and which to let go. This is the role of the second layer of the model which is the consensus layer (Casino, Dasaklis and Patsakis, 2019).

Figure 2.2 Overview of Blockchain (Casino, Dasaklis and Patsakis, 2019)

2.2.1.2 Cryptography

It is almost certain that blockchain technology uses advanced cryptographic methods like hashing, public key cryptography and Merkle Trees to keep a check on reliability of data and on confidentiality of consumer. Hashing encrypts data to character strings by applying strong algorithms like SHA-256 to the datasets. It is because of Hashing that blockchains have acquired the property of immutability (AR and Banik, 2020). Public key cryptography started way back in 1970s and in the crypto world this method is used to generate a pair of keys – private key and public key. Typically, the private key leads to the production of the public key. Generally, a public key relates to getting the coins or crypto money whereas private key is associated with expending the same coins from the Bitcoin wallet. It is commonly believed that the private key is a randomly generated number from which the public key is derived using mathematical cryptographic procedures from which the public key bitcoin address is engendered by applying hash method (Antonopoulos, 2017).

Coins are not actually moving on the crypto network, instead a notification is transmitted to the nodes to provide information about the transformation of possession of the particular Bitcoin entity. The coin address that is obtained via public key is used as false identity. As the sequence of private key to public key and public key to address of the crypto coin is unidirectional, it cannot be undone or overturned (Berentsen and Schar, 2018). Digital signatures are another form of crypto primitives which are a must in the adoption of a blockchain technology. Diffie and Hellman introduced the idea of digital signatures in 1976 which paved the way for public key cryptography. ECDSA and EdDSA are generally used formats of digital signatures in blockchains (Wang et al., 2019).

2.2.1.3 Proof of Work (PoW) and Proof of Stake (PoS)

Authors have generally agreed on the various consensus mechanisms based on the type of blockchain technologies. The most common is Proof-of-work (POW) in which a tough computational method is to be found out or solved, for e.g., searching for a hash with some pattern like a number of preceding zeroes. This Proof-of-work signifies the validation and authenticity of the transaction and the solvers are termed as miners. The miners spend their mining resources which comprise Computational power, electricity etc. (Casino, Dasaklis and Patsakis, 2019). Originally Satoshi Nakamoto used the notion of PoW and it has proved to be the most widely accepted consensus mechanism.

Markus Jacobson and Ari Juels coined the term Proof of Work. It is based on the principle of “Easy to verify but difficult to find” (Sriman, Kumar and Shamili, 2020) as illustrated in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3 Mechanism of Proof of Work (Sriman, Kumar and Shamili, 2020)

Another popular consensus mechanism is the Proof-of-stake (POS). PoS protocol has been put forward as a substitute to PoW. Under a PoS, mining has been eliminated which causes this mechanism to save a lot of electricity and computational power. PoS is an energy saver consensus process as compared to PoW (Saleh, 2020). The PoS system involves the choosing of winners among different nodes who have put forward their stakes in the form of digitised tokens or coins. Only one block is created in PoS unlike PoW where miners put forward different blocks thereby wasting a big amount of energy. Likewise, due to the above reason PoS is considered to be a quicker mechanism than the PoW (Nguyen et al., 2019).

Figure 2.4 Comparison between PoW and PoS mechanism (Nguyen et al., 2019)

2.2.1.4 Mining

A procedure known as mining, represented in Figure 2.5, is used to tabulate a crypto riddle. Computers on the network do mining. The mathematical riddle is solved when a random hash value is deduced. When a hash is traced within the allotted time slot, a message is broadcasted to all the other nodes to stop mining for that particular block. The awards of successful mining are the crypto coins. (Sriman, Kumar and Shamili, 2020). When miners group together in order to accumulate the scattered resources, they are said to form mining pools in which case the incentives of successful mining are also divided among the pool of miners (Dziembowski, 2015).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.
Original figure can be found in Aljabr, A., Sharma, A. and Kumar, K. (2019) Mining Process in Cryptocurrency Using Blockchain Technology: Bitcoin as a Case Study. Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience. Vol.16.

Figure 2.5 Rewarding process of Mining (Aljabr, Sharma and Kumar, 2019)

2.2.1.5 Crypto Exchanges

Crypto money can be exchanged with fiat currency just as fiat money could be exchanged for cryptocurrencies through the crypto exchanges. The volume of trade on these exchanges mainly decides the price of the digital coins. Consumers deal with these online exchanges through the exchanges' websites using Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) connection. These trade zones provide services of storing the digital coins in e- wallets of the consumers and facilitates trade of cryptocurrency just like stock markets. Generally, a fee is charged for these services while some exchanges provide free services to the customers. The private key of clients' wallet is known to the exchange so it is suggested to choose trusted exchanges. (Bhaskar and Chuen, 2015).

2.2.1.6 Crypto wallets

A web wallet is a wallet on the internet that is accessed via a website as it is hosted on a distant server machine. It operates instantaneously, does not engage memory of the hard disk and can be accessed from all over the globe. Varieties of web wallets are functional. A

few of them store private keys on server side and some do the same in the browser on client side (Gervais et al., 2014). A wallet for cryptocurrencies is software that stores public and private keys, facilitates the transactions of coins on different blockchains, and maintains a record of balance of users. A transaction really means updating of record on blockchain and alteration in the digital wallet of the client (Jokić et al., 2019).

2.2.2 Features of cryptocurrencies

Cryptocurrencies possess two very distinctive features. One of them is decentralisation which means there is no governing authority behind these digital assets. This feature has attracted many clients as the coins can be created with confirmation of a group of deals or exchanges and there is no third party to keep a check. Another attribute is cryptography that makes the transactions secure through encoding. Generally, the cryptographic technique applied is “asymmetric encryption” that involves the use of public key to cipher the data file at sender end and private key to decipher the same at the receiver end (Miller, 2016). One more thing that makes a blockchain so powerful is its peer-to-peer network. All transactions are recorded not only on a single computer, rather stored on numerous computers across the world and again it is almost impossible to hack all these systems to change the data. Hence due to the property of immutability whatever data once goes into a block chain can never be changed (Zheng et al., 2017).

Decentralization, counterfeiting, check point for double-spending and pseudonymity are the features of cryptocurrency that have drawn the attention of researchers and also enhanced its usage in various fields (Wang et al., 2019). The ascent in fame and usage of cryptocurrencies has raised a potential threat to the survival of the existing financial system which is centralized and involves a lot of infrastructure. Also, cryptocurrencies are practically easy to handle as the transactions involve use of a smart phone and internet which are easily accessible and hence provide a less costly, safer and quick means of transactions thus attracting billions of people who benefit through this bank less and hassle-free route as compared to traditional banking approach (Härdle, Harvey and Reule, 2020). Cryptocurrencies can certainly prove to be a valuable contribution or add on to an investors’ array of instruments to help enhance portfolio.

2.2.3 Uses of cryptocurrencies

Although originally proposed as a form of currency and a medium of exchange, cryptocurrencies have found widespread usage as an investment and savings instrument (Chuen, Guo and Wang, 2017). Apart from their application as monetary devices and online chattels, Bitcoins and other cryptocurrencies find uses in many areas. Some of the other applications of cryptocurrencies are Coloured Coins, Smart Contracts, usage of biometrics like fingerprints for file security in blockchain etc. (Berentsen and Schar, 2018). Here, some of the prominent uses are discussed.

2.2.3.1 Investment and Currency

Research by Yermack (2013) indicated that the behaviour of cryptocurrencies seems to be more aligned to an investment instrument than as a medium of exchange. They further identified that business related applications of Bitcoins are minimal globally as it does not possess the necessary features that qualify it as a currency since digital currencies can neither be deposited in banks nor are they insured and the virtual coins cannot be used to provide loans nor to secure mortgages or credits. Furthermore, Research by Glaser et al. (2014) concluded that particularly unacquainted consumers of virtual currencies view these digital coins as an optional means of investment and trading on exchanges rather than participating in their transaction mechanism or using them as currency. Similarly, with cryptocurrencies being a newly introduced alternative with a high volatility in prices, customers tend to put fewer amounts at stake as investment. The other point of concern is that if someday the government of their country declares that the digital currency is legally invalid in that particular land then the total value of investment is lost. The authors also clearly established that although there is a very minute impact of negative news on the crypto market, positive news acts as a magnet to draw new investors and stresses the existing investors to hold on.

On the other hand, Kristoufek (2015) explains that bitcoins or crypto coins are considered a strong replacement of government issued currencies due to certain cutting-edge characteristics like a fixed and regulated algorithm for generation of coins, minimal or no charges for transactions and clarity of information for every transaction. Success of Bitcoins in the role of a currency has triggered the emergence of many other such currencies,

collectively termed as Altcoins. This also aligns with the original purpose with which cryptocurrencies were first created.

2.2.3.2 Smart Contracts

It is generally understood that a smart contract is “a mechanized or automated set of rules for a deal that runs or carries out the conditions of a contract”. To avoid the interference of intermediaries and malevolent or unintended incidences, empirical research recommended incorporating the points of a contract into a set of programming instructions (Christidis and Devetsikiotis, 2016). Furthermore, smart contracts can be understood as programs that can be created and run on base platforms of blockchain technology. These digital contracts are deals between two undependable parties that are involved, with no intervention of a third party.

Compared to normal paper-based contracts, smart contracts provide a digital system of negotiations between the dealing parties, which is devoid of any supervision of controlling or governance bodies. Due to usage of blockchain technology, smart contracts are tamper proof as each node in the chain stores a copy of it and renders it less prone to man made mistakes as they are totally computerised (Khan et al., 2021). The functioning of the smart contracts is put into effect by the Bitcoin architecture. Escrow, dispute mediation and assurance contracts are some examples of this kind. Other sophisticated varieties include multiparty protocols such as decentralised lotteries (Dziembowski, 2015).

2.2.4 Drawbacks of cryptocurrencies

The crypto currency market and technology is still in its budding stage and with several attractive pros holds many cons. Cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin have come into highlight recently due to media promotion and its characteristic of making anonymous transactions helps the people in acquiring commodities online unethically (Miller, 2016). Since, most unfettered currencies on the globe are the cryptocurrencies, it is estimated that almost one fourth of these currencies are used for illicit trades. Issues involved in the usage of these non – fiat currencies include scams, robbery, assail for ransom, non-exchangeability and hacking.

An additional uncontrolled factor is the complete absence of norms for safety and insurance as cryptocurrencies are imaginative, decentralized, barely discernible and unnamed. On the one hand, the main charm or charisma involved with these digital coins is the lack of involvement of governing bodies. It is even seen that intervention of state regulations can make them lose their attraction and bring a fall in investment and trade (Inci and Lagasse, 2019). On the other hand, it is seen that the price of cryptocurrencies is highly unstable and keeps fluctuating, maybe due to the absence of a regulatory mechanism. This causes trust issues among consumers and makes the virtual currency more susceptible to be used for illicit practices. Technical glitches are also a cause of fear among consumers and many feel unsafe to invest (Akar and Akar, 2020).

Another major drawback of cryptocurrencies is that, a humongous amount of energy in the form of electricity and computational power is used up in the mining of these digital currencies (Giudici, Milne and Vinogradov, 2020; Li et al., 2019). This suggests that a surge in the number of currencies in the crypto market will prove to be expensive and can lead to an energy crisis as well as issues related to sustainability. There is a massive amount of information on the internet that is not accessible through traditional search engines. This makes information on cryptocurrencies invisible on the surface layer of the internet down this layer, which allows platforms like the Deep Web and Dark Web, which hosts the malevolent sites involved in illegal trading of banned goods like drugs, weapons, etc. through open online anonymous markets like the Silk Road. Reports show that many such sites have been scraped off by the officers yet the veiled world continues to expand. The Onion Router (TOR) or Invisible Internet Project (I2P) are the popular networks through which surfers can gain access to the Dark Web. The tools help users exchange information without revealing themselves (Finklea, 2017).

In order to maintain anonymity, monetary transactions are done using cryptocurrencies (most commonly used is Bitcoin). However, Governments and related agencies utilise the feature of anonymity of Dark Web to conduct online scrutiny and secret online missions. Additionally, cryptocurrencies serve as the most appropriate medium of exchange on the Silk Road which is an online market place where both the buyer and the seller do not reveal their identities. Other examples of such markets include Black Market Reloaded, the Armory, or the General Store. The most popular items on sale are drugs, tranquillizers and medicines like anti-anxiety

drugs and anti-depressants. Other exhibits for sale include weapons, pornography, forged IDs, books, Bitcoins etc. Due to mostly offering prohibited items for sale, the regulatory agencies have exhibited keen interest in putting a check on the Silk Road operations (Christin, 2013).

2.2.5 Types of Cryptocurrencies

Thousands of cryptocurrencies have come into existence like Litecoin, ripples Ethereum, Cardano, Tether, Dogecoin but the pioneer and the most popular among them is Bitcoin. Many of them find their usage as saving instruments though they were not originally designed for the same (Inci and Lagasse, 2019). Cryptocurrencies other than Bitcoins are collectively called altcoins that include Dash, Dogecoin, Ethereum, Ripple, Litecoin etc. and the market trends presented by Akar and Akar (2020) indicate that Bitcoin and alt-coins can soon present themselves as popular unconventional digital payment methods. Some of the cryptocurrencies are discussed in detail as follows.

2.2.5.1 Bitcoin

As seen before Nakamoto (2008) brought in the concept of cryptocurrencies in the form of bitcoin. The circulation of bitcoin started to take place among the enthusiasts from the world of internet. The interest in bitcoin among the people developed and spanned over to such a point that trading in bitcoin started in 2010 in a Japanese online exchange (Wallace, 2011). As of now, bitcoin is unarguably the most widely known cryptocurrency in the world (Prathap, 2021). In the research conducted by Grinberg (2011), they explain that bitcoin was designed and invented with precise rules based on the trading in the gold market. The inventor of Bitcoin termed the users of Bitcoins to be miners that were capable of solving cryptographic problems for the transaction validity. They further stated that the successful solution of the problems led to the reward received in the form of Bitcoin. Following this Yermack (2015) explicated that bitcoin endeavours to overcome the issues associated with the fiat money and the gold-based currencies that function on the basis of algorithms with a limited supply bound by the precision of mathematics. Furthermore, the supply of the bitcoins cannot be regulated or manipulated by any central authority. An interesting aspect highlighted in the research by Möser and Böhme (2015) was that the reward over Bitcoin falls to zero when there are 21 million bitcoins minted and there shall not be any further creation of this cryptocurrency. As

an outcome of the limited number of issuance of Bitcoins, the expansion of this currency is within a controlled pace.

According to (Böhme et al., 2015), software to use bitcoin can be downloaded freely and the implementation involves a variety of features. The creation of a wallet for the user enables storing of bitcoins without requiring a proof of identity or name which helps in enhancing the anonymity of this cryptocurrency. Their research further explains that tracing of transactions of bitcoin is quite easy due to its dependency on the blockchain technology. The nodes in the bitcoin network play the role of trusted third party and a copy of the ledger of transactions is maintained and updated on all the nodes involved. Once acknowledged in the network the transactions are irrevocable (Bamert et al., 2013). The transfer of the coins is enabled through the digital signing of the owner with the public key being available with the owner (Nakamoto, 2008). The following figure depicts the transaction chain of a Bitcoin.

Figure 2.6 Generation of Bitcoin (Nakamoto, 2008)

The issue identified in the transaction illustrated above was the lack of verification feature available to the users or owners while spending the coins. This issue was proposed to be resolved with the inclusion of a timestamp server. The hash would be time stamped and this will be published widely for presenting the existence of specific data on a specific time and reinforcement of this helped in gathering the solution for the owners (Nakamoto, 2008).

Further regarding the issues with bitcoin, research conducted by Moore and Christin (2013) on 40 Bitcoin exchanges determined that the Bitcoin is more volatile as compared to the hard currencies because of their presence solely in the digital wallets which are more exposed to hackers. The anonymity of the virtual transactions results in the inexistence of the transaction fees and this makes it difficult for the developers to control and issue. Additionally, Natarajan, Krause and Gradstein (2017) depicted that Bitcoin design is an outcome of the anti-censorship ideology developed amongst the users of dark web and supporters of techno-libertarianism. This cryptocurrency has increased concerns and security issues for the governments because no centralised authority is responsible for the working of Bitcoin. Regardless of these issues, bitcoins continue to endure in the market in spite of the shortcomings like no usage in providing loans and finance, no spending through credit or debit cards as they are not operated through bank accounts, rather used via “digital wallets” (Yermack, 2015).

2.2.5.2 Litecoin

The Litecoin is considered to be a strong competitor of Bitcoin. It was founded in October 2011 by Charles Lee who rated Litecoin as silver metaphor if Bitcoin is accessed as gold in the virtual currency market. Gonzalez (2015) explains that Litecoin was created as an alternate of bitcoin to produce four times the coins that bitcoin produces in order to prevent it from becoming insufficient and expensive, for making the transaction process quicker, and also allowing the general public to mine coins. This cryptocurrency uses script cryptographic technique and Proof of Work mechanism and similar to bitcoin, it is not under any central authority control (Aggarwal and Kumar, 2020). A total of only 21 millions of Bitcoins can be programmed but the Litecoin caps supply at 84 million coins (Haferkorn and Quintana Diaz, 2015). Research conducted by Miglietti, Kubosova and Skulanova (2019) on the volatility of the Euro, Bitcoin and Litecoin determined that the volatility of Litecoin is more than the Bitcoin. They further showed that Litecoin have transaction fees which are fraction of that of bitcoin. Additionally, they explain that bitcoin is exchanged on all exchanges whereas Litecoin is not traded on all, but most of the exchanges.

2.2.5.3 Ethereum

Ethereum was launched by Vitalik Buterin in a paper that covered the shortcomings of Bitcoin’s coding. Attributes like Turing completeness were attached to Ethereum which denotes that it enables all types of calculations together with loops. It uses GHOST (Greedy

Heaviest Observed Subtree) protocol to meet the problem of left over non performing blocks. (Vujicic, Jagodic and Randic, 2018). Ethereum is a decentralised computing platform for which the token called Ether is visualised not as a currency but as a simulation to functionalise “world computer” by establishing a base for Ethereum users to take part in different events through smart contracts. (Kim et al., 2018). Ethereum uses GHOST (Greedy Heaviest Observed Subtree) protocol and stresses on laying a platform that gives base to develop DApps or decentralised applications on blockchain. The non performing blocks termed as “Uncles” are included in the blockchain and the rewards are issued to the respective miners. In the case of Ethereum the interval between blocks is maintained around 10 to 20 seconds and the size of a block is decided by carrying out a charge known as “gas” which tends to alter with time (Gencer et al., 2018).

Ethereum’s supply has become deflationary and this indicates that this cryptocurrency has the potential of reducing the value of Bitcoins by half. The utility of Ethereum could be higher than Bitcoin with the surpassing of this value (Bambrough, 2021). Additionally, Inci and Lagasse (2019) presented that Ethereum since its creation in 2014 has been considered as the tool of smart contracts which are used for decentralisation of applications. This cryptocurrency is more gainful in comparison to other such currencies and also improved applications can be created using its feature of in-built programming language. Furthermore, the developers are also working towards slashing down the energy consumed for producing Ethereum (Fairley, 2019) and this could bring about a boon in the cryptocurrency market.

2.2.5.4 Ripples

Operations of Ripple are conducted by Ripple Labs and it is an alternative cryptocurrency, built on an open-source platform which is decentralised and runs on credit networks. The nodes in a Ripple network can assume three kinds of roles. They can behave as users which can send and get payments. Another role is of market makers who facilitate trade and the third role is that of servers that are responsible of running consensus protocol for Ripple so that the transactions can be tested and authenticated (Armknecht et al., 2015). According to the research conducted by Philip, Chan and Peiris (2018), the Ripples is only one such cryptocurrency which doesn’t involve any credit risk and counter party risks. It has greater safety and therefore, Ripples is often used by large corporations and banks for their technological infrastructure. Further, the minimum exchange rate volatility risk for Ripples

makes them more in demand as compared to the other cryptocurrencies with higher leveraging effect and volatility (Phillip, Chan and Peiris, 2018).

2.2.5.5 Dogecoin

Dogecoin is named after a famous online meme, Doge and it began as a comic story in 2013 but very soon gained fame as one of the most admired altcoins (Gonzalez, 2015). Billy Markus, a programmer from Portland, Oregon designed Dogecoin as “fun cryptocurrency”. The configuration of Dogecoin is founded from pre-existing cryptocurrency Luckycoin which in turn was derived from the design of Litecoin. Initially it was proposed that only 100 billion Dogecoins would be supplied, but afterwards it was declared that there would be no limit and the supply would be endless (Chohan, 2021). The reasons for the magnetism of Dogecoin are its light hearted culture and lesser obstructions in initial investment and obtaining it. Furthermore, it also has high transaction processing speed. (Chan et al., 2017)

2.2.6 Impact of Covid-19 pandemic on cryptocurrencies

Without a doubt, the Covid-19 outbreak has significantly affected the world economy. In such a manner, sales have decreased, the production has declined and consumer behaviours have also changed (Béjaoui et al., 2021). Such changes in global economy and even in the stock markets are bound to have an impact on the cryptocurrencies market. Where all conventional financial resources appeared to lose esteem unreservedly, a great deal of investors were observing intently the conduct of these advanced cryptocurrencies, particularly the Bitcoin during this upsetting period of Covid19 pandemic. Cryptocurrencies which began simply as a peer-to-peer framework, have arisen as a significant class of assets (Iqbal et al., 2021; Corbet et al., 2019).

The research conducted by Jabotinsky and Sarel (2020) observed that during the first year of Covid crisis the crypto market registered a boom. This uprise can be attributed to the fact that these currencies can be dealt with online from all over the globe even during the lockdown when trading at stock markets and exchanges is not feasible. The scholars Jabotinsky and Sarel (2020) further mention that another reason for a pull towards cryptocurrencies is that these are free from the control of regulatory bodies and hence independent of political jeopardises during pandemic. Counter to the above point, it is expected that investors who have a high

net-worth and extensive experience in financial markets may fictitiously raise the demand to attract new investors and then sell off their portions on high prices. This may also draw the attention of malicious players and people may refrain from investing in crypto market.

The researchers Lahmiri and Bekiros (2020) conducted a big number of vigorous tests and reached to the conclusion that in the course of pandemic the cryptocurrency markets have suffered considerable oscillations as compared to the world stock markets. Furthermore, Conlon, Corbet and McGee (2020) carried out experimental investigations on Bitcoin, Ether and Tether during pre and initial period of Covid19 outbreak. They suggested that out of the three coins mentioned, only Tether qualifies to be a secure refuge in terms of downside risk hedging attributes, but these features seem to be inconsistent over the period of time as Tether suffered humungous short-term losses as a result of unsteady attachment with the US Dollar.

As debated for long in the financial world, printing of more fiat currency tends to raise inflation and reduce the worth of money. However, cryptocurrencies rule out the possibility of increasing inflation as they have a predetermined number of coins, 21 million coins in case of Bitcoin. The Covid times have given a great opportunity to test this argument because a large number of countries have input trillions of Dollars as a relief package in the market to sustain the economy. There was a huge boom of 300% in 2020, during the pandemic situation, in the prices of Bitcoin because of rumours of investors collecting digital coins, owing to less rate of interest in the market. The cause of this rise was also assessed to be the investors assuming Bitcoin to act as a hedge against inflation due to Covid – 19 pandemic (Sarkodie, Ahmed and Owusu, 2021). During the commencement stage of Covid – 19 pandemic, the cryptocurrencies performed as traditional assets but then transformed to a hedge as the disease started to get fierce. The research by Demir et al. (2020) advises the investors to consider including crypto coins in portfolios as they would guard their profits due to hedging and also provide a platform for payments and money transfers.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 Technology Adoption Theories

The modern digital world is filled with new innovations, such as cryptocurrencies, that have the potential to revolutionize the world. While some such innovations flourish, several others flounder owing to a lack of acceptance and adoption by consumers. Over the years several theories have been developed in order to better understand the circumstances and factors surrounding consumer behaviour in general, and adoption of novel technologies in particular. In this subsection, some of the prevalent theories of consumer behaviour and technology adoption is reviewed. These theories will serve as the foundation of the research model of this study.

2.3.1.1 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) proposed a Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which aims to explain the connection between the behaviour of an individual and the individual's attitude. This theory was developed due to the research in social psychology on the attitude and behaviour relationship. This theory assumes that the behaviours are volitional in nature and the intentions of the individuals to perform certain behaviour can be said to be the best determinant and predictor for that behaviour. It can be understood in a way that individuals would have strong intentions towards performing an action when they gauge it positively and also when their significant others support them in performing that behaviour (Sutton, 2001). This theory came into being in order to anticipate and describe the conduct of the individuals as well as to comprehend their psychological influences.

It is believed that the individuals act rationally and according to the information present with them, with behavioural intentions being the fundamental element responsible for their conduct (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980). In this theory it is considered that behavioural intentions that are predecessors to behaviour, provide with significant direction regarding the possibility that performing a certain action or behaviour will point towards a particular consequence (Madden, Ellen and Ajzen, 1992). Intentions are referred to as the individual's motivations with respect to their intentional efforts in order to conduct a behaviour (Wright, 1998). Antecedents to behavioural intentions are based on two causes which are individuals' attitude towards that behaviour and also subjective norms (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980);

(Chang, 1998). Attitude is referred to as the person's overall opinion towards the likability and non-likability for that behaviour whereas subjective norms signify the perceptiveness of an individual that whether the important people in their life support the performance of that particular behaviour or not (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980). The behavioural beliefs are the presumptions that are the cause of an individual's attitude and normative beliefs are those that lie behind the subjective norms (Ajzen, 1985).

This theory gained extensive attention in the domain of social psychology and has been applied to various situations. It is seen that this theory holds very well under the constraints it provides but it has major limitations including that this theory is applicable only to the voluntary behaviours that do not require a great amount of knowledge or skills. It is also not feasible to apply this theory when more complex behaviours are being studied (Wright, 1998). It does not take into account the determination of those factors that are not in control of the individuals. For example, in several cases, a person is still not in a position to perform such actions even when the intentions to perform those actions are strong enough. Also, it is many times beyond one's capability to achieve certain intentions or outcomes. This theory does not include these circumstances (Sheppard, Hartwick and Warshaw, 1988). Due to these limitations, specifically that many behaviours require knowledge, skills, cooperation and resources to be able to execute them, another theory called the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) was proposed (Sutton, 2001).

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Figure 2.7 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989)

2.3.1.2 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The Theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1985; Ajzen, 1987; Ajzen,1991) was created in order to tackle the limitations of the theory of reasoned action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975) and act as its extension. It was proposed by TPB that volitional behaviour is affected by intentions to execute the behaviour as well as perceived behaviour control (PBC). Thus, here intentions would be a function of subjective norms, perceived behavioural control, and attitude (Sniehotta, Pesseau and Araújo-Soares, 2014). Originally in the theory of reasoned action, chief element is the person's intentions to execute the behaviour and intentions are considered to sum up the factors that affect a behaviour, indicating the efforts that people consent to put in to be able to perform a particular behaviour. In TRA, behavioural intentions can be found to affect behaviour only when the behaviour under study is volitional which means that it depends on the person's will to execute the behaviour or not. Since many behaviours may not meet such requirements as they will depend on the availability of resources like skills, time, cooperation, etc. (Ajzen,1991). In order to predict the behaviours that are not completely volitional in nature, perceived behaviour control was added in the theory of planned behaviour. It provides information regarding the potential limits on behaviours as perceived by the individuals and it also helps in explaining the reasons that intentions are not always the best interpreter of behaviour (Armitage and Conner, 2001). Ajzen (1991) refer to perceived behavioural control as "the perceptions of the ability of the people to perform a certain behaviour".

Theory of Planned Behaviour has attracted substantial interest and has been applied widely in various fields since its development. According to google scholar, research paper by Ajzen (1991) regarding the Theory of Planned Behaviour has over 91 thousand citations, reflecting its widespread importance. A significant amount of literature in diverse fields including cognitive and social Psychology (Aarts, Verplanken and Knippenberg, 1998), health behaviour (Conner, 2001), new technology related behaviour (Pavlou and Fygenson, 2006), environmental science (Paul, Modi and Patel, 2016), entrepreneurship (Lortie and Castogiovanni, 2015), tourism and hospitality (Ulker-Demirel and Ciftci, 2020), sports and physical activity (Blue, 1995), education (Cheon et al., 2012) etc. have applied theory of planned behaviour in their research.

Though theory of planned behaviour is vastly used in several domains, there are many criticisms to this theory. The theory has been said to be rigid since it is based on only four concepts. It does not take into account the role of emotions as well as unconscious effects on behaviour. It also does not consider the influences of past behaviour on future behaviour (Sniehotta, Pesseau and Araújo-Soares, 2014). Some authors like Ogden (2003) have demonstrated that several studies provide various explanations for the validity of the theory even when the results indicate that the models should have been rejected. Another concern with this theory does not evaluate the variability in the behaviour through its measures, for example when people have an intention to act but consequently do not act upon (Sheeran, 2002). Also, there are differences in the individuals' cognitions at the time of filling the questionnaire as opposed to their behaviours in real life. It does not provide accurate prediction of the behaviours.

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Figure 2.8 Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen,1991)

These types of theories only include the well thought and reflective actions and eliminates the influences that are impulsive in nature (Conner, 2020). There are many authors that argue the relationship between the variables of TPB, as they do not reflect the important criteria of

decision-making process. With respect to this consideration, efforts have been made to add constructs to the theory and extend the model (French et al., 2005). Many more models were produced to overcome the limitations of TPB, one of them being Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989). TAM was considered to be one of the best models for predicting behaviour and especially technology related behaviour.

2.3.1.3 Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a theory studying the factors that affect a user's acceptance and adoption of a technology. TAM which was first proposed by (Davis, 1989; Davis, 1993), to study computer usage is a modification and adaptation of psychology-based Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and its extension Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) applied in the domain of information technology adoption (Marangunić and Granić, 2014; Davis, 1989). TAM postulates that the intentions to use the technology are explained by their attitude towards using that particular technology (Davis and Venkatesh, 1996) and the important perceptions about the usability and the effortlessness of using a technology determine the attitude of the individuals towards using that technology (Diop, Zhao and Duy, 2019). As per TAM, an individual's attitude and their intentions of using a technology are primarily influenced by two factors: Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh and Davis, 2000).

Perceived Usefulness (PU) is defined by Davis (1989) as "the extent to which a person believes that adopting a specific technology system would be advantageous to them". A technology with high PU is therefore one for which the individual feels that its use provides a boost in their performance. On the other hand, Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) represents "an individual's views regarding the effort needed to adopt a technology system". A technology that is supposed to be easy to use will be expected to be adopted than the one that is difficult to use (Davis, 1989; Davis, Bogozzi and Warshaw, 1989).

An important point to note is that these factors do not necessarily reveal an objective reality, rather they indicate an individual's subjective opinion concerning the utility and learning complexity of a technology. Hence in TAM, PU and PEOU are not used as substitutes for some objective factors describing actual usefulness and actual ease of use, instead they are independent constructs that incorporate the perceptions and beliefs of the individual (Davis, 1989). The justification behind the use of variables evaluating user's perception rather than

the objective reality is that irrespective of actual usefulness, if perception of the individuals related to the technology are negative about its usefulness, it's very likely that they will not be using it (Alavi and Henderson, 1981). While on the other hand, individuals may adopt technologies that are dysfunctional in reality, if they overestimate the gain in performance that the technology entails (Davis, 1989). It was also observed that theories of motivation were an important theoretical basis for TAM (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh and Davis, 2000).

Motivation can be either extrinsic or intrinsic where "extrinsic motivation" refers to behaviour driven by a desire to achieve a reward or an aim while "intrinsic motivation" signifies the feeling of pleasure or gratification from carrying out the behaviour (Venkatesh, 2000; Atkinson and Kydd, 1997). In the context of TAM, according to Davis (1989), Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1989) and Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1992) perceived usefulness is an extrinsic motivation factor, while Venkatesh (2000) argued that perceived ease of use can be considered to be an intrinsic motivation factor.

Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) derived another important construct of attitude towards using the technology in TAM from the theories of psychology including the theory of reasoned action. Attitude is comprehended as a function of two constructs which are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The characteristics of the system or technology have a direct effect on the two constructs of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use and an indirect effect on the attitude towards using that particular technology (Davis, 1993). Though the construct of attitude was later removed from TAM whereby perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness directly had an influence on behaviour intentions (Marangunić and Granić, 2014), a large number of studies still correspond to the importance of the construct of attitude (Yi, Fiedler and Park, 2006) and determine that it plays a crucial role in assessing the intentions of the users to adopt a system or a technology (Hussein, 2017).

According to the empirical evaluations by Kim, Chun and Song (2009), attitude towards using a technology will fully mediate the influences of the crucial beliefs on behavioural intentions in case where the attitude is rather strong and when the attitude is not strong, it will partially mediate the impact of the important beliefs. Furthermore, Oh, Ahn and Kim (2003) stipulate that attitude is turning out to be an important construct over the years of research and through the continuous efforts of determining the behaviour towards technology. Hence, in

this research the construct of attitude is not removed and is considered relevant for investigating the consumer intentions towards cryptocurrencies.

It can be established that TAM is widely adopted in several studies associated with adoption of technologies, due to its parsimony and robustness (Plouffe, Hullah and Vandenbosch, 2001). It is different from theory of reasoned action since TRA is a theory that is used for studying human behaviour in general while TAM is used specifically for studying usage behaviour towards technology or information systems (Oh, Ahn and Kim, 2003). Further, Hong, Thong and Tam (2006) explain that TAM is parsimonious as it has the capability of explaining the variance in individual's intentions towards the technology adoption and their usage through wide and diverse contexts. As per Mathieson (1991), TAM is extensively selected over other theories including TRA, which was further supported in the research by Venkatesh and Davis (2000) where they specify that extensive theoretical verification as well as empirical validation has been amassed towards approval of TAM over other models like TRA and TPB. Additionally, Manis and Choi (2019) illuminate that TAM can be used for explaining the major elements of acceptance of technology and also to help understand the behaviour of consumers over a wider variety of technologies and across diverse populations despite conserving parsimony and the theoretical justification. All these aspects of TAM, contribute to its enhanced application for the purpose of understanding consumer behaviours towards specific technologies.

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Figure 2.9 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989)

The literature suggests that the far-reaching usage of TAM can be seen in various studies. For instance, it was utilised for understanding the internet usage by Porter and Donthu (2006) where they determined that both perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness tend to have strong effect. Another research by Rauniar et al. (2014) integrated TAM in their research in order to investigate the attitude of users regarding the usage of social media, where they found that perceived usefulness plays an important role. A recent study by Rafique et al. (2020) has explored the behaviour of consumers towards adoption of mobile library applications in Pakistan where they reaffirmed using the statistical method of structural equation modelling that both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use have a strong influence and mediating effects on usage of mobile library applications. Furthermore, TAM has even been used to explore the acceptance of financial technologies (Hu et al., 2019), adoption of fintech in Germany (Stewart and Jürjens, 2018). Besides, integration of TAM has been seen in a few studies where factors associated with cryptocurrency adoption and acceptance have been examined (Nuryyev et al., 2020; Alqaryouti et al., 2020).

Although a large portion of literature suggests that TAM amongst the other theories, is the most favoured for investigating consumer behaviour towards technologies, majority of studies prefer using a modified or an extended version of it (Legris, Ingham and Collerette, 2003). There are certain limitations associated with TAM that are the cause of this. Firstly, TAM does not take into consideration the effect of social influence. This limits the scope of TAM since several studies have exhibited that factors associated with social influence have a significant impact on a user's behaviour intention (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000).

Effect of social influence as measured via the construct subjective norm is also a crucial element of the theory of reasoned action (TRA) on which TAM is based (Ajzen, 1985). Secondly, the original TAM does not incorporate constructs that can be considered as predictors of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. Including such antecedents in the research model allows for a deeper understanding of the factors that affect user's perceptions. This eventually aids in better adapting the system to influence the user's behaviour towards accepting it (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). It is important to incorporate such external factors since they are ultimately responsible for technology usage (Legris, Ingham and Collerette, 2003; Burton-Jones and Hubona, 2006). In addition to all this, the original technology acceptance model is observed to have a low explanatory power. Studies

have found that generally the original TAM is able to explain only around 40% of the variance in the behaviour intention of the user (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008; Venkatesh and Davis, 2000).

A consequence of all these is that, the standard approach in technology adoption research is to focus on finding factors that can be used to modify TAM in order to make the research model more specific to the context of the system being studied (Musa, 2006). In other words, rather than using TAM alone to explain the behaviour intention of an individual, it should be incorporated into a larger model that includes the constructs of TAM as well as other external and internal constructs (Legris, Ingham and Colletette, 2003). According to Venkatesh and Davis (2000) the primary method of identifying such factors to be integrated in the model is by the thorough review of the relevant literature. There are various ways in which such constructs can be appended with the variables of the technology acceptance model to create a modified TAM model.

Factors that modify TAM can be external factors, contextual factors, factors based on other theories, or consequent factors (King and He, 2006). Constructs concerned with the individual can be used as an external factor that affect the belief variables (Burton-Jones and Hubona, 2006). The contextual factors can be factors such as age, gender, culture etc that can moderate the relations between the other constructs (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Factors from other theories allow for the model to become more specific to the system under consideration. This also improves the predictive ability of the model (King and He, 2006). Such factors include subjective norm, risk and trust factors etc. The consequent factors are factors that may be included to study the impact of the outcome variable from TAM. This includes factor such as actual usage which is determined by the behaviour intention (King and He, 2006). In addition to the above approach of modifying TAM by including additional constructs that have an effect on the core constructs of TAM (Marangunić and Granić, 2014), another approach is to extend TAM. In this approach a new general model is created by discarding some of the less significant constructs of TAM and including additional factors that mediate or moderate the relations in the model. Some popular extensions are TAM2 and TAM3 that are discussed below.

2.3.1.4 Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2)

TAM2 was first proposed by Venkatesh and Davis (2000) by considering TAM as the initiating theme for the model. TAM2 aimed to include the constructs related to social influence and cognitive influence. To capture the aspect of social influence, they included the factors of voluntariness, subjective norm, and image (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). Here the subjective norm, taken from TRA, refers to the perception of the individual regarding the opinions of the people important to him regarding his performing the behaviour (Ajzen, 1985). While, voluntariness refers to the extent to which the individuals assume that the acceptance of the technology is voluntary and not compulsory (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). On the other hand, the construct of image is meant to capture the perception of the individual regarding the extent to which they feel that performing the behaviour will positively impact their social status (Moore and Benbasat, 1991; Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). TAM2 also proposes that increasing experience will lead to decrease in the influence of subjective norms on intentions and perceived usefulness. In addition to the social influence factors, TAM2 also incorporates cognitive influence factors. These factors are proposed to be antecedents to perceived usefulness.

Cognitive influence factors are included in TAM2 since Venkatesh and Davis (2000) believed that the perceptions of the individuals regarding the usefulness of a system are determined by their mental comparison of what they require the system for and what it is capable of doing. Their cognitive influence factors are output quality, job relevance, and result demonstrability. The authors also characterised perceived ease of use as a cognitive influence. Job relevance, as the name suggests, refers to the perception of the user regarding how relevant and meaningful the particular system or technology is to the job that they are trying to accomplish using it. Output quality indicates the user's feelings regarding how well the system or technology is able to perform the actions that the job requires. Result Demonstrability refers to the perceptions of users regarding the extent to which using the system or technology leads to and is able to contribute to the results that are eventually observed (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). Apart from the addition of these social and cognitive influence factors in TAM2, the construct of attitude was eliminated and perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were postulated to directly affect the behaviour intention. The figure below shows the TAM2 model.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. (2000) A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. Management Science. Vol.46 (2), pp.186-204.

Figure 2.10 Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2) (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000)

2.3.1.5 Technology Acceptance Model 3 (TAM3)

Another extension of the TAM is TAM3 proposed by Venkatesh and Bala (2008). While TAM2 focused on introducing the factors that affect perceived usefulness, TAM3 further extended this by involving the elements of the construct's perceived ease of use (Venkatesh, 2000). In this sense, TAM3 can also be considered as an extension of TAM2. The antecedents of perceived ease of use were first proposed by (Venkatesh, 2000) in the context of computer adoption. He proposed that these can be classified into two categories anchors and adjustments. Anchors refers to constructs that reflect the individual's beliefs regarding the technology and its usage while adjustments refer to the perceptions of users based on their direct experience with the technology (Venkatesh, 2000).

The constructs that were considered were computer anxiety, computer self-efficacy, computer playfulness, and perceptions of external control. Computer self-efficacy indicates the "individual's belief in their ability to use the technology" while perceptions of external control signify "the extent to which their usage is affected by external factors". Computer anxiety measures "the extent to which the individual is afraid of using the computer".

Computer playfulness is the extent of mental spontaneity in the interactions with the computer (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008; Venkatesh, 2000).

The constructs associated with adjustments are perceived enjoyment, and objective usability. Perceived enjoyment measures the degree to which the user considers using the technology enjoyable, independent of the results from such usage. Objective usability refers to the real, actual amount of work needed to perform the task using the technology rather than the individual's perception of it (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008; Venkatesh, 2000). The figure below shows the TAM3 research model.

Figure 2.11 Technology Acceptance Model 3 (TAM3) (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008)

2.3.1.6 Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

In addition to these extensions of TAM another popular model that originated from TAM is UTAUT which was introduced by Venkatesh et al. (2003). The model consisted of four key constructs that affected the behaviour intention, and four moderating factors that affected the relations between these constructs. The model proposed effort expectancy, performance expectancy, facilitating conditions and social influence which in turn affected the usage behaviour. The effect of these constructs on the intention and usage was moderated by the gender, age, experience of the user, and their perceptions of voluntariness of use. The model is depicted in the figure below.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B. and Davis, F. D. (2003) User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. MIS Quarterly. Vol.27 (3), pp.425–478

(Venkatesh et al, 2003)

Despite the development of TAM2, TAM3, and UTAUT to overcome the drawbacks associated with TAM, it was found that they were less generalizable owing to their lack of parsimony and consequently had less explanatory power (Tang and Chen, 2011). TAM2 consists of 11 constructs, TAM3 has 17 while UTAUT has 10. This makes it unsuitable to modify and adapt these models to suit the requirements for specific technology systems. Adding more constructs to TAM2, TAM3 and UTAUT based on review of the subject literature will make the resulting model very complex. Consequently, TAM is still preferred over these models for

technology adoption research. Furthermore, Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1989) compared TAM and TRA and found TAM to be the better model.

In addition to the above models, another popular theory of innovation adoption is the theory of diffusion of innovation (DOI) proposed by Everett Rogers in his book *Diffusion of Innovation* (Rogers, 1962).

2.3.1.7 Diffusion of Innovation (DOI)

The theory of diffusion of innovation aimed to probe how novel techniques, ideas, or technologies spread and gained widespread adoption. According to Rogers (1995) diffusion refers to the method by which innovations pass via various communication channels over time within a community. Rogers (1976) identified four key factors that characterise any diffusion research. These factors are innovation, communication channels, time, and the social system. Rogers (1995) defines innovation as a system, idea, or an item that is perceived to be original and fresh by the adopter. The novelty of the innovation need not be true in practice but should be perceived as such by the user. In other words, the intention to adopt an innovation is determined by the potential consumer's beliefs regarding that particular innovation (Agarwal and Karahanna, 2000). An important factor affecting the diffusion of innovation is the communication channel via which information about the innovation is spreading. Information channels such as mass media are considerably more effective at spreading awareness about the innovation to a much larger audience, as compared to interpersonal channels. Another important characteristic of innovation diffusion is time (Rogers, 1976). This is in contrast to behavioural research in which time generally doesn't play an important role (Rogers, 1995). The effect of time can be seen in the process of adoption or rejection of the innovation by an individual, or in the rate of adoption of an innovation by a social group. The rate of adoption of an innovation depends on factors such as the relative advantage the innovation has over the idea it replaces, compatibility of the innovation with the extant values and expectations of the adopters, complexity of the innovation, trialability of the innovation, and the observability of the consequences of adoption of the innovation (Rogers, 1995; Solomon, 2016). Finally, the composition of the social system also has a significant role to play in the adoption of innovation. The members of the social system involved in the adoption can be classified on the basis of their innovativeness. This allows for the development of ideal adopter categories.

Rogers (1995) found that the distribution of adopters of innovation approaches a normal distribution. Using the mean and the standard deviation of this normal distribution, five adopter categories were proposed based on the extent of the innovativeness of the user. These categories were innovators, early adopters, early majority, later majority, and laggards. These categories were innovators, early adopters, early majority, later majority, and laggards. The innovators are individuals that lie beyond two standard deviations from the mean of the normal distribution of the adopters, accounting for 2.5% of the people adopting the innovation. These are the risk-taking users that seek out novel products or ideas. They generally tend to have higher educational levels and economic backgrounds (Solomon, 2016). Early adopters refer to individuals within one and two standard deviations of the mean, and are around 13.5% of the adopters. Early adopters share many traits with the innovators, except that they have a stronger concern for social approval, and are more risk averse than innovators. The next group, early majority, account for 34% of the adopters and refer to individuals that are less than one standard deviation from the average adopter (Solomon, 2016). According to Rogers (1995) early majority are usually not in a leadership role within the community but are generally quite social with other members of the social system. Late majority also account for 34% of the adopters and denote the group that embrace the innovation after the average adopter. These individuals generally tend to be sceptical and end up adopting either due to socioeconomic necessity or strong external pressure. The last group to adopt any innovation are the laggards. These constitute the remaining 16% of the adopters. Laggards generally don't have opinion leadership in the community and tend to be traditionalists (Rogers, 1995). The distribution of adopters is shown in the figure below.

Figure 2.13 Distribution of Adopters of Innovation (Rogers, 1995)

While the innovation diffusion theory played an important part in the development of the innovation adoption research, DOI is not quite appropriate for the current study. According to Otieno et al. (2016) DOI considers the adoption of innovation over an extended duration of time through various stages, which while being relevant is not sufficient for a technology adoption study. Also, quantification of diffusion is a very complex and non-trivial task due to the inherent complexity of social systems (Damanpour, 1996). Furthermore, according to Lee, Kozar and Larsen (2003) TAM is more suitable for information technology research. Also, Otieno et al. (2016) posits that DOI is generally recommended for use within the context of an organisation or an enclosed social system with strong opinion leaders that have influence on the technology being accessed by the members of the community. Despite the above issues, DOI highlighted the importance of the innovativeness of the potential users.

In light of this and keeping in mind the advantages of the TAM and its ubiquity in technology adoption research, in the present research a modified TAM approach was followed to understand the consumer's behaviour towards cryptocurrency adoption. In this study, other than the original constructs of TAM, constructs from theories of social-psychology, and risk and trust theory were used to develop the research model. These concepts and theories are further discussed in the next sections.

2.3.2 Psychology and Consumer Behaviour

The factors influencing the behaviour of consumers can be largely categorised into two kinds: external and internal (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). External factors refer to factors such as the group that the individual belongs to or the opinions of the society that influence the consumer's decisions. Social norms, bandwagon effect, culture, reference groups etc. are examples of external factors affecting consumer behaviour (Solomon, 2016). Internal factors, on the other hand, refer to influences arising from the consumer's own thoughts, feelings, and lifestyle (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). The internal factors characterize how individuals perceive the system or service and how they feel about using these and about themselves. The internal factors are primarily rooted in various theories of psychology and are hence also referred to as psychological factors (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). The internal influences that are commonly studied while investigating the effect of psychological

factors on consumer's decision are perception, motivation, attitude, personality, and emotions (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010).

Perception refers to the process wherein an individual decides, arranges, and deciphers the information that they have been exposed to (McGuire, 1976). Motivation signifies the reasons and rationales that lead consumers to behave in the fashion that they do (Solomon, 2016). Attitude represents the cumulative effect of the consumer's thoughts, feelings, and actions (Ajzen, 1987; Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). Attitude is also the most widely studied concept in consumer psychology (McGuire, 1976). The effect of these three internal influences is incorporated into the various consumer adoption theories discussed earlier (Ajzen, 1987; Davis, 1989; Venkatesh, 2000). These theories include the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) etc. The contribution of the remaining internal factors, i.e. personality and emotions, is also investigated in this study and their influences are integrated with the rest of the factors in the TAM.

2.3.2.1 Influence of Personality

The personality of an individual refers to the distinctive and overarching response that the individual tends to display across similar circumstances (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). According to Solomon (2016) personality is the characteristic psychological composition of the individual. In psychology research, the behaviour of an individual has frequently been studied and explained based on the individual's personality (Shropshire, Warkentin and Sharma, 2015). Thus, not surprisingly it has long been theorized that from a consumer behaviour perspective, the consumer's personality plays a crucial role in their decision-making process (Brody and Cunningham, 1968). In order to understand how personality can be utilized for this purpose, it is first imperative to comprehend the psychological underpinning of the theory of personality. Over the course of the years different theories of personality have been proposed. Some of the prominent ones include the psychoanalytic theory of personality, Neo-Freudian theories of personality, and the trait theory (Solomon, 2016).

Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic theory of personality postulates the existence of three components of the mind, the impulsive id, the realist and mediating ego, and the moral and conscientious superego. According to the theory, it is the interaction between these three

that determine the personality and behaviour of individuals (Freud, 1923; Solomon, 2016). In the consumer behaviour context, the Freudian theory of personality signifies the role of unconscious mind in behaviour of the consumer (Solomon, 2016). While the Freudian theory forms the basis of the theory of motivation, it is itself not very relevant from the perspective of studying the behaviour of the consumer.

Influenced by Freud's theory, several new theories of personality were developed that postulated the importance of social relations in the formation of personality (Solomon, 2016). These theories are referred to as the Neo-Freudian theories of personality. Some of the prominent Neo-Freudian's theories studying personality include Karen Horney theory of Compliant, Aggressive, and Detached Individuals, and Carl Jung's theory of analytical psychology (Solomon, 2016). Similar to the Freudian theory, these theories were also subjective in nature and were not very useful in analysing the consumer's behaviour from the marketing perspective (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010).

The trait theory posits that the personality of an individual can be expressed with regards to personality traits. Personality traits refer to the unique and distinguishable features that characterizes and defines a person (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). Trait theory assumes that all individuals have these internal personality traits and these remain consistent over time and situations. It also assumes that these personality traits differ among individuals and can be measured and used to distinguish them (Ajzen, 1987; Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). The trait theory of personality aims to measure these personality traits in a quantitative manner. This makes the trait theory very useful in incorporating the concept of personality in an analytical study of consumer behaviour (Solomon, 2016). This is evident from various studies that have used personality traits to understand the behaviour of consumers (Shropshire, Warkentin and Sharma, 2015; Lu, Yao and Yu, 2005; Brody and Cunningham, 1968).

This approach allows businesses to subdivide the consumers based on their personality traits and thereby better target them and understand their intentions (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). For instance, an individual with an innovative personality will tend to be an early adopter of new services or systems (Rogers, 1995). Therefore, businesses planning to launch a new product would prefer to target such individuals. In the context of technology adoption, such a trait can be measured using the Personal Innovativeness factor (Agarwal and Prasad,

1998). Similarly, proactive consumers would be more likely to go out of their way to seek the products or services they desire. To evaluate this trait, the proactive personality measure proposed by Bateman and Crant (1993) can be used. In this study these two personality traits are utilised in order to understand the user's behaviour towards cryptocurrencies.

2.3.2.2 Influence of Emotions

In addition to personality, another important internal factor that influences the consumer's behaviour is emotions. While the concept of emotion is very familiar to everyone, no preferred definition of emotion exists in psychology research (Cabanac, 2002). Despite this, one may vaguely define emotions as the strong and spontaneous feelings experienced by an individual (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). For a long time, consumers were assumed to be rational actors whose actions were based on the properties of the product or service and the benefits associated with its usage. Emotions were assumed to have little role in their behaviour. Recently though, emotions have been realized to play an important role in determining the consumer's behaviour (Laros and Steenkamp, 2005).

It has been found that products or services that tend to elicit positive consumption emotions tend to be favored over those that elicit a negative emotion (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2010). In the technological context, Venkatesh (2000) claimed that the concept of technological anxiety encapsulates the emotional attributes of technology adoption. According to Saadé and Kira (2006) technological anxiety represents the apprehensions or fears associated with the usage of technology in the mind of the user. While the concept of technological anxiety has been studied in depth in psychology research, it has not been sufficiently explored in technology acceptance context (Venkatesh, 2000).

2.3.3 Concept of Trust and Consumer Behaviour

The concept of trust is cross disciplinary in nature that integrates beliefs from various fields including psychology, economics, organizational behaviour, marketing, information systems, etc. (Mukherjee and Nath, 2003). There are numerous ways in which trust has been characterized in the literature (Fam, Foscht and Collins, 2004). Regarding the perspective of social psychology, the willingness and expectations of an individual or a group that is partaking in a transaction is representative of their trust (Roca, García and Vega, 2009).

Mayer, Davis and Schoorman (1995) defined trust as “the readiness of the individuals to be vulnerable towards the actions of another individual with the belief that a person will act without controlling or monitoring the other person.” According to Moorman, Deshpande and Zaltman (1993) trust is “willingness to rely on an exchange partner in whom one has confidence.” While Chung and Kwon (2009) define trust as an emotion related to security and the feeling where one can become dependable. In the context of consumer satisfaction, Fam, Foscht and Collins (2004) explicate that trust is a dynamic process that takes time to build while providing satisfaction that goes ahead of the effects of the economic outcomes.

Trust is fundamentally seen as a typical component for lessening social intricacy and perceptions of risks by increasing the positive outlook associated with the behaviour of the trustee (Luhmann, 1979; Grabner-Kraeuter, 2002; Wu and Chen, 2005). In order to measure trust as a factor, researchers study the perceptions of trust of an individual in social psychology as well as in other fields (Lyon, Möllering and Saunders, 2012). Perceptions of trust or perceived trust refers to the beliefs of the trustor regarding the competence and integrity of trustee. These perceptions are framed as a trustor deciphers and attributes thought processes of the trustees' activities (Ferrin and Dirks, 2003). Subsequently, perceptions of trust, even though innately inside the trustor, are a component of the connection of trustor and trustee as the trustor is preparing information about the trustee. Although these perceptions might sometimes not provide accurate facts since they are simply the attributed beliefs of the trustor, though they insinuate an information processing model to trust behaviours (Alarcon et al., 2018).

Literature in marketing advocates that trust is a crucial aspect for building relationships from marketing point of view. It is understood as an underlying bond between the businesses and consumers and is crucial for creating customer loyalty and their retention (Yoon, 2002). Several information system studies have examined the significance of trust in e-commerce (Lee and Turban, 2001; Gefen, 2002; Gefen, Karahanna and Straub, 2003; Stewart, 2003). Moreover, trust is considered as a critical factor which influences control and actions of the consumers while they are trading and making transactions over the online platforms (Roca, García and Vega, 2009) as well as in creating business to customer and business to business relationships (Chung and Kwon, 2009).

Research conducted by Jarvenpaa, Tractinsky and Vitale (2000) depicted that online trust of the consumers is generated with the positive interactions that are acquired over websites or on digital platforms. This is due to the reason that online exchanges frequently do not involve synchronous trade of products as well as cash and where spatial and besides transient parcel between exchange associates occurs. Due to the wild rivalry in electronic business sectors the online shopper is immersed with a heap of comparative contributions to browse and further they become overpowered by clashing promoting messages. Having just restricted psychological assets accessible, buyers try to lessen the vulnerability and intricacy of exchanges in electronic business sectors by exerting mental shortcuts. Such a compelling mental alternate way is trust, that can fill in as a system to decrease the intricacy of a person's actions in circumstances where individuals need to adapt to vulnerability (Grabner-Kraeuter, 2002).

Perceptions of trust also play a critical role while adopting new technologies since the adopters are surrounded with many uncertainties including the lack of knowledge regarding the technology as well as the provider of that technology. These types of ambiguities generate susceptibility, making trust crucial in acceptance of technologies (Bahmanziari, Pearson and Crosby, 2016). Furthermore, due to the significance of perceived trust in technology adoption especially in the online transactions taking place through digitised platforms, some of the studies have recognised its importance in understanding the acceptance of cryptocurrencies (Cordero, Sánchez and Cortés, 2020; Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018). It is even observed that many studies have extended TAM by including perceived trust in their studies since the construct of trust is missing in TAM (Xie et al., 2017). As it can be established that trust is a crucial element while studying the acceptance of technologies in the market, this research makes careful consideration to sustain its importance in investigating the acceptance of cryptocurrencies.

2.3.4 Concept of Risk and Consumer behaviour

There is a long-standing interest in risk as a particular property of decision choices. Decisions regarding actions with probabilistic results are known as "risky decisions." Risk in general is defined as "the chance of injury, damage, or loss" (Weber, Anderson and Birnbaum, 1992).

The concept of risk was primarily introduced by Bauer (1960) in marketing studies for investigating the consumer decision making. They explained perception of risk in the sense that actions undertaken bring about the outcomes or effects which cannot be predicted with conviction and some of those consequences might be adverse or undesirable. Consequently, the two essential primary measurements were uncertainties and unfavourable consequences.

Bauer (1960) unequivocally stresses that he is concerned distinctly with emotional or perceptions of risk rather than the real-world concept of risk. Taylor (1974) stipulated the importance of risk in understanding consumer behaviour since risk is believed to be painful and leads to apprehensions. Advancing on this concept, they explain that there are two facets of risks which are uncertainty regarding the outcome and uncertainty regarding the consequences of making that mistake. As per Im, Kim and Han (2008) perceptions associated with risk or the uncertainties have an effect on the assertions regarding the decision-making process of the individuals. They further elucidate that the situations can be said to be risky in nature when the possibility of the outcomes are unknown and even the outcomes might be identifiable or unidentifiable. According to Campbell and Goodstein (2001) the perceptions associated with risk is crucial in social sciences and other related research. It is due to the reason that the constructs of risks are influential in describing the behaviour of consumers since they generally strive to avoid making mistakes rather than maximising the effectiveness or utility in purchasing (Mitchell, 1999).

In the case of purchasing products through virtual platforms or through telephone, the concept becomes important due to the reason that customers do not see the products in person before purchasing them and hence are not able to access their quality (Cox and Rich, 1964 ; Lim, 2003). Furthermore, there are many various categories of risks including physical risk, psychological risk, time risk, social risk, financial risk, performance risk, privacy risk, and personal risk and also their relevance differs across the type of product being studied (Laroche et al., 2004; Hong and Yi, 2012; Lim, 2003). Researchers or academicians and even the practitioners have given significant attention to the construct of risk.

The application of this construct has been observed in numerous studies from diverse fields (Mitchell, 1999). Jarvenpaa and Todd (1996) have looked into various kinds of risks like economic risk, and privacy risk, social risk, performance risk and personal risk. They suggest

that impact on consumer perceptions regarding the online shopping on internet is varied. In a recent marketing study by Zhang and Yu (2020), where they study different types of risk, showed that perceptions associated with those risks have a significant impact on the user adoption. They elaborated that the uncertainties and perceptions of risk have an impact on the intentions of the consumers to purchase or use a product.

Comparative research conducted by Maditinos, Chatzoudes and Sarigiannidis (2013) examined the risk factors that have an impact on the consumer adoption of online banking and found that performance risk and security risks have a negative influence on the consumer acceptance. The concept was even studied in the context of adoption of fintech by Ryu (2018) where the researcher examines the intention of adoptions taking into consideration legal risk, financial risk, security risk, and operational risk where the research indicated that legal risk has a negative influence on the intentions of consumers. Similarly, the elements of risks have been studied in relation to cryptocurrencies by a few researchers (Arias-Oliva, Pelegrín-Borondo and Matías-Clavero, 2019; Low and Teo, 2018). Literature also evokes that several studies have integrated the elements of perceptions of risk from literature with TAM (Featherman and Pavlou, 2003; Wu and Chen, 2005; Lee, 2009; Hu et al., 2019). Given the important and crucial role of risks in identifying consumer attitudes, this research considers the idea of risk and applies it to the adoption of cryptocurrencies.

2.3.5 Concept of Bandwagon Effect and Consumer behaviour

The effects of society on an individual plays a crucial role on their decisions and belief systems. Hence, it becomes essential to comprehend the significance of the external factor of social influence on the individuals. Social influence in this regard is associated with the impact that the people have on the feelings, suppositions, or behaviours of other individuals (Axsen, Orlebar and Skippon, 2013). Social influence has a wide history in the areas of psychology, social science, and marketing. Moreover, social influence is indescribably expansive, that covers everything from simple presence influences to more straightforward kinds of social influences frequently found in consumption settings (Dahl et al., 2013). Various researchers have examined the psychological components that cultivate social influence. One of the notions that constantly appears in this regard is that consumers recognize influence from a

source they associate with and discard those influences that they need to separate from the source (Shalev and Morwitz, 2012).

Research conducted by Pachauri (2001) reiterates that social influence has been studied extensively in social psychology and further states that attitudes of the individuals are prejudiced or affected by the culture, social statuses or classes, and other groups that the users belong to. Thus, it can be claimed that the social forces have a substantial impact on the consumer behaviour and therefore it is necessary to include them while investigating the attitudes of users. As is often observed that in today's social world, people are affected by the thoughts, choices, beliefs and attitudes of the group or communities they are associated with (Escalas and Bettman, 2003). Among the group members, these attributes can affect the choices they make regarding the products, brands or new innovations whether intentionally or unintentionally and therefore reflect on the ideals and beliefs as encouraged by the group. This kind of effect is referred to as "bandwagon effect" (Kang and Ma, 2020). According to Leibenstein (1950), bandwagon effect alludes to "the degree to which the interest for a commodity is expanded due to the reason that others are also using or consuming that same product". It addresses the need of individuals to buy products to be able to get into "the swim of things" or to adjust with individuals they wish to be related with or to be in tune with the trends or style (Leibenstein, 1950). According to Schmitt-Beck (2015) the prerequisite for bandwagon effect is that individuals agree to the collective phenomenon outside the domain of their own experience which cannot be observed directly as a perspective for their attitude and development of inclinations and in this manner, it becomes as real as a social reality.

Bandwagon effect has been seen studied in various fields such as economics (Leibenstein, 1950), fashion industry (Sabir et al., 2020), luxury goods (Tsai, Yang and Liu, 2013), social networking (Xu et al., 2012), adoption of new technology (Lo and Weng, 2012), etc. It has been observed that the bandwagon effect is commonly studied in the domain of elections and voting (Barnfield, 2020; Navazio, 1977). The research conducted by Barnfield (2020) studied the bandwagon effect in the context of voting and described it as a phenomenon that causes change in the voting preferences or decisions shifting to more popular candidates or parties. With reference to luxury goods consumption, the bandwagon effect has been proved to have a distinctive role. For instance, a study by Kastanakis and Balabanis (2012) justifies that bandwagon effect takes place in the luxury goods market and when more customers

purchase those luxurious products due to their recognition by many others, it further creates demands for those products. Additionally, their research conveys that the value of luxury goods is strengthened by emerging from communications among numerous social groups.

Furthermore, importantly bandwagon effect in technology adoption has been analysed by economists according to the viewpoint of network externalities. Wherein a network externality alludes to the positive effect that an additional user of products or services has on the worth of that item to other people. At the point when network externalities are present, the worth of the products or services builds as per the number of other individuals utilizing it (Hong, 2018). Regarding the integration of a social phenomenon like bandwagon to TAM, Rauniar et al. (2014) stipulated that such a psychological concept that is quite essential for consumer behaviour studies has not been a part of TAM. Due to the relevance of bandwagon effect as a social phenomenon and its significance in consumer behaviours, this study pursues the integration of bandwagon effect with the TAM for studying the user behaviour towards cryptocurrencies.

2.4 Consumer Behaviour and Cryptocurrencies: A Comprehensive Literature

2.4.1 General Studies on Cryptocurrencies

Over the years, a large number of studies have examined cryptocurrencies and their influence on different industries and sectors. It was observed that the studies majorly laid focus on the technical aspects and economic impacts of cryptocurrencies. In the last few years research in another facet of cryptocurrency has gained traction (Sanchez, Saura and Aystaran, 2021). Some of the studies in cryptocurrencies took into account factors like popularity, security, value creation of cryptocurrencies. Research by Krombholz et al. (2017) with a large number of survey participants as well as interviews at a later stage explored the experience of the users of bitcoin with respect to privacy, security and anonymity. They investigated the management strategies for bitcoin and the method of managing the risks. They also tried to understand the way users implement the security measures for the protection of the bitcoins and the keys. It was found that many of the participants used web hosted solutions for the

management of bitcoins. It was also determined that many users did not have a clear idea regarding being anonymous and maintain the privacy and security.

Further, a study by Shehhi, Oudah and Aung (2014) investigated the factors behind choosing the cryptocurrencies. They focused on two main questions including the factors that help online in deciding the usage and mining of cryptocurrency and the key criteria that impact the value and popularity of the various crypto coins. Their results indicated that the currency name and logo of cryptocurrency had a major impact on decision making of the users for the purpose of using and mining. Other factors that had an influence on the selection of cryptocurrencies were ease of mining, anonymity, privacy and popularity of the currency, their value. There are studies like (Shanaev et al., 2020) that have studied the regulatory aspects of cryptocurrencies. They determined that strict regulations and government intervention would bring a decrease in the prices of cryptocurrencies but it will also reduce the risks associated with cryptocurrencies and lead to wider adoption.

2.4.2 Technology Adoption Frameworks and Cryptocurrencies

With the rise in awareness of cryptocurrency among the general public, consumer adoption of blockchain and cryptocurrency has turned into an interesting and pertinent topic for investigation. Cryptocurrency research from the perspective of technology adoption theories has been performed with the aim of understanding the adoption criteria, adoption type or the adoption process in various sectors, industries, organisations or by users directly (Sanchez, Saura and Ayestaran, 2021). Theories regarding acceptance of technology examine the decisions and choices that the individual makes with regards to rejecting or embracing the technology under investigation (Sobhanifard and Sadatfarizani, 2019). In these theories individual perceptions and opinions are considered as the main determinants of adopting new technological innovations. These alludes to individuals' cognitive translations of innovation and themselves (Talukder, 2012). Within this context several studies have been conducted that have looked into cryptocurrency adoption by consumers, exploring the factors that motivate users to make the decisions of adopting cryptocurrencies. Most of these studies have integrated the technology acceptance theories and models such as TAM, UTAUT, DOI, etc in their research for analysing the user's behaviour. In addition to the factors intrinsic to these technology adoption theories, several academicians have modified and extended these theories by examining and incorporated various other constructs. These constructs stem from

theories such as theory of trust and risk providing perceived trust, perceived risks etc, Socio-psychological theories leading to constructs such as personality factors and social influence etc.

The paper produced by Mendoza-Tello et al. (2019) is a noteworthy research that aimed at examining the impact of cryptocurrencies on trust and acceptance as perceived by the users with respect to the transactions that take place in e-commerce. Evaluation was conducted using PLS SEM method. This research proposed a model using the variables from TAM and adding factors of perceived risk and trust. Their findings demonstrated that perceived usefulness proves to have a strong influence on intentions to use cryptocurrencies and perceived risk, perceived trust and perceived ease of use do not prove as strong predictors. Diffusion of Innovation theory was deployed by Presthus and O'Malley (2017) for investigating the motivations as well as barriers of adopting cryptocurrencies among two groups of users and non-users. They observed that motivations of the users were not because of any monetary or other kind of influences rather they exhibited technical curiosity. Regarding the non-users, they found out that they also showed interest in the cryptocurrencies but also questioned the advantages and security aspects of cryptocurrencies. Also, the group of non-users waited for others to begin using bitcoin.

Jonker (2019) looked into the factors that have an influence on the adoption of payments by cryptocurrencies among the online retailers. They considered two dependent variables including adoption intention and acceptance. Other constructs that were considered in the study were consumer demand for cryptocurrency payments, exchange rate risk, perceived ease of use, perceived compatibility. Further, it was observed that the retailers showed interest in adopting cryptocurrencies in the future pointing out that their acceptance will advance when there is reduction in some perceived barriers. Similar study by Roussou, Stiakakis and Sifaleras (2019) that investigated the adoption of digital currencies from a commercial perspective. It incorporated TAM combined with an innovation process model. Additionally, it inserted other variables of perceived security for identifying the factors that influence the user adoption. It was determined that perceived usefulness and perceived security are the major factors that have a direct effect on the acceptance of digital currencies commercially and compatibility had an indirect impact. Also, it was identified that perceived

ease of use does not have a significant effect on perceived usefulness as well as on actual usage.

Baur et al. (2015) in their qualitative research explored questions regarding the advantages and disadvantages of bitcoin, the factors that drive the adoption of bitcoin and the factors that become the barriers. They also studied the future potential from the perspectives of the users. They incorporated technology acceptance models in their study and other constructs like subjective norms. Their findings revealed that perceived ease of use is relatively low due to the issues involved with the usability of storage, implementation and transfer of mobile wallets as well as the risks associated with cryptocurrencies. With respect to perceived usefulness, they found out that it had an impact on adoption due to the lower cost and faster payments. Subjective norms had lesser influence on the adoption and future potential is still considered low and was advised that educating masses about bitcoin can help them embrace cryptocurrencies.

Another research by deploying TAM and other constructs like security and control and transaction processing, in their research delved into the factors of adoption of bitcoin in China (Nadeem et al., 2021). They collected data from a large sample of 385 respondents from China. In their findings, they showed that both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use have a direct positive influence on intentions to use bitcoin. They further presented that perceived usefulness acts as a mediating variable between intention to use bitcoin and perceived ease of use. Their results also presented that the security control does not show a strong statistical impact on perceived usefulness while transaction processing and perceived ease of use have a significant relationship with perceived usefulness.

2.4.3 Trust and Risk Factors and Cryptocurrencies

It was seen that trust and risk are also important factors while studying cryptocurrencies adoption among consumers. In a study by Arli et al. (2020) that focuses on perceptions of consumers regarding cryptocurrencies, found out that awareness of cryptocurrencies, speedy transactions as well as trust in government are the major factors that promote to trust in cryptocurrencies by consumers. It means that the consumers with knowledge and understanding of the cryptocurrencies have more trust in them. It was also evident that the

consumers have more trust in cryptocurrencies when there are government regulations associated with them, therefore trust in the government will lead to trust in cryptocurrencies.

Cordero, Sánchez and Cortés (2020) focused on the factors that affect the intentions of usage of cryptocurrencies from the users in Spain. They developed a model comprising of different variables from various models and these were performance expectancy, trust, perceived risk, electronic word of mouth, quality of the website and behavioural intentions. Among these variables, it was found out that the trust and performance expectancy had a strong influence on behavioural intentions of the consumers of cryptocurrencies. Further, the results revealed that electronic word of mouth had more influence on trust than perceived risk and web quality.

Jung et al. (2018) applied UTAUT is a comparative study between Korea, China and Vietnam. This study was conducted to identify the factors affecting the usage of cryptocurrencies. They also enhanced the model by adding other important elements like government regulation, risk, economic feasibility, and payment convenience. They incorporated perceived risk theory and theory of cultural differences by countries in their study. It was further demonstrated that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social expectancy and facilitating conditions all had positive influence on intention of using cryptocurrencies.

Ermakova et al. (2017) focused on the advantages and disadvantages of bitcoin. They surveyed the bitcoin experts and applied the diffusion of innovation theory for identifying the factors of adoption of bitcoin. They ascertained that the factors relating to anonymity and security form important elements under both advantages and challenges in adoption of bitcoin. Vulnerability, lack of trust and risks associated with bitcoins were observed as other challenges in their adoption. The demographics of the study also displayed that there were more male users than female users.

Another interesting research produced by Abramova and Böhme (2016) is an exploratory study that investigates the key influences of adopting bitcoin as a method of online payment and legal money transfers and making purchases. It draws upon from the Technology Acceptance Model while integrating other variables like perceived risk and perceived benefits. This study demonstrated that there were significantly large number of mal users than female users. The findings suggested that perceived ease of use did not have a significant

impact on the usage, perceived risk had a negative and significant impact on usage, while perceived benefit did not have a significant impact on usage.

Similarly, Shahzad et al. (2018) addressed the adoption of cryptocurrencies, specifically bitcoin where the participants belonged to mainland China. They have also incorporated TAM in their study along with other constructs including awareness and perceived trustworthiness for examining the adoption of bitcoin as a method of exchange, explicitly in China. The study produced a model using SEM and the findings explained that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, awareness, and perceived trustworthiness all had a positive relationship with intentions of using bitcoin. Awareness and perceived trustworthiness came out to be significant factors.

2.4.4 Psychological and Social Factors and Cryptocurrencies

Psychological factors and other social facets are also given importance while studying the intentions of adopting cryptocurrencies. A study by Kim (2021) was conducted to understand the behavioural intentions towards using bitcoin, incorporating theory of planned behaviour and expanding their model along with other psychological constructs such as anxiety, distrust, quality, retention time, financial self-efficacy, power prestige, etc. Their findings suggested that there was a significant impact of perceived behavioural control on anxiety, distrust, power prestige, retention time and quality.

Abbasi et al. (2021) performed a study to comprehend the factors that can enable in understanding the behavioural intentions of adopting cryptocurrencies. They deployed a version of UTAUT model along with some unique constructs like personal innovativeness as well as trust. The analysis for this study was conducted by using SEM as well as Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and further deploying deep learning based dual stage SEM and ANN methods. The results displayed that trust was the strongest predictor for influencing the user intentions. In their findings, they also suggested that performance expectancy and price value had a positive impact on the behavioural intentions of the users. With respect to personal innovativeness, it was found out that it had a positive and moderating role between the two constructs of price value and performance expectancy.

Saiedi, Broström and Ruiz (2020) carried out a study to explore the growth of cryptocurrencies, specifically bitcoin and worldwide digital infrastructure. They studied the impact of financial, legal, criminal and other social factors in the adoption of bitcoin. They identified that adoption of bitcoin was mainly influenced by the perceived failings of present financial institutions, including the distrust by society in banks and overall financial systems as well as the risk-taking capacity of the entrepreneurs. They also advocated that the growth and spread of bitcoin is also related to its ability of allocating speculative or unlawful business activities. By using social commerce and social support theory along with TAM, Mora et al. (2018) analysed the role of social media in developing trust and the intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies for making payments electronically. Regarding the collection of data for their research, a survey was designed in which there were 125 participants. It was observed that usage of social commerce has a positive impact on trust and intention to use cryptocurrencies and it reduces the perceived risk. Further it was seen in the study that mutual support does not sufficiently generate trust to be able to advocate perceived usefulness for cryptocurrencies.

From the above literature, it can be established that most of the research that looks into the adoption of cryptocurrencies have majorly studied bitcoins as they are the most popular cryptocurrencies. In spite of growing trends of cryptocurrencies and advancement in the technologies, there is still a dearth of research conducted on cryptocurrencies from the viewpoint of the consumers. This research is an endeavour that studies adoption of all kinds of cryptocurrencies thoroughly and takes into account various factors that can have an impact on users' decision of adopting cryptocurrencies. Through the literature, it was also assessed that TAM has been a widely adopted theory along with other constructs to examine the adoption of cryptocurrencies. Following this, the theory of TAM is integrated with other relevant factors for understanding the factors of adoption of cryptocurrencies.

2.5 Research Gaps Identified in Literature Review

Through the literature review, it was observed that a large number of studies on cryptocurrencies, predominantly bitcoin, have researched the security and technical elements associated with cryptocurrencies (Barber et al., 2012; Reid and Harrigan, 2013). The

major gap identified here is that most academic research in cryptocurrencies has focused on the technical, financial or the economic aspect of it whereas there is a lack of literature investigating consumer behaviour towards cryptocurrencies.

The research presented by Ajzen (1991), Davis (1993), Venkatesh et al (2003), and several others depicted the multiple constructs and theories which would be influencing the consumer's behaviour and their acceptance towards new technologies. These studies have indicated that consumer behaviour can be easily tracked through the identification of factors that would be influencing their purchase intentions and attitudes. However, it was observed that the technology acceptance model by Davis (1989), does not include any emotional or socio psychological factors (Bagozzi, 2007) or factors associated with perceptions of trust and risk (Pavlou, 2003) for examining the behaviour of consumers towards adoption of new technologies. Furthermore, in the exploration of cryptocurrency research, it was observed that there hasn't been any multifaceted comprehensive study simultaneously examining the effect of trust, risk, socio-psychological factors, and personality traits on the adoption of cryptocurrencies. Most importantly, although the bandwagon effect has been widely discussed in the non-academic discourse surrounding cryptocurrencies, there hasn't been any proper research investigating adoption of cryptocurrencies based on the bandwagon effect. Also, psychological elements that have been distinguished as affecting adoption decisions incorporate innovativeness and proactive personalities.

In simple terms, it can be established that many studies in innovation adoption and consumer behaviour domains have investigated the attitude of consumers towards various technologies but regarding the cryptocurrencies there are studies that seek out their technical and economic aspect and not enough academic literature that inquire about the behaviour of consumers regarding them from a multidisciplinary angle. This study therefore includes criteria like trust, risk, social influence, personality traits along with well-known constructs of TAM to understand the influence on decisions regarding adoption of cryptocurrencies.

Chapter 3 Hypotheses Development

3.1 Overview of the Chapter

The previous chapter reviewed the extant literature concerning cryptocurrencies, technology adoption frameworks, and consumer behaviour studies. Based on these theories and concepts, the development of hypotheses corresponding to various constructs takes place in this chapter. Following this a brief outline of the conceptual framework of this study is presented.

3.2 Intention to adopt

As defined by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) intentions are the indications of individuals' willingness to perform a particular behaviour. They have further defined intentions as "a person's location on a subjective probability dimension involving a relation between oneself and some action". Corresponding to the theory of reasoned action, the most immediate cognitive antecedent of any kind of behaviour to be studied is the intention to perform that particular behaviour (Ajzen and Fishbein, 2005). This means that if a person has strong intentions, they are more likely to try to perform that behaviour and therefore there is greater probability that the behaviour will actually be performed (Ajzen and Madden, 1986). A large number of studies verified the predictive validity of behavioural intentions which implies that specific behaviour can be anticipated with extraordinary precision from the intentions to perform the behaviour under investigation (Ajzen and Fishbein, 2005). There is a clear distinction between attitude and intentions and rather there is a strong relationship between the two. It can be said that if a person has a favourable attitude towards a behaviour, they are more intended to perform that behaviour. Furthermore, intentions are considered to be the "conative" element of the construct of attitude (Leone, Perugini and Ercolani, 1999; Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975).

Ajzen (1988) has explained that the intentions are the direct functions of the social and personal variables, primarily the attitude towards the behaviour, a personal interpretative response, subjective norms as explained in theory of reasoned action or else a perceived

social behaviour construct. All kinds of external variables or constructs on intentions are mediated through attitude towards the behaviour or personal or social behaviour constructs like subjective norms (Leone, Perugini and Ercolani, 1999). Studying the behavioural intentions is the ultimate aim as it assists in understanding the user acceptance or rejection of a technology (Davis, 1989). Within the context of cryptocurrencies, the relevant behaviour that this study is trying to understand is adoption of cryptocurrencies, hence the construct of behaviour intention has been adapted into the construct intention to adopt. It is assumed that attitude towards using cryptocurrencies will directly influence the intentions to adopt them (Schaupp and Festa, 2018). This means that if a person has a positive attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, their intentions will be more likely to use them and if they have a negative attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, they would be less likely to have intentions to use them. Besides these, most other external variables except social behaviour variables will influence the intentions through attitude towards cryptocurrencies.

3.3 Attitude towards using cryptocurrencies

An enormous number of methods have been used for predicting and understanding the behaviour of consumers and the construct of attitude has been found to play a very important role to play in this regard (Leone, Perugini and Ercolani, 1999). The importance of attitude can be gauged from the fact that in the field of social psychology attitude was once considered to be the fundamental factor for understanding human behaviour (Ajzen and Fishbein, 2005). As per Ajzen & Fishbein (1980) in their theory, attitude is defined as an “individual’s positive or negative feelings towards performance of a certain behaviour” which means that attitude expresses whether a person is in favour or against the performance of the particular behaviour (Ajzen and Madden, 1986). Adapting the construct of attitude to the context of technology adoption, Davis (1986) proposed the construct “attitude towards using a technology”. Davis (1991) defined attitude towards using a technology in TAM as “the degree of evaluative affect that a person relates with using the target technology or system in their job”.

As per Theory of Reasoned Action, the attitude towards a behaviour is influenced by the individual’s belief towards the behaviour and their evaluations of the consequences of

performing it (Ajzen, 1985). In the technology acceptance model the beliefs evolved into the factors perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989). Along with these belief factors affecting the attitude, a common approach to constructing extensions of these theories is by incorporating external factors that are postulated to affect the attitude and its antecedents ((Wu and Chen, 2005; Park and Kim, 2014; Lee, 2009). In addition to this, there has been considerable research conducted for studying the relation between attitude and behaviour intention or intention to adopt (Leone, Perugini and Ercolani, 1999). The relation of attitude with intention implies that rest remaining equal, individuals develop intentions of performing certain behaviour towards which they have positive affect (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989).

The cognitive responses have an influence on affective responses of the users i.e. attitude towards the use of technology, and ultimately the attitude, drives the behavioural intentions towards using the technology (Holden and Rada, 2011). It has been found through the literature survey that attitude is the strongest predictor of intention to adopt or use (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989); (Holden and Karsh, 2010); (Ajzen and Fishbein, 2005). With respect to cryptocurrencies for example if the individual believes that transacting in cryptocurrencies will not have adverse effects, it is likely that the intention towards transacting would be higher. Whereas, when an individual deems that transacting in cryptocurrencies will be risky or will have adverse effects, the intentions to transact would be quite low (Schaupp and Festa, 2018). Keeping these in consideration, hypothesis regarding the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies is developed as:

H1: Attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT) positively affects the intention to adopt (IA) them

3.4 Perceived Usefulness

Based on the literature, it was observed that technology acceptance model has been widely used to study the adoption of various new technologies (Venkatesh and Davis, 1996). Perceived usefulness is one of two key constructs of Technology Acceptance Model which has been broadly recognised in adoption of technology. Davis (1989) defined perceived

usefulness as “the degree to which an individual deems that using a specific technology or system would enable in enhancing their job performance”. It indicates that by the use of such technology, it would be easier to complete the given task at hand. With respect to this study, perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which an individual assumes that by using cryptocurrencies, whether as a method of payment or investment, it will enhance their performance (Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018).

Perceived usefulness is associated with the usage of the particular technology and is considered as a crucial and significant factor while evaluating the attitude of users towards the adoption of innovative technologies (Calisir et al., 2014; Tan and Teo, 2000). It focuses on various aspects of the innovative technology including the performance, efficiency, effectiveness, productivity, and quality as well as the need and usefulness of the technology, and in this case cryptocurrencies (Grover et al., 2019).

It is explicated in large number of studies including the studies in fintech (Hu et al., 201; Hsu, Wang and Lin, 2011), that perceived usefulness has a significant impact on the intention to adopt a technology (Chen and Barnes, 2007; Venkatesh, 2000). In a large number of studies, it is hypothesised that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant impact on attitude (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989). According to this, it has been assumed in this study that perceived usefulness will have a significant and a positive impact on attitude towards adoption of cryptocurrencies (Albayati, Kim and Rho, 2020) as well as on intention to adopt (Shahzad et al., 2018). This means that the greater the perceived usefulness of cryptocurrencies, the more positive will the attitude be towards them which will then lead to an increase in the intention to adopt them.

Also, technology acceptance model theorises that perceived usefulness will be influenced by perceived ease of use, reason being that if the technology is easier to use, it will therefore be more useful (Venkatesh, 2000). In the context of this study, it means that if the individuals believe that the use of cryptocurrencies is easy then they are more inclined to feel that cryptocurrencies are useful for them (Nadeem et al., 2021). Furthermore, Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1989) elucidate that any other external variables such as perceived risk or perceived trust that need to be added to improve the technology acceptance model will have an influence on perceived usefulness. In the light of the above-mentioned observations, for this study it is hypothesized that:

H2: *Perceived usefulness (PU) of cryptocurrencies positively affects the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT)*

H3: *Perceived usefulness (PU) of cryptocurrencies positively affects intention to adopt cryptocurrencies (IA)*

3.5 Perceived Ease of Use

Perceived ease of use is another construct of the technology acceptance model and has been extensively used for studying the usage behaviour of technological innovations (Venkatesh and Davis, 1996; Venkatesh, 2000). It refers to the degree to which an individual has a belief that using a particular technology will be easy to use or would not require much effort. It is taken from the definition of the word “ease” which means “freedom from difficult or large amount of effort” (Davis, 1989). It means that an individual is likely to use a particular system or technology when it is easier for them to use it, or the interaction with that innovation does not require too much effort (Thong, Hong and Tam, 2004). Perceived ease of use is associated with the estimations of the essential traits of technology such as ease of use, ease of learning, simplicity and flexibility of the user interface (Gefen and Straub, 2000). The prominence of perceived ease of use is backed up by the theory of self-efficacy by Bandura (1982); (Davis, 1989). In the light of this study, perceived ease of use is understood as “the degree to which an individual believes that using cryptocurrencies is effortless, demonstrating the amount of effort needed to use cryptocurrencies” (Mora et al., 2019).

Extensive amount of literature suggests that perceived ease of use has a significant indirect effect on intention of using a technology (Ramayah and Lo, 2007; Venkatesh and Morris, 2000). The effect of perceived ease of use on the intention is mediated via perceived usefulness and attitude (Davis, 1991). Various studies have determined that perceived ease of use has an impact on attitude (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989; Buabeng-Andoh, 2018; Holden and Rada, 2011; Calisir et al., 2014). It means that if the technology is easy to use, individuals will have a positive attitude towards its adoption. Regarding the perspective of this study, it is supposed that perceived ease of using cryptocurrencies will have a positive effect on attitude towards using them (Albayati, Kim and Rho, 2020). In TAM, while this effect

of ease of use on attitude is significant it is often found to be much weaker as compared to the impact of perceived ease of use on perceived usefulness or the impact of perceived usefulness on attitude (Davis, 1991).

It is also seen that it has a noteworthy and positive influence on perceived usefulness (Wang et al., 2003). The indirect effect on intention via perceived usefulness suggests that if the technology is easier to use, it is more likely to be useful (Venkatesh and Morris, 2000). For cryptocurrencies, the perception regarding how effortless it is to use them, positively affects the attitude of individuals towards using them (Roussou, Stiakakis and Sifaleras, 2019). This means that the perceived usefulness of the cryptocurrencies will enhance if the individuals believe that using cryptocurrency does not require too much effort and is easy to use (Nadeem et al., 2021). Moreover, similar to perceived usefulness, factors external to the technology adoption model will have an impact on the perceived usefulness (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989). Although, according Venkatesh and Davis (2000) external factors will mostly act on perceived usefulness rather than perceived ease of use. Based on the above the hypothesis framed are as follows:

H4: *Perceived ease of using cryptocurrencies (PEOU) has a positive effect on the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT)*

H5: *Perceived ease of using cryptocurrencies (PEOU) has a positive effect on the perceived usefulness of cryptocurrencies (PU)*

3.6 Perceived Trust

Trust has been defined by Mayer, Davis and Schoorman (1995) as a behavioural characteristic which is based on the beliefs of one person regarding the characteristics of another person. With reference to the usage of technologies, it relates to the level of confidence, comfort and security that individuals experience while using the technologies (Albayati, Kim and Rho, 2020). Importance of trust has been recognised in various fields such as social psychology, e-commerce, e-banking, marketing, management, organisational behaviour technology adoption, etc. (Roca, García and Vega, 2009). Perceived Trust is considered to be a critical factor when studying the adoption or usage of technologies or systems, banking, commerce

and social media (Hansen, Saridakis and Benson, 2018). For online banking, it was found that higher the consumer's trust in using online banking systems, higher was their inclination towards using the e-banking service (Bhattacharjee, 2002).

In the domain of e-commerce, an individual's willingness to use a particular e-commerce website was found to be strongly related to the individual's trust in that online business (Roca, García and Vega, 2009; George, 2002; Mukherjee and Nath, 2007). These indicate that individual's perception of the trustworthiness of cryptocurrencies play an important role in their intention to adopt it (Cordero, Sánchez and Cortés, 2020). This is understandable since cryptocurrencies are based on a novel online distributed ledger technology and hence trust in the system or the cryptocurrency transactions is an important aspect that should be investigated. There might be various reasons for lack of trust in cryptocurrencies which might become a major factor for consumers not accepting them. Also, the role of trust becomes even more important in case of transactions made through e-services since the degree of insecurity in the virtual world makes the consumers vulnerable (Roca, García and Vega, 2009). This is also due to the lack of face-to-face interaction of the consumers with the e-vendor in online businesses (Gefen, Karahanna and Straub, 2003) or seller in case of cryptocurrencies. Trust assists in reducing the social complexity and vulnerability as perceived by the user while participating in cryptocurrency related transactions (Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018).

Substantial research has been conducted where Trust has been integrated with the Technology acceptance model (McCloskey, 2006; Ha and Stoel, 2009; Gefen, Karahanna and Straub, 2003). Perceived trust has exhibited to have a strong impact on the willingness to adopt and attitude towards the adoption of technology (Hu et al., 2019; Wu and Chen, 2005; Xie et al., 2017; (Zhao, Fang and Jin, 2018). It implies that the more trust a user has in the service or the technology, they would be more inclined towards its adoption or they would have a positive attitude towards that technology or service (Basak, Govender and Govender, 2016). Furthermore, literature suggests that perceived trust also has a relationship with perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. It is because trust in a system or a service would allow the consumers to come open and vulnerable to the e-vendors, which would help in ensuring that the customers acquire usefulness of the system or service (Wu and Chen, 2005). Also, if a large number of studies support that if one has trust in a technology, they are more likely to suppose that it would be simple to use (Lee, Lin and Shih, 2018). Similarly, with

respect to cryptocurrencies in this study, it is posited that perceived trust will have an impact on attitude towards their usage, their perception of usability (Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018) as well as their perception of ease of use. Hence the hypothesis framed are:

H6: *Perceived trust associated with cryptocurrencies (PT) positively affects the attitude towards using them (ATT)*

H7: *Perceived trust associated with cryptocurrencies (PT) has a positive effect on their perceived usefulness (PU)*

H8: *Perceived trust associated with cryptocurrencies (PT) has a positive effect on their perceived ease of use (PEOU)*

3.7 Risk

The construct of risk has been studied in the field of consumer behaviour (Faqih, 2016) as well as in the domain of acceptance of technology (Featherman and Pavlou, 2003). In the framework of this research, since cryptocurrencies are a relatively new financial technology, there are uncertainties associated with them. Also, they are often treated as an investment asset (Corbet et al., 2019), and since they involve instability in prices, financial frauds, and speculations, this makes them an even more risky financial technology (Cordero, Sánchez and Cortés, 2020). Thus, including constructs of risk can prove to be quite important while studying the intentions of consumers towards cryptocurrencies (Arias-Oliva, Pelegrín-Borondo and Matías-Clavero, 2019). The concept of perception of risk was incorporated by Dowling (1986) in their study and they explained that risks can be associated with various kinds of losses including financial, performance, time, social, physical, psychological, etc. (Peter and Ryan, 1976; Bearden and Mason, 1978; Kim, Ferrin and Rao, 2008). Although there are several elements of risks, this research investigates two major types of risks, that are considered to be quite relevant for the nature of cryptocurrencies. They are legal risk and privacy risk.

3.7.1 Legal Risk

Financial technology is different from the traditional electronic financial service with respect to risks, legal effects and opportunities (Ryu, 2018). One of the risks that is very closely related to the usage of cryptocurrencies is legal risk (Abramova and Böhme, 2016; Grant and Hogan, 2015; Grinberg, 2011). Legal risk is a consequence of the undefined legal status and absence of worldwide regulations regarding fintech (Ryu, 2018). Cryptocurrencies do not exist in conventional physical form of money rather, they are completely digitised and the consumers do not interact with a trusted bank or other financial institutions when dealing in cryptocurrencies. This brings in the question of legal rights of possessing the cryptocurrencies (Low and Teo, 2018). Furthermore, what adds to the perception of legal risk associated with their usage is the fact that cryptocurrencies have very often been utilised by criminals for conducting illegal or illicit activities owing to the anonymity and privacy afforded by their use and the lack of regulations (Kethineni and Cao, 2019; Moser, Bohme and Breuker, 2013; Brown, 2016).

Unlike traditional financial institutions the regulations regarding the cryptocurrencies in various countries are still under development (Cvetkova, 2018) and they tend to vary wildly between countries. While some countries have plans to put severe restrictions on the usage of cryptocurrencies for example, China (EconomicTimes, 2021), Russia (The library of Congress, 2021) etc), others have given it the status of legal tender (El Salvador (Renteria, Wilson and Strohecker, 2021)). Keeping this in consideration, in this study the construct of legal risks is studied as a general concept independent of any specific geographic location. This will help in encapsulating the perceptions of people regarding the legal risk in general, anywhere in the world. Most of the researchers believe that risk is one of the chief factors that shows a negative influence on adopting a new technology or a system (Hu et al., 2019).

In various studies, constructs of risk have been integrated with technology acceptance model since this model majorly considers the advantages of using a technology and ignores the losses or factors linked to resistance of consumer adoption (Cheng and Huang, 2013; Park, Kim and Kim, 2014). Risk has been hypothesised to have a negative effect on the constructs of TAM which are PU and PEOU (Im, Kim and Han, 2008; Li and Huang, 2009) as well as attitude towards using the technology (Hu et al., 2019; Hansen, Saridakis and Benson, 2018). If an individual considers the legal risks associated with using cryptocurrencies to be high,

they are more likely to feel that cryptocurrencies are less beneficial to them and using them would require more effort. Furthermore, they would have a more negative attitude towards using cryptocurrencies if they feel there is an increased legal risk associated with their usage. Hence the hypotheses are developed as:

H9: *Legal Risks associated with cryptocurrencies (LR) negatively affect their perceived usefulness (PU)*

H10: *Legal Risks associated with cryptocurrencies (LR) negatively affect their perceived ease of use (PEOU)*

H11: *Legal Risks associated with cryptocurrencies (LR) negatively affect the attitude towards using them (ATT)*

3.7.2 Privacy Risk

Privacy risk is another form of risk that is considered important while studying the consumer behaviour towards technology adoption (Cazier, Wilson and Medlin, 2007). Privacy risk refers to the issues and concerns that the people might have involving the probable loss or compromise of their financial or personal data (Johnson et al., 2018). In other words, privacy risk is the possible loss of command over personal information (Featherman and Pavlou, 2003). In the context of digital currencies this would imply linking of the cryptocurrency addresses to real identifiers of the user (Abramova and Böhme, 2016). In the traditional financial system, limiting the access to information about financial transactions is used to achieve privacy. Unlike this, for most cryptocurrencies, the underlying blockchain is public where all the transactions are anonymous but publicly visible.

This pseudonymity leads to the risk that it might be possible to find all transactions by a user if information about one transaction is leaked (Conti et al., 2018). The construct of privacy risk or concerns for privacy or sometimes even security risk have been integrated with the technology acceptance model in various studies and it is stated that it affects the variable of the technology acceptance model negatively (Dhagarra, Goswami and Kumar, 2020; Giovanis, Binioris and Polychronopoulos, 2012; Featherman, Miyazaki and Sprott, 2010). In the context of cryptocurrencies, it implies that privacy risk can have a negative impact on the attitude of

consumers towards their usage. The consumers will also not be able to relate to the usability or ease of use of cryptocurrencies when they have privacy concerns regarding them. Hence, the hypotheses are framed as:

H12: *Privacy Risks associated with cryptocurrencies (PR) negatively affect their perceived usefulness (PU)*

H13: *Privacy Risks associated with cryptocurrencies (PR) negatively affect their perceived ease of use (PEOU)*

H14: *Privacy Risks associated with cryptocurrencies (PR) negatively affect the attitude towards using them (ATT)*

3.8 Personal Innovativeness

It has been observed in various studies that personality traits and social psychological constructs bring about variation in the behaviour and are also considered to be important factors when studying consumer decision making regarding adoption of technology (Shropshire, Warkentin and Sharma, 2015). Research conducted in the area of innovation diffusion has established that people who are highly innovative seek information regarding ideas actively. Due to their tolerance towards uncertainties, they tend to develop a positive attitude towards adoption of technology (Rogers, 1985). Innovation was studied by Rogers (1985) through their theory of diffusion of innovation, where individuals they characterised as innovative, were early adopters of an innovation. It was also investigated in the field of marketing by Midgley and Dowling (1978) where they criticised the idea that innovation is just a temporal concept. Instead, they believed that innovation is a situational concept and it also depends on the communicated experience of other people (Yildirim, Saygili and Yalcintekin, 2021).

Agarwal and Prasad (1998) brought in the construct of personal innovativeness and integrated this concept with the technology acceptance theories. Despite its importance, not much research has been conducted where personality traits like personal innovativeness have been incorporated in the information technology or system innovation research (Lu, Yao and

Yu, 2005). Personal innovativeness within the field of technology is the inclination of people to use or experiment with new technologies and it is believed to have a notable role in ascertaining the user adoption and acceptance towards new technology (Jackson, Yi and Park, 2013). High level of personal innovativeness in individuals implies that they would have positive perceptions regarding the new innovations and therefore positive intentions for the new innovation adoption. It can be measured in all kinds of domains since personal innovativeness reflects an individual's instinctive desire to check out the innovative technologies (Lu, 2014). The construct of personal innovativeness has been postulated to have a relationship with constructs of TAM which are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Svendsen et al., 2013).

Several studies have stipulated the positive effect of personal innovativeness on the factors of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness (Lewis, Agarwal and Sambamurthy, 2003; Yi, Fiedler and Park, 2006; Turan, Tunç and Zehir, 2015). With respect to the perceived usefulness, it implies that innovative people perceive the new innovations as more useful and they can visualise the benefits and usability of the technologies much more easily compared to the people with low levels of innovativeness. Innovative people are able to relate to the technological innovations with their needs and then realize the compatibility of those innovations (Yi, Fiedler and Park, 2006). Regarding the positive effect of personal innovativeness on perceived ease of use, it is anticipated that highly innovative people deem the technologies as easier to use and do not have a need for much effort to acquire the skills required since their technical acceptance towards that technology would be more than the people who are not very innovative (Yi, Fiedler and Park, 2006). Analogous to these arguments, for this study it is hypothesised that personal innovativeness will have a positive impact on perceived usefulness of cryptocurrencies as well as on their perceived ease of use. Since cryptocurrencies are also new financial technologies, investment assets and exchange currencies, highly innovative people are more likely to have a positive outlook towards their usability and effort required to use them.

Few studies have also considered the impact of personal innovativeness on attitude (Amoroso and Lim, 2015; Wu, Li and Fu, 2011), but Yi, Fiedler and Park (2006) state that attitude is one of the main drivers for understanding the user's perception of technological features as well as a crucial factor for understanding user intentions towards their technology. This simply

means that more the personal innovativeness in an individual, the more favourable attitude they will have towards using that technology. Personal innovativeness has hardly been studied with respect to cryptocurrencies in a few studies where personal innovativeness was predicted to influence attitude, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Nuryyev et al., 2020). In the context of cryptocurrencies this implies that an individual with an innovative personality will more likely have a positive attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, perceive them as useful as well as simpler to use. Complying to the above-mentioned lines of reasonings, the hypotheses are framed as:

H15: *Personal Innovativeness (PI) positively affects the perceived usefulness (PU) of cryptocurrencies*

H16: *Personal Innovativeness (PI) positively affects the perceived ease of use (PEOU) of cryptocurrencies*

H17: *Personal Innovativeness (PI) positively affects the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT)*

3.9 Proactive Personality

As explained before, personality is expressed as the response of individuals to specific situations. Personality refers to the arrangement of distinguishing feelings, thoughts and behaviour, that separates one individual from another and stays similar in different situations and times (Phares and Chaplin, 1997). Due to the unique nature of personality traits and their role in human behaviour, personality must surely play a role in user acceptance of technology or innovative systems (Devaraj, Easley and Crant, 2008). One such personality trait that seems to be relevant for the acceptance of technology is proactive personality. Bateman and Crant (1993) explicated that the individuals with proactive personalities “scan for opportunities, show initiative, take action, and persevere until they reach closure by bringing about change”. They further explained that people with proactive personalities are not constrained by situational forces and have an effect on environmental changes. In contrast the people who do not exhibit proactive behaviour, tend to fail at finding and seizing the opportunities to change things (Crant, 1996).

Proactive personality has gained recognition in the field of management (Crant, Hu and Jiang, 2017). In the domain of technology adoption, personality traits like proactive personality have not been studied adequately (Özbek et al., 2014; Lam, Chiang and Parasuraman, 2008 ; Erdoğan and Esen, 2011). Since personality has been observed to be linked with technology in several ways (Svendsen et al., 2013), personality features have been integrated with TAM or TPB and their combination is still under research (Özbek et al., 2014; Devaraj, Easley and Crant, 2008). Ajzen & Fishbein (1980) in their explanation of theory of reasoned action illuminate light on personality and treat it as an external variable that can only influence behaviour indirectly. Devaraj, Easley and Crant (2008) later extended the reasoning to TAM and suggested a relationship between personality traits and perceived usefulness. Many other studies have also examined this relationship between personality traits and constructs of TAM (Svendsen et al., 2013; Barkhi and Wallace, 2007).

Besides this, researchers have also introduced external variables to the two major constructs of technology acceptance model which are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, including the personality characteristics and demographic features (Gefen and Straub, 2000; Venkatesh, 2000; Venkatesh and Morris, 2000). It can be expected that people with proactive personalities who tend to be more inclined towards technology, will presume the technology to be more useful and easier to use (Svendsen et al., 2013). Crant, Hu and Jiang (2017) have expanded on the concept of proactive personality and have mentioned that it is positively related to the attitude towards an innovation. In the context of this study, that is regarding the attitude towards cryptocurrencies, through an in-depth literature review, it was determined that no such research has been conducted where adoption of cryptocurrencies was studied along with the construct of proactive personality. Based on the other studies mentioned above and logical reasonings provided for relationship of proactive personality with constructs of technology acceptance model, hypotheses have been developed as follows:

H18: Proactive personality (PP) positively affects the perceived usefulness (PU) of cryptocurrencies

H19: Proactive personality (PP) positively affects the perceived ease of use (PEOU) of cryptocurrencies

H20: Proactive personality (PP) positively affects the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT)

3.10 Bandwagon Effect

Bandwagon effect denotes that the impression of "as more individuals accept a message to be right then it is likely legitimate" represents a "consensus" heuristic, which is one of the straightforward decision making principles for people (Chaiken, 1987). In simple terms, bandwagon effect can be understood as the tendency of the individuals to conform to the social norms (Tsai, Yang and Liu, 2013). Bandwagon effect is sometimes also looked from the point of view of network externalities (Hong, 2018) or herd behaviour. This effect has been adopted as a construct with many financial products and new technologies. The bandwagon effect can cause investment in specific assets simply because numerous others put resources into them (Naeem, Mbarki and Shahzad, 2021). A genuine illustration of a bandwagon effect is putting money into cryptocurrencies (Koutmos and Payne, 2020), since they are speculative in nature and are called as unsupported assets, which are for all intents and purposes difficult to dissect in a general sense (Ionescu and Rădulescu, 2019).

Moreover, investments in cryptocurrencies come from young individuals, sometimes computer enthusiasts, who might lack experience or knowledge with respect to trading (Yelowitz and Wilson, 2015; Naeem, Mbarki and Shahzad, 2021). This is also the reason due to which bandwagon effect or herd behaviour is seen in cryptocurrencies. It can be said that increase in prices, attract a large number of investors to "jump into bandwagon" to be able to earn profits simply without even finding the functioning or the working of cryptocurrencies and their potential, but knowing very well that prospective cost for failing to take part is relatively high (Calderón, 2018). Although bandwagon effect in context of cryptocurrencies is widely discussed, but it was found that no study has been conducted where bandwagon effect is studied as a construct in the investigation of behaviour towards cryptocurrencies.

In this study, bandwagon effect has been integrated in the model as a social construct of technology acceptance. The TAM as proposed by Davis (1986) does not include social factors unlike the TRA which had the construct of subjective norms (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw,

1989). Importance of social construct was very well recognised by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) in TRA where subjective norms have an influence on intentions to adopt. It was found by Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1989) that in the context of technology adoption, factors of social influence can have a direct effect on behavioural intentions as well as an indirect effect on intention via attitude. In this study, bandwagon effect has been used as a construct capturing the social influences. Therefore, this study proposes that bandwagon effect has a direct effect on intention to adopt as well as on attitude towards using cryptocurrencies. This implies that someone who is more likely to follow the bandwagon will likely have stronger intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies. Moreover, such an individual is very likely to develop an optimistic attitude towards cryptocurrencies. Hence, the hypotheses are developed as follows:

H21: Bandwagon Effect (BE) associated with cryptocurrencies positively affects the attitude towards using them (ATT)

H22: Bandwagon Effect (BE) associated with cryptocurrencies positively affects the intention to adopt them (IA)

3.11 Technology Anxiety

The term anxiety in general refers to the natural body reaction to stressful situations and the feeling which is associated with fear regarding the future (Dönmez-Turan and Kır, 2019). When an individual shows negative sentiment in certain situations while interacting with a technology, then this indicates that they are experiencing technology anxiety (Saadé and Kira, 2007). The reference to the term technology anxiety comes from the studies conducted on computer anxiety (Heinssen, Glass and Knight, 1987). Some scholars have defined technology anxiety as the state of being afraid or apprehensive while using or even thinking of using a technology (Saadé and Kira, 2006). There are certain causes of anxiety including previous usage experience, self-efficacy, gender, age or mathematical anxiety (Tsai et al., 2020). In simple terms technology anxiety can be understood as a propensity of an individual to become uneasy or apprehensive while using a technology or while thinking about using it in future (Parasuraman and Igarria, 1990). Technology anxiety is also associated with the

perception of users towards the new technology and has a negative influence towards their adoption (Venkatesh, 2000).

Several studies have been conducted on technology and computer anxiety wherein the factors of anxiety are established to have a negative effect on the adoption of the particular technology (Calisir et al., 2014; Lee, Warkentin and Choi, 2004). Technology anxiety has been widely assented to negatively influence the constructs of TAM which are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Turan and Kir, 2019; Hackbarth, Grover and Yi, 2003; Chatzoglou et al., 2009; Guo et al., 2012). It was found by Venkatesh (2000) that the construct of anxiety has a negative impact on perceived ease of use specifically during the early period of adoption. This implies that the feeling of uneasiness and trouble experienced by users towards the technology may lead to that technology being perceived by the user as being more difficult to use than it really is (Raaij and Schepers, 2008). It is also observed that the anxiety related to technology has a negative effect on the attitude towards its usage and therefore the intention of adopting that technology (Parasuraman and Igarria, 1990; Compeau and Higgins, 1995). While there haven't been many studies examining the effect of technology anxiety on cryptocurrency adoption, based on the above reasonings it can be argued that if an individual is anxious or apprehensive towards using the cryptocurrencies, they will have a negative attitude towards their usage. They will also not be able to realize their usability and might consider them difficult to use due to the feelings of nervousness and apprehension attached to their adoption. Therefore, the hypotheses for this construct are formed as:

H23: Technology Anxiety (TA) associated with cryptocurrencies has a negative effect on their perceived usefulness (PU)

H24: Technology Anxiety (TA) associated with cryptocurrencies has a negative effect on their perceived ease of use (PEOU)

H25: Technology Anxiety (TA) associated with cryptocurrencies has a negative effect on the attitude towards using them (ATT)

3.12 Conceptual Framework

Following the review of the various constructs considered in this study and their associated inter-relations, the conceptual framework of the research model is summarised here. The constructs considered relevant for the study can be classified based on their underlying theoretical framework. The psychological factors include Technology Anxiety along with the personality traits Personal Innovativeness and Proactive Personality. They are hypothesised to affect each of the factors associated with the technology acceptance model, i.e. the factors Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Attitude towards using Cryptocurrencies. The trust and risk factors of Legal Risk, Privacy Risk, and Perceived Trust are also hypothesised to affect the TAM factors. The Bandwagon Effect, representing a social factor, affects the Attitude and the overall Intention to Adopt Cryptocurrencies. Among the TAM factors, Perceived Ease of use is hypothesised to affect both the Perceived Usefulness as well as the Attitude towards using Cryptocurrencies. Perceived Usefulness is hypothesised to have an effect on the Attitude and the Intention to Adopt Cryptocurrencies, while the Attitude is considered to only influence the Intention to Adopt. These relations are shown in the figure below.

Figure 3.1 Conceptual Framework of the Research Model

Chapter 4 Research Methodology

4.1 Overview of the Chapter

In order to understand the behavioural patterns and other exogenous driving factors that determine consumers' tastes, preferences and patronage of cryptocurrencies, it is important to discuss the leading philosophies that underpin this research. In this section, the ontological assumptions and the epistemological positioning will be considered and the paramount driving philosophy, positivism, will be discussed in-depth. Subsequently, the research approaches, research purpose and comprehensive design of the research are critically discussed to provide both a theoretical and supporting framework for the research work. This chapter, thus, forms the fulcrum that connects the previous chapters (Introduction, Literature Review, and Hypothesis Development) to the analysis and final recommendations (sections) and conclusions drawn on the understanding of consumer preferences and adoption of cryptocurrencies.

4.2 Research Philosophy

The term research philosophy associates with developing knowledge in a specific field and the nature of that knowledge. The selection and subsequent defence of the premises for the choice of a particular research philosophy by any researcher is fundamental to any academic research. This is because the choice of a research philosophy underpins the way the researcher perceives the social system of the world (Saunders et al., 2007).

4.2.1 Ontology and Epistemology

It is thought that research philosophy could be segmented into two major components, namely Ontology and Epistemology. Many scholars hold the view that the ontological assumptions of research deals with the nature of reality whereas the epistemological positioning relates to the meaning of knowledge (what knowledge is/are and what is the universal or explicit definition of a particular piece of knowledge) and the means of investigating that knowledge base (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015). If Easterby-

Smith et al. (2015) definition of ontology and epistemology is constructively adopted, then understanding research philosophy is valuable due to three motivating reasons. These three reasons include clarifying the research designs to provide solutions to those research questions being investigated; establishing the most suitable research approach; and creating or adapting to the agreed-upon research designs according to the constraints of the subject.

In general terms, ontology deals with the branch of research philosophy that examines the process of knowledge acquisition. Conversely, epistemology is more concerned about the sources, origins and foundational basis of knowledge. As Ryan et al. (2002) explicitly mentioned, ontology delves into what reality (of knowledge) is by defining “what is” and understanding the “being or format or structure” (of knowledge) whereas epistemology is more focused on the reflection, imagination, perception, belief in, conception and construction of knowledge. These stances were corroborated by Rawnsley (1998) who intimated that the epistemological positioning of any research field deals with human practices of investigations to understand what knowledge is, whereas the ontological assumptions of (or what reality actually is) a particular field of research will vary from one researcher to another due to the varied epistemological practices adopted.

In this current research, the ontological assumptions are highly objective in nature since reality is considered a tangible structure which is characterized by facts, figures and scientific or statistical and quantitative metrics. In the same vein, the epistemological positioning of the research is equally highly objective in the sense that the definition of knowledge or what knowledge is tends to hinge on the constructive analysis and verification of datasets that are empirically proven with scientific human practices. In effect, there is no room for any interpretivist proposition in the area of researching cryptocurrencies since the subject matter consists of numerical and quantitative validation of numbers and perceptions. Regardless, even though this research looks at a subtle form of subjectivity in which overt human perceptions, tastes and preferences for cryptocurrencies are being examined, these perceptions are reduced to quantitative analysis with the aim of sustaining the objective ontological and epistemological stances adopted. Subsequently, these foundations determine the choice of a Positivist approach or philosophy to guide the research.

Figure 4.1 below is a graphical illustration, created for this research, corroborating and supporting the above ontological assumption and epistemological positioning of this thesis.

Figure 4.1 Ontological and Epistemological Positioning of this Research

4.2.2 Positivism - Overview

From an epistemological point of view with the aim of validating and understanding what knowledge consists of in the study of the changing dynamics of cryptocurrencies, this study adopts a Positivist approach as the guiding philosophy. It is generally thought that positivism builds upon the empiricist premise where all knowledge sources about the natural and social worlds could only be obtained via empirical facts (Hamilton, 1992). What Hamilton (1992) sought to advance was that, an empiricist approach to understanding the social and economic system requires the use of the five senses, namely sight, feeling, taste, hearing and smell, to objectively collect accurate data and analyse same by using the scientific methods in order to confirm the supposed knowledge. Thus, an empiricist paradigm relies on meaningful scientific objectivity in which testable and factual statements are clearly distinguished from any form of subjective value statements (Benton and Craib, 2010). It is generally argued that these

separations could only be best achieved by subjecting the datasets and variables to scientific and quantitative analysis in order to get rid of the value judgements.

Following from the above, a positivist paradigm aims at adopting the philosophical stance of that of a natural scientist (an empiricist) where researchers work with observable reality with the resultant outcomes being subjected to possible generalisation. On the other hand, and in contrast with positivism is the interpretivist approach which advocates the importance of the role of people as social actors. Here, the researcher takes an empathetic viewpoint towards the social world. It does not consider generalisability of results as an important factor (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007). The philosophical stance that this study adopts is an objectivist ontology and a positivist epistemology (as illustrated in Figure 4.1 above).

Positivists adopt the position of a realist and believe that reality is single and exists objectively and independently from perceptions of the individuals. Similar to the physical world, the social world exists independently of what individuals perceive as a concrete, real and perpetual structure. Positivists believe that this reality that exists as a structure is a constituency of relationships among its parts. This supposes that reality is separable and fragmentable and as a result comprises the measurements of the physical and social world that can be accurately and precisely evaluated (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). In a related argument, positivism involves using an existing theory to develop the hypothesis and further testing of those hypotheses (Saunders et al., 2007). Accordingly, any research project that adopts a positivist philosophy will usually adopt a structured methodological approach to provide replication and generalisation of results or outcome. Subsequently, Saunders et al. (2007) postulated that the positivist researcher will deploy statistical techniques to produce quantifiable results.

It has commonly been assumed that positivism has been unequivocally perceived, and upheld, as the "natural science model" in social sciences, and has discovered far reaching application, specifically in organizational studies. According to Lee (1991), the positivist school of thought uses tenets such as "rules of formal logic", and "rules of hypothetico-deductive logic", to be able to satiate the four prerequisites of any scientific method which are "falsifiability, logical consistency, relative explanatory power and survival". It is interesting yet imperative to know that the positivist philosophy assumes that the physical world and social reality co-exist separately from each other and that one can apprehend, classify and measure

their natural system without encountering any problems provided a scientific approach is adopted to guide the study. Furthermore, positivism also assumes that human beings are rational and their interactions occur in logical ways (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991).

4.2.2.1 Pillars and Arguments of Positivism

The field and philosophy of Positivism is accredited to Auguste Comte (1798 – 1857), who was assumed to be the “First Positivist”. Subsequently, researchers in philosophy like Herbert Spencer (1820 – 1903) as well as Emile Durkheim (1858 – 1917), became associated with the positivist paradigm and are equally considered the founding fathers of Positivism (Smith et al., 1996). There is certain verification to suggest that pioneers of positivism agreed on four topical pillars and foundational arguments of the paradigm. These philosophical positionings are critically discussed here.

In their thorough analysis of the philosophy, Smith et al. (1996) indicated that positivists assume that a comprehensive understanding of the social and economic world can only be achieved through a systematic, empirical and scientific study of the economy. The researchers argued that positivism’s scientific approach or process deals with the detailed assimilation of the data and analysing that collected data by using statistical tools and techniques. It is then assumed that this systematic and scientific approach will result in accurate and reliable interpretations and presentations of facts and outputs that will inform human decision-making. Smith et al. (1996) consequently concluded that the positivists often consider the scientific approach of gaining knowledge as being more appropriate and preferable. This is because this approach utilises robust statistical and objective analysis, instead of relying on subjectivity and value judgements. Such subjectivity and value judgements could be prone to errors and misinterpretations that could impair the judgements and decisions of key stakeholders.

Subsequent to the above, Smith et al. (1996) also argued that positivists agree in the concept of “Unity of Scientific Method”, i.e., the situation where the overarching motives and supporting objectives of the study match with the scientific methods that are used for collection and further analysis of the data. For instance, the gathering of opinions and consumer preferences on the patronage of cryptocurrencies cannot be subjected to a chemical and laboratory test since the aims and methods may not be congruent. Instead, data collected on the study of social sciences should at best be matched to statistical analysis that meet the aims of the study. Practically, this argument makes sense and clearly distinguishes

one field and aim of study from the other due to the varied scientific methods and instruments applied to validate and gain knowledge.

The third pillar and foundational argument, according to Hollis (1994) stipulates that any accurate use of scientific methods to understudy the social and economic system should lead to the discovery of new knowledge, laws and theories that will guide human activities. A likely explanation of this third strand of positivism is that, a consistent application of scientific methods to derive knowledge results in the promulgation of new and amendments to existing societal laws and regulations in the social and economic world. For instance, a critical scientific approach into the study of consumer preferences and attitudes to cryptocurrencies would lead to the formulation of financial regulations that will dictate ethical practices in the trading of cryptocurrencies.

The fourth principle of positivism encompasses the initial three strands explained above. Positivism conclusively argues that the adoption of accurate scientific methods, matching of the scientific methods to the aims of the study, and the subsequent discovery of laws and regulations to regulate social and economic lives should culminate in finding the lasting solutions and remedies to the current social and economic challenges being experienced (Hollis, 1994; Smith et al., 1996). In effect, positivism argues that any scientific method that does not result in finding meaningful solutions to societal challenges loses its worth as a valid and reliable source of knowledge acquisition and validation. At best, any such methods could be classified as unscientific since positivists presume that all scientific methods should ideally lead to finding practical solutions to the topic under study. It is imperative on this basis that this research favours the argument that a study into consumer preferences and attitudes towards cryptocurrencies should result in identifying solutions to any fallouts or ramifications of these digital currencies.

4.2.2.2 Weaknesses of Positivism

Positivism comes with its associated weaknesses and it is not immune to criticisms. Critics question the premises of positivism that assume that science is rather superior to any other form of acquisition of knowledge. This argument is flawed to the extent that some bases of knowledge can only be acquired and derived from human experiences, exposures, revelations, natural phenomenon and unexpected social observations that cannot be subjected to any form of scientific enquiry (Hollie, 1994).

Consequent to the above identified weakness, it is imperative to highlight that some sources of knowledge acquisition that relates to the social and economic systems can only be better understood via the study of the reasons, motivations and intents surrounding these socio-economic variables and actions. Here, some subjective interpretations could play key roles which may deviate from the positivist norm of objective scientific analysis of gathered datasets.

Figure 4.2 Positivism and its dominant strands or arguments

A serious weakness with positivism, as identified by Hollie (1994) suggests that the positivist approach may not be comprehensive, after all, in the study of human actions and behaviours. This argument could be premised on the fact that statistical and quantitative models do not fully explain the subjective activities of human activities and cannot, therefore, fully provide a holistic explanation behind human and societal actions. In this vein, it is probably prudent not to use scientific, quantitative and statistical models as benchmarks and standards for a comprehensive understanding of any economic decisions in which human efforts and activities play key roles. Figure 4.2 is a graphical illustration that depicts the four pillars and strands of positivism.

4.2.2.3 Case for Positivism

In spite of the limitations associated with Positivism, it is a widely adopted research philosophy due to its validation, rigorousness and replication while conducting research. It is

one of the most suitable to answer some types of research objectives in various fields due to its enforceability of quality standards in empirical research (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991).

The positivist approach is the most appropriate for approaching the results of this study since the research here aims to investigate the attitude of consumers towards cryptocurrencies where the study takes place among targeted samples who are treated as rational human beings. This implies the research constituents would make their decisions based on the information available after evaluating the alternatives presented. Several consumer behaviour and marketing studies follow this approach to be able to predict consumer attitude which is based on scientific facts and observations. It aims at drawing generalizable results thereby helping with appropriate and viable marketing practices. In application to the research being undertaken, positivism will direct the researcher to identify the existing single reality which should allow researchers to objectively identify, measure and predict the causes of consumer behaviour.

A paramount driving motivation for adopting positivism as a research philosophy for this study is the belief that, when characteristics of consumers such as their cognitive responses, personality traits, etc. are well-known, it becomes possible to draw some significant predictions of consumer actions (Pachauri, 2001). Research by Williams et al. (2009) corroborates this stance by specifying that positivism is the most prevalent form of research philosophy used in the study of consumer behaviours, psychological studies and the adoption of cryptocurrencies literature. Similarly, Hudson and Ozanne (1988) equally illustrated the instance where positivists utilize a generalizing approach to explore the impact of source validity on consumers' attitudes which endeavours to determine abstract and general construction of the same phenomenon. Further, they explained that positivists place high priority to the causal relationships following deterministic theory in order to ascertain the real causes of the behaviour of the individuals. The particular and in-depth details of the phenomenon are not so relevant for positivists as opposed to Interpretivists. In this research where the objective is to investigate the behaviour of the individuals in addition to providing generalizable laws and to determine cause and effect relationships among the variables impacting the cryptocurrency adoption, positivism makes concrete sense.

Significant among the arguments for the adoption of positivism is that, in this study, the researcher intends to take into account the views of different people objectively and measure

these views using statistical techniques. The overall aim here is to investigate the impact of various constructs on the consumer acceptance of cryptocurrencies. It considers not only the variables to measure their effects on consumers but also aims to draw correlations based on consumer's insights and experiences. In this situation, the researcher seeks to examine the research question objectively in order to produce generalizable results. Since positivist epistemological approach lay emphasis on research setting where variables and constructs are to be deployed, controlled and manipulated, studies adopting positivist approach are based on previously set relationships studying a phenomenon with systematized instruments (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991; Park et al., 2020). Accordingly, this research provides evidence for deploying variables, testing the research hypothesis using statistical tools, and falsifying and verifying the associated theories; thus, a positivist philosophy must be the most suitable for this study.

4.3 Research Approaches

The two major kinds of research approaches are Deductive Reasoning and Inductive Reasoning. The approach that this research most appropriately agrees with is the Deductive approach. Deduction is referred to as a process where the researcher draws reasonable conclusions through understandable generalisation of facts (Sekaran, 2003). Deductive reasoning is similar to the scientific approach which involves deducing hypotheses and testing of theory which results in the modification of theories and laws (if necessary) with respect to the new findings. This argument is consistent with the fourth strand of the positivist paradigm. In this approach, causal relationships between the variables are explored. Also, it follows the principles of reductionism and generalisation. It requires a large number of datasets and the researcher tends to be independent of what is being researched (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007).

It is instructive to firmly mention that the use of a deductive reasoning approach in this research makes both academic and empirical sense in that it intends to deploy various theories such as Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Theories of risk and trust, and other Socio-Psychological Theories. As mentioned earlier, positivism philosophy mostly takes into the use of pre-existing theories for development and testing of hypotheses in accordance with

the subject matter under study. Hence this research also reviews in-depth the existing theories of technology adoption and consumer behaviour. It then deploys these theories to build on the hypothesis, taking in the important constructs to understand the behaviour of consumers towards adoption of cryptocurrencies. The entire research work involves developing hypotheses that are to be subjected to rigorous testing. Specifically, the data is to be collected in relation to the concepts or variables under investigation. In doing so, it becomes intuitive to clearly indicate the aim of the research, i.e., to create a model showing variables and their relationships which are validated through testing. Given the above, the adoption of a deductive reasoning approach justifies the need to formulate theories that precede the data collection process. Hence, there will be enough proof or falsification of the primary hypothesis or theory, in contrast to using an inductive approach where theories are developed subsequently from the collected data (Franklin, 2012). From the above discourse, it can be easily inferred that this study follows the deductive approach.

4.4 Research Purpose

Research purpose has been classified into three types: Exploratory, Descriptive, and Explanatory. Exploratory Studies are carried out in cases where there is very little or no information available about the research issues at hand or the similar kind of problems or issues have been solved in the past (Sekaran, 2003). Descriptive Studies are carried out where the characteristics of the phenomena to be studied are known to exist and the researcher wants to describe them in an improved and accurate way by creating a profile of those factors. The researcher needs to describe the attributes of the variables relevant to the study (Sekaran, 2003). Explanatory Studies are those types of studies where the aim is to establish underlying relationships among the variables of interest. The researcher here studies a problem to be able to elucidate the relationships between the variables under investigation. Hypothesis testing and statistical tests like correlations are undertaken in order to get a clearer conception of the relationships (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). This study is Explanatory in nature since the objective here is to test the defined characteristics of the variables under consideration and test the hypothesis to be able to understand the connections and relationships between those variables. It delves into comprehending the

underlying factors that influence the decision making of the consumers for accepting the cryptocurrencies.

4.5 Research Methodology

Research methodology is concerned with how the research is to be conducted based on the chosen research philosophy and this further determines what methods are to be used. Sarantakos (1993) defined methodology as “a model, which entails theoretical principles as well as a framework that provides guidelines about how research is done in the context of a particular paradigm”. There are two ways in which research can be conducted i.e., Quantitative and Qualitative approach. Quantitative research is characterised as empirical and is denoted as a scientific paradigm. It involves numerical calculations and conducting statistical tests for analysing data. This approach generally holds a positivist position in nature and generally follows a deductive approach. It involves measurement, causality, generalisation and replication (Bryman and Bell, 2011). In contrast, Qualitative research is based on judgements of the social environment by the means of interpretation of that social world by its contestants. It is a strategy where words are emphasized instead of quantification. The participation of the researcher during the process of the research is considered crucial in qualitative methodology (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

As explained in the philosophy section, this study is positivist, deductive and explanatory in nature since the aim is to develop a model by testing hypotheses and variables objectively. Consequently, the most appropriate methodology adopted for analysis must be quantitative methodology where the data collected is measured and data analysis conducted with the use of statistical methods. Comprehending from the information provided in the philosophy section and owing to the objectivist and positivist stance for this research, it makes absolute sense that the data must be collected quantitatively. Also, statistical techniques are used for arriving at the reliable interpretation of the social world in research that adopts positivism. Hence in this research in order to understand the human decision making towards adoption of cryptocurrencies, it would be best to implement statistical tools for analysing the data. Hence, it can be said that quantitative methodology perfectly aligns with the positivist

philosophy adopted in this research, therefore makes it even more valuable for carrying forward this research.

Furthermore, the use of quantitative methodology is a well-established approach in consumer behaviour, technology adoption and marketing studies. A study conducted by Yu, Lin and Liao (2017) adopted a quantitative survey method to understand and predict the adoption behaviour towards Information communication technology. Findings in the research by Williams et al. (2009) suggest that quantitative methodology has been predominantly deployed in the domain of technology adoption research. In the same vein, Murphy and Rottet (2009) conducted a study where they investigated the elements that would have an impact on the adoption of biometric technologies. They deployed quantitative methodology and surveyed 300 hotel customers focusing on the main determinants including technology behaviour, biometric technologies, etc. and their willingness to adopt. Comparatively, a study by Irani, Dwivedi and Williams (2009) tested the model using quantitative techniques where data was collected using surveys from broadband consumers in the United Kingdom. They conducted regression analysis for estimating the influence of the constructs on behavioural intentions to adopt broadband.

Leveraging on the above comparative studies vis-à-vis this research work, since this study aims to examine the behavioural intentions of the consumers towards cryptocurrencies, quantitative methods offer an effective way for achieving the objectives of the study. It is not denied that many researchers have advocated the need to adopt qualitative methodology in this type of research; however, its limitations like lack of generalizability and replication and lack of hypothesis testing and statistical methods to test the data hold the researcher from adopting qualitative techniques of data analysis in this study. Additionally, in this research, the aim is to get an overall generalised picture of the consumer behaviour towards cryptocurrencies and not to provide deeper insights on a particular topic. If the aim of the research would have been to understand the judgements of people in depth on the same particular variable, for example only their personality traits, an interpretivist approach followed by qualitative research would have served the purpose. In this case, statistical correlations will be an ideal method for developing a multi-criterion model to investigate the attitude towards cryptocurrencies. Quantitative design allows the implementation of statistical methods and rigorous testing of models to understand the intentions of consumers

towards cryptocurrencies. A quantitative approach will not only help in understanding the present scenario of cryptocurrencies among the individuals but also aid in predicting the future markets. Also, after reviewing the literature and studies mentioned in the above sections, a quantitative methodology serves as a useful technique to understand the relationship among the variables or constructs and draws correlations among them in order to develop a model.

4.6 Data Collection

There are various ways of collecting primary data like using semi-structured interviews, group interviews, structured observations, participant observation, structured questionnaires, experiments, etc. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Based on the literature reviewed as well as the philosophy and the methodology adopted, the survey method consisting of a structured questionnaire is selected for collection of data in this research. The term survey includes the method of collecting data through a structured questionnaire from the individuals who are the focus of the research and belong to the desired sample group thereby fulfilling the objective of studying the relationships between the constructs (Corbetta, 2011).

Questionnaires are the most popular way of collecting data for quantitative study in social science research. In this method, each individual is requested to provide responses for the same questions in a definite sequence (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Questionnaires are distributed by various means including through post, emails, face to face or via online modes (Rowley, 2014). In this research, questionnaires are sent through emails and online modes since the electronic questionnaires are the most suitable and sometimes the only option for the researcher when the data is needed to be collected on a larger scale by using structured questionnaires with limited resources of cost and time from the sample dispersed widely at varied locations (Sekaran, 2003).

Questionnaires are different from the use of interviews due to the routes by which they are intended to be completed by the respondent without the need for any direct interactions with the researcher - whether in person or remotely. Respondents to a questionnaire might be asked to answer the questions in regards to realities (for example their age or pays), or

their mentalities, convictions, practices or encounters as a resident, managers, experts, employees or consumers. Since one of the fundamental benefits of questionnaires is the capacity to connect with and accumulate reactions from a moderately huge number of individuals in dispersed and potentially far off areas, questionnaires are ordinarily utilized in overviews, where the goal is to profile a "population" (Rowley, 2014). For collecting data using a questionnaire, a strategic choice is made in terms of uniformity as opposed to individuality where the researchers aim to understand the common factor among the individuals instead of understanding what differentiates them. This decision includes restricting the study to that common element of the behaviour of the individuals which can be standardized, grouped and looked at regardless of the individuality of the subjects. However, this approach is considered a limitation of quantitative studies where the focus is on working on large numbers instead of studying small numbers in depth (Corbetta, 2011).

It was observed that many studies have used the survey method to collect data in the domain of adoption of technology and consumer behaviour. Research by Singh and Srivastava (2020) regarding the adoption of mobile banking by existing online banking users deployed a positivist approach where a structured questionnaire method was used. Another study by Sanka et al. (2021) followed the quantitative methodology and surveyed the developments, applications and adoption of blockchain technology. Comparative research conducted by Arias-Oliva et al. (2019) used a structured online questionnaire to gather responses regarding the cryptocurrencies from the consumer perspective. Furthermore, using this method would be less costly and less time consuming and it would be easy to reach out to a large number of participants, with the limited resources available to the researcher. Participants will also be able to spend time to provide appropriate answers without any pressure of sharing information immediately with the interviewer. It will also enable the researcher to ask similarly formulated questions with different response scales (Fowler, 2002).

Additional derived advantages of using questionnaires are that they would guarantee anonymity in the data as compared to using interviews since the questionnaires would not administer any form of identification. It prevents biasness of the researcher and participants who live far away across the borders can also be easily reached. The questionnaires can be filled at any time by the participants according to their suitability (Corbetta, 2011). Questionnaires are predominantly utilized in quantitative studies where the researcher is

required to create a profile from the sample with reference to numbers such as the extent of variations in the various age groups, or for evaluating the frequencies of experiences, feelings, attitudes, opinions, behaviour, etc. This method is particularly useful in cases where the research purpose is to understand the relationship among the variables. Moreover, it was observed that researchers prefer interviews when it is needed and possible to recognize people in significant positions in order to understand the phenomenon (Rowley, 2014).

Considering the aims of this research, this research is also assessing the attitude and perceptions of people towards cryptocurrencies quantitatively from users and potential users and not trying to gauge the opinions from experts or people in key positions regarding the technology adoption of cryptocurrencies. The benefits of collecting quantitative data using questionnaires from a large number of people further make the approach the most feasible and appropriate method for investigating the behavioural intentions of consumers towards cryptocurrencies with respect to various constructs. Hence, agreeing to the literature studied regarding the technology adoption as well as conferring to the aim of the research which is understanding the relationship among the variables under investigation, questionnaire comes out to be the most suitable tool for collection of data for this research.

4.7 Design of the Questionnaire

It is rational for the questions to be designed in a way that they address the research aims and objectives. In the same vein, it is essential that the questions use an appropriate language that the respondents fully comprehend. Likewise, in situations where the research examines the relationship between the variables, it is imperative that the questionnaire addresses those constructs accordingly by collecting data which can be analysed to determine the relationship. In the case of a deductive research approach such as this study, theory becomes an important factor for ascertaining the research objectives, thus, it is prudent that part or all of the questionnaire is used from the previous research of similar kind (Rowley, 2014).

As a consequence of the above arguments, the design of the questionnaire for this research was based on the prior literature on adoption of technologies by consumers, various theories like TAM, UTAUT, TPB, etc. and theories of risk, trust, and other socio-psychological theories.

A large number of studies that have collected data using survey were reviewed prior to developing a questionnaire. These studies included adoption of different technologies like cryptocurrencies, mobile banking, e-commerce, etc. in various settings. The questionnaires studying similar variables were examined thoroughly and it is after these thorough examinations that the measurement items were chosen for the constructs of this study. The measurement items or scales used for collecting data for the independent and dependent variables were adapted from a number of studies and appropriately modified according to the framework surrounding cryptocurrencies keeping in mind the end goal of this study.

The questionnaire designed for this research uses closed ended questions i.e., those questions where individuals are able to answer just by clicking an appropriate box or circle from the set of scale as provided. It is almost certain that when the researcher provides the respondents with a list of appropriate answers, it will give the respondents the same experience of what represents an appropriate answer. Unlike an open-ended type of questionnaire, the closed ended questions allow the respondents to select one or more answers from a set of alternative choices provided. Arguably, closed ended questions are considered more useful than open ended questions since the latter survey tool type does not produce a large number of responses as required (Fowler, 2002). Most significantly, closed ended questions help in increasing the responses since they are quicker to answer in addition to the ease with which the responses are subject to analysis (Rowley, 2014).

It is important to highlight that scale-based questions or rating questions are utilized when it is needed to measure the variables. One of the most common type of scale is the Likert scale. By definition, the Likert scale deals with situations where the items under consideration address various concepts of the object under measurement; also, the responses are offered to represent different levels of agreement or disagreement with the measurement items (Gray, 2008). The questionnaire used in this research applies the Likert scale where the participants need to denote how strongly they agree or disagree with the given statements or questions. The items are measured using a seven-point Likert scale i.e., anchored by Strongly Disagree (1), Somewhat Disagree (2), Disagree (3), Neither Agree nor Disagree option (4), Agree (5), Somewhat Agree (6), and Strongly Agree (7).

4.7.1 Structure of the Questionnaire

Rowley (2014) mentioned that the value of the responses will be improved in the form of a preamble by introducing a clear title, combined with a decent, short initial passage towards the start of the survey. This preamble section typically is structured to present the reason for conducting the study and must provide contact details of the researcher. Following this, the questionnaire designed for this research comprises the title of the research and starts with an invitation letter to the participants which is an introductory paragraph stating the purpose of the research, prerequisites for participation and the estimated time required to fill the questionnaire. In addition, the preamble section further explains that the participation is voluntary and the data collected will be anonymised. It provides the participants with clearer details in order to seek and obtain their informed consent for participating in the survey. A consent form along with the participant information sheet with more detailed information regarding the study are also made available to the participants. The questionnaire is divided into different sections to encapsulate the opinions of the consumers regarding the constructs required to be studied for the research.

After taking the consent from the participants, the questionnaire begins with a couple of screening questions including the prerequisites for the research aimed at collecting data from only those participants who fall under the selected sample or the target group. In this section, the first requirement is that participants must have knowledge or experience of cryptocurrencies i.e. individuals who are unaware or have no knowledge regarding the cryptocurrencies cannot be allowed to answer the questions that follow. The second requirement is that participants must fall under the age group of 21 - 60 years. This was intended to narrow down the target sample to the working age group. It is important that there is a rational flow in the arrangement of the questions as it will help the respondents to understand each question separately in addition to appreciating the whole intent of the questionnaire.

Research papers also contend that questionnaires should begin with those questions that are effortlessly answered and important for the research. In cases where the cover letter has featured the key topics of the survey, it is reasonable to commence with the questions that are directly linked to the research theme. It is also recommended that questions in the beginning must be well thought out by the researcher since they will help in deciding whether

the survey should be answered further or not. Other valuable guidance incorporates going from simple to more complicated or complex questions with the most sensitive questions being placed in the end or latter parts of the questionnaire (Gray, 2008).

Adhering to the above criteria for structuring a good and credible questionnaire, section A in the questionnaire works towards the individuals' attitude towards innovation. This is where the questions regarding the research theme start off. This includes simple and interesting questions about behaviour of individuals towards technology in general in order to receive their attention. The subsequent section brings in the questions regarding the perceptions of participants towards usage of cryptocurrencies. It deals with the important constructs for the research such as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and technology anxiety with respect to cryptocurrencies.

Section C involves the attitude of consumption towards cryptocurrencies i.e. how likely individuals are affected by the society while adopting cryptocurrencies. The variable that is evaluated through these questions include bandwagon effect. This section was put here in order to make the questionnaire appealing to answer as it discusses social attitudes. The next section includes questions regarding the opinions of the respondents with respect to trust and different types of risk associated with cryptocurrencies are considered. This is a crucial section for the research as it demonstrates some important variables for technology adoption.

Section E connects directly to the central question of the research since it contains questions for the outcome variable i.e. intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies. As it was suggested that sensitive questions must be put in the end, these critical questions are arranged just before the last section of demographics. Research by Rowley (2014) mentioned that personal information including the age, gender, salary, etc. should be included in the questionnaire. In this regard, the demographic questions like gender, education, number of cryptocurrencies held by the respondents, amount invested are retained for the end of the questionnaire. The questionnaire is formulated in such a way that it encapsulates the user perceptions of cryptocurrencies and personality traits driving their behaviour towards the adoption. The questionnaire is designed using Google Forms. Other websites were also considered like SurveyMonkey and Qualtrics but finally Google Forms was found to be the most feasible and economical for the researcher.

The questionnaire went through several stages before its final outcome. Firstly, the draft of the questionnaire was reviewed a number of times by the research and her supervisor. It was revised multiple times, following which a pilot study was conducted.

4.7.2 Pilot Study

A pilot study is conducted to refine the survey questionnaire and evaluate its viability, coherence, and understandability (Saunders et al., 2007; Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). It is essential that the questionnaires must be tested before the final questionnaire is distributed. It is required in order to confirm that the questionnaire is understandable and clear to the respondents (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2013). For the questionnaire of this research, pilot study was conducted with 20 respondents and they were asked to provide their insights regarding its comprehensibility. The respondents belonged to the group of co-workers, batchmates, and acquaintances. Following the pilot study, the respondents were asked to share their opinion regarding the questionnaire, whether they faced any issues, or had any comments or suggestions. Based on the pilot study, several respondents mentioned that the questionnaire was too long. Following this, efforts were made to reduce the length of the questionnaire by eliminating repetitive items and questions from the demographic section. The length of the main research questions couldn't be reduced significantly since they were essential for the intended multi-criterion study. Furthermore, some minor formatting and grammatical issues were identified in the questions, primarily relating to the differences between British and American English. This was promptly rectified and the entire questionnaire proofread. The order of the questions corresponding to some constructs was also slightly altered to make the intentions of the questions easier to follow and to ensure that the more important questions were not likely to be missed by the respondents. With regards to the comprehensibility of the questionnaire, the respondents of the pilot study indicated that the questions were clear and understandable. The pilot study also helped in ensuring the reliability of the questionnaire. It was then reviewed by the Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland, UK and an approval was provided to proceed with administering the questionnaire. It ensured that there were no major ethical issues concerning the study.

4.8 Sampling

Sekaran (2003) defined sampling as “a method of selecting an appropriate number of elements from the population”, such that through the investigation of that sample and the understanding of their traits and attributes one is able to generalise those traits and attributes to the entire population. Sampling is needed since it is almost impossible to collect and scrutinize data of the entire population. Also, it saves time and money. It is important that the sample is for the most part representative of the population. Broadly, there are two kinds of sampling techniques namely Probability Sampling and the other is Non-Probability Sampling (Sekaran, 2003).

Probability sampling entails the situation where the probability or chance of selecting elements from the population is well-known and generally equal without any provision for biases and favouritism. Probability sampling involves statistical estimation of the sample characteristics from the population. Sampling frame is required in the case of probability sampling, which includes an entire list of the cases of the population and from which the sample will be taken. Conversely, with non-probability sampling techniques, the chance or probability of each element being selected from the total population is unknown. It does not require statistical estimation of samples from the population. Probability sampling methods include “Simple random sampling”, “Systematic sampling”, “Stratified-random sampling” and “Cluster sampling”. On the other hand, non-Probability sampling methods include “Quota Sampling”, “Convenience Sampling”, “Snowball Sampling”, “Purposive Sampling” and “Self-reflection Sampling”. For most of the projects, a variety of sampling techniques are used (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009).

It is generally thought that studies in the social sciences rely heavily on non-probability sampling techniques since it becomes difficult to get a clear view of the population and it becomes complicated to accumulate an entire sampling frame. In addition to this, it is not possible to achieve a 100 percent response rate (Rowley, 2014). Since it is generally not possible and appropriate in the field of business research including market surveys or case studies to obtain a sampling frame, in such cases, non-probability sampling techniques provide a solution for selecting the sample which is based on the judgement of the researcher.

In this situation, the sample size would be centred on the objectives of the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). It is observed that a large number of studies depend on purposive, convenience and snowball sampling (Rowley, 2014). The sampling strategy deployed in this research is non-probability sampling comprising a combination of Purposive Sampling and Snowball Sampling.

Purposive sampling is a kind of non-probability sampling method where the researcher selects a sample comprising the target groups which will help the researcher to obtain the required information that are pertinent enough to answer the research question and meet the objectives of the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). This is helpful where the specific group is the only one who has that information or where they meet certain criteria set by the research objectives.

In this case, this is very useful since this research aims to investigate the consumer attitude of people towards cryptocurrencies. It requires recruitment of those participants who have knowledge or experience of cryptocurrencies as well as those who belong to the age group of 21 - 60 years, i.e. respondents that belong to the adult working age group. The target sample must comprise of both users and potential users of cryptocurrencies and possess some requisite knowledge and experience of cryptocurrencies for the purpose of investment or exchange currency. This requirement aligns well with the research objectives and will enable the researcher to draw valid conclusions. People who are not well-informed or are less informed about the cryptocurrencies will not be able to contribute meaningfully for achieving the intents of this study.

The researcher also makes use of Snowball Sampling, i.e. the technique where the initial sample selected by the researcher makes contact with other cases of the population to identify new samples who then make contact with further members of population and this goes on until a large sample is achieved (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). This would aid the researcher in achieving the desired number of participants much efficiently. It will also save time and cost.

4.9 Recruitment of Participants

As mentioned earlier, recruitment of participants took place using non-probability sampling. Through purposive sampling a target group from the professional and social network of the researcher were contacted via emails and messaging. The group primarily comprised cryptocurrency users and enthusiasts and people with technical and financial backgrounds. In addition, the group predominantly consists of cryptocurrency users, potential users and fintech enthusiasts. The colleagues from the researcher's DBA cohort group were contacted and the members who had knowledge and experience regarding cryptocurrencies and who showed interest in filling out the questionnaire were then communicated with through email. Course instructors and various other Professors at the University were also approached.

The survey was made available on the Peer-reflection forum through which all the Professors and Doctoral students of the university were sent an email informing them about the study and requesting them to fill out the questionnaire. Furthermore, co-workers of the researcher and professional network of the researcher on LinkedIn were messaged individually and were requested to spread the word and forward the message to others in their network who satisfied the eligibility criteria. Attempts were made to contact prominent cryptocurrency investors, traders, researchers, Blockchain specialists, Fintech experts, Tech Innovation experts, etc. via LinkedIn and Twitter. If respondents are found to be interested in the survey, they are provided with the consent form, participation information sheet and the survey form. Friends and acquaintances of the researchers who satisfied the eligibility criteria were personally contacted and when they approved their participation in the survey, then the survey was made available to those respondents via email.

All the participants were also requested to forward the information regarding the survey to their social and professional networks. Decentralised finance enthusiasts and cryptocurrency communities on social media platforms were approached to elicit responses. If they showed interest, they were sent the survey form through the email. As all the participants were requested to forward the survey to the individuals who have knowledge or experience of cryptocurrencies, snowball sampling became quite useful in the data collection process.

4.10 Sample Size

The population for this research can be defined as individuals within the age group of 21 to 60 years who have either prior usage experience of cryptocurrencies or are well informed about it. According to some estimates there are presently over 100 million cryptocurrency users (Business Insider, 2021) and their numbers are steadily increasing. A study has found that the majority of the cryptocurrency users are aged between 22-42 (Bohr and Bashir, 2014) and including the number of well-informed non-users of cryptocurrency significantly increases the size of the target population. As per Krejcie and Morgan (1970) “as the size of the population increases, the sample size rises at a diminishing rate and stays relatively constant”. Hence, despite the significantly large size of the population, a large sample size is not required. Sekaran (2003) and Roscoe (1975) state that for most studies a sample size that is greater than 30 and lesser than 500 is considered appropriate. Having a significantly large sample size can cause errors as it may cause even weak relationships to be mistaken as significant relationships in the population (Sekaran, 2003). According to Roscoe (1975) “a research where multivariate analysis is used, the sample size should be at least 10 times the number of variables used in the study”. This is further supported by (Hair et al., 2019) who state that the number of observations should be at least 5 times and preferably 15 to 20 times the number of independent variables.

In the present study the number of independent variables is around 10 and based on the suggestions from (Hair et al., 2019) the appropriate number of observations should therefore lie in the range of 150 to 200. Hence for the present study an intended sample size of 200-250 was considered. Furthermore, studies similar to the present research have also used sample sizes in the same range. A study by (Albayati, Kim and Rho, 2020) using a modified and improved technology acceptance model for investigating behavioural intentions towards blockchain based cryptocurrency transactions used a sample size of 277. by Stewart and Jürjens (2018) in their study on trust and security factors affecting financial technology adoption in Germany using a modified Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) used a sample size of 209 respondents. A study conducted by Gagnon et al. (2012) used a sample size of 234 in their study of acceptance of Telemonitoring System amid the healthcare professionals using modified Technological Acceptance Model (TAM).

4.11 Data Processing

4.11.1 Response Rates and Invalid Responses

Around 1500 people were contacted which led to a total 265 responses. The response rate was calculated to be 17%. Such a value of response rate was expected since the response rates of digital surveys are generally very low (Sekaran, 2003). Out of these 265 responses 6 (2.3%) respondents did not give their consent to take part in the survey. Of the remaining respondents who consented, 33 (12.5%) respondents were ineligible to participate since they claimed they had no idea about cryptocurrencies and 12 (4.5%) respondents did not satisfy the age requirements. The remaining 214 respondents were able to participate in the survey and view the measurement scales.

While most of the responses were complete some of them had missing data in the form of unanswered questions. The average completion rate of the Likert scale questions was 98%. Out of the 214 responses 6 (2.8%) responses were less than 80% complete and 12 (5.6%) were less than 95% complete. The non-response rate was higher in the Demographic section most likely due to being the last section of the questionnaire. In this study, it was decided that the responses with less than 95% completion rate would be discarded. This led to the data consisting of 202 responses which could be utilised for statistical analysis.

4.11.2 Missing Data

After removing the invalid and unsuitable responses, data from 202 participants remain. In this data, it was found that the missing values consisted of only 0.14% of the total data. According to Hair et al. (2019) for datasets with less than 10% missing data any approach of dealing with the missing values is acceptable. For this study, a neutral value imputation method was used wherein the missing data was substituted with the neutral value of the seven-point Likert scale (Malhotra, 2010).

4.11.3 Data Labelling

Following the recording and cleaning of the data, in order to properly analyze it using statistical techniques, variable labels and value labels have to be assigned. Value labels refer to the codes or labels for the responses in our dataset. In this study, the Likert scale labels in the dataset are converted into their corresponding values for their analysis. Since this study

uses a seven-point Likert scale, the values labels range from 1 for Strongly Disagree to 7 for Strongly Agree.

The variable label refers to the code or label assigned to the questions in the survey. The labels are created such that they represent the construct that these scales are measuring. The variable labels for the scale items used in the survey for this study and their corresponding constructs are mentioned in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Variable Labels

Factor Name	Scale Item	Label
Personal Innovativeness (PI)	If I hear about a new technology that I can use, I will look for ways to experiment with it	PI1
	Among my peers, I am usually the first to try out new technologies	PI2
	In general, I am hesitant to try out new technologies	PI3
	I like to experiment with new technologies	PI4
Proactive Personality (PP)	I enjoy facing and overcoming obstacles to my ideas	PP1
	I excel at identifying opportunities	PP2
	I love to challenge the status quo of things	PP3
	I can spot a good opportunity long before others can	PP4
Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	I think that it is easy to make cryptocurrency transactions	PEOU1
	I think that interaction with cryptocurrencies does not require a lot of mental effort	PEOU2
	Learning to use cryptocurrencies would be easy	PEOU3
Perceived Usefulness (PU)	Using cryptocurrencies will improve the profitability of my savings	PU1
	Using cryptocurrencies will allow me to send money inexpensively to anyone in the world	PU2
	Using cryptocurrencies will improve my financial performance	PU3
	Using cryptocurrencies will allow me to increase my productivity	PU4
Technology Anxiety (TA)	It is frightening that I could face financial losses due to mistakes made while using cryptocurrencies	TA1
	I am reluctant to make cryptocurrency transactions due to the risk of making mistakes I cannot correct	TA2
	I feel apprehensive about learning the steps associated with cryptocurrency transactions	TA3
	Cryptocurrency usage is somewhat intimidating to me	TA4

Bandwagon Effect (BE)	I am likely to buy cryptocurrencies used by most investors	BE1
	I am likely to buy popular cryptocurrencies that everyone would know about	BE2
	I am likely to use cryptocurrencies recognized by many investors	BE3
Perceived Trust (PT)	Electronic payments made with cryptocurrencies are trustworthy	PT1
	Using cryptocurrency wallets is reliable	PT2
	I think cryptocurrency transactions are safe	PT3
	Privacy is guaranteed in each cryptocurrency transaction	PT4
Legal Risk (LR)	I feel uncertainty when using cryptocurrencies due to the lack of regulations	LR1
	The legislation regarding cryptocurrency usage is uncertain	LR2
	It is difficult to access various cryptocurrency e-wallets due to government regulations	LR3
	It is difficult to make cryptocurrency transactions due to the government regulation	LR4
Privacy Risk (PR)	I worry about the abuse of my personal data (e.g., transaction and private information) when I use cryptocurrencies	PR1
	My financial information might not be secure when I use cryptocurrencies	PR2
	I worry that someone can access my personal or financial information when I use cryptocurrencies	PR3
Attitude towards Cryptocurrency (ATT)	Using cryptocurrencies is a good idea	ATT1
	Using cryptocurrencies would be a wise idea	ATT2
	I enjoy the idea of using cryptocurrencies	ATT3
	Using cryptocurrencies is a pleasant experience	ATT4
Intention to Adopt (IA)	I intend to use cryptocurrencies	IA1
	I think that I will use cryptocurrencies	IA2
	I plan to invest or trade in cryptocurrencies in future	IA3

	Question	Label
	I give my consent to participating in the research	CONSENT
	What is your previous experience with cryptocurrencies?	EXPERIENCE
	Select your Age group	AGE
	Gender	GENDER
	Educational Qualifications	EDUCATION
	Primary purpose of using cryptocurrencies	PURPOSE
	No. of different cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, Ethereum, etc) you possess	NUMBER
	How much money have you invested in Cryptocurrencies?	AMOUNT

4.12 Ethical and Integrity Issues in Research

The researcher has put in the best efforts to maintain the ethical and integrity considerations in the research. These include taking informed consent (UWS, 2020; ESRC, 2018) which is considered to be the basic or founding principles of research ethics signifying that the participants must be informed clearly as to what they are consenting to. In order to ensure this, voluntary consents were taken from all the participants and detailed information regarding the research and how the data provided by them will be used in the research is also provided to the participants in the Participant Information Sheet.

Details and contact information of the researcher as well as the lead supervisor of the study are also provided to the participants. This will also ensure that important information is not withheld from the participants. This fulfils one of the core principles of ESRC (2018) that research must be conducted with transparency and integrity. ESRC (2018) has also stipulated that there should not be any kind of coercion or undue influence on the participants or respondents. This was made sure since there was no bribery involved for getting the information by coercing people to take part in a type of research that is against their values or principles in exchange for financial compensation.

Another important ethical concern is privacy and confidentiality (UWS, 2020) of the data which is maintained by collecting the data anonymously. For safeguarding the privacy and

confidentiality of the participants, the participants will not be identified personally in the research. Furthermore, the data collected from the respondents will not be shared with anyone other than the researcher.

The principles of good research (UWS, 2020) including honesty, rigour, transparency, respect and care were keenly thought about at every stage of the research process. Utmost care was taken while formulating the questionnaire to ensure that participants are treated with utmost respect and that they are protected from any form of physical, emotional and cultural harm (UWS, 2020). Efforts were also made to keep the personal biases and individual prejudices completely aside during the whole process of completing the research.

UWS (2017) guidelines state that plagiarism is a type of cheating and an attempt to gain an unfair advantage to get better grades in assessments by using another person's work. It is fundamentally ensured by the researcher that the research produced will be completely an original work and appropriately referenced to prevent any kind of plagiarism. Furthermore, data is stored in different places and back-up is taken on a regular basis for maintaining data integrity and avoiding any loss of data.

Above all, the ethics committee at the UWS has also reviewed the study in order to ensure that the researcher maintains the highest ethical and integrity standards. Besides these, the researcher was driven by her individualistic moral and ethical principles and was self-regulated throughout the process of the research project.

Chapter 5 Data Analysis

5.1 Overview of the Chapter

This chapter delves into the quantitative aspect of the study. First, general demographic information about the respondents is provided to get a good understanding of the individuals who participated in the survey and whose views and opinions form the basis of the results of this research. The next section of the chapter looks into the descriptive statistics through which the characteristics of the data are assessed. After being familiar with the data, inferential statistics is then conducted. The data is examined to check if it satisfies the assumptions for multivariate analysis. Then the factor analysis is conducted using the Confirmatory Factor Analysis and further a model is developed using Structural Equation modelling, showing the relationships among the factors that have an influence on the adoption of cryptocurrencies thereby fulfilling the objective of the study. Here, the testing of hypotheses also takes place.

5.2 Demographics

5.2.1 Respondent's Profile

A sample of 202 eligible respondents was considered for the study. The respondents were distributed into 4 age groups comprising of the ages between 21-30, 31-40, 41-50 and 51-60. As can be observed from the table below, out of these 202 respondents 94 (46.5%) i.e., nearly half of the respondents, lay in the age group 21-30. Nearly a quarter, 53 (26.2%) were in the age group 31-40, 37 (18.3%) respondents were part of the age group of 41-50 and 18 (8.9%) respondents belonged to the 51-60 age group. This indicates that the study mostly has the views of the young respondents. It should also be noted that most cryptocurrency users also tend to be young (Bohr and Bashir, 2014) so the cryptocurrency users are well represented. Respondents below the age of 21 and above 60 were not studied since they did not satisfy our eligibility criteria. This information is represented in Table 5.1 and Figure 5.1.

Table 5.1 Age wise distribution of respondents

Years	Frequency	Percent (%)
21-30	94	46.5
31-40	53	26.2
41-50	37	18.3
51-60	18	8.9
Total	202	100.0

Figure 5.1 Age wise distribution of respondents

As far as gender of the respondents is considered, it was observed that 144 (71.3%), i.e., a majority of the respondents were male while about a quarter were female, i.e., 55 (27.2%). One respondent did not identify with either gender and the rest chose not to share their gender preferences. The distribution of the participants as per the gender is provided in Table 5.2 and Figure 5.2 below.

Table 5.2 Gender wise distribution of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)
Female	55	27.2
Male	144	71.3
Prefer not to say	1	0.5
other	1	0.5
Total	201	99.5

Figure 5.2 Gender wise distribution of respondents

Next looking at the highest education qualification of the respondents, 85 respondents that is 42.1% held a Master’s degree. This was the largest group. 46 (22.8%) respondents held a bachelor’s degree, 37 respondents that is 18.3% held a Doctorate degree, 28 (13.9%) respondents held a professional degree, 3 respondents i.e., 1.5% held only a high school degree or equivalent and 2 respondents i.e., 1.0% held some college credit but no degree. This denotes that most respondents to this survey were postgraduates with extensive education. This information is shown below in Table 5.3 and Figure 5.3.

Table 5.3 Education wise distribution of respondents

Education	Frequency	Percent (%)
High School Degree or Equivalent	3	1.5
Some College Credit, No Degree	2	1.0
Bachelor's degree	46	22.8
Master's degree	85	42.1
Professional degree	28	13.9
Doctorate degree	37	18.3
Prefer not to say	1	0.5
Total	202	100.0

Figure 5.3 Education Qualification wise distribution of respondents

5.2.2 Cryptocurrency Usage Profile

As far as experience with cryptocurrencies is considered, out of the total 259 people who consented to participate in the survey, 33 people who had no idea about cryptocurrencies. These were considered ineligible to participate in the study. After further discarding of the ineligible respondents based on their age and level of completion of the survey, 202 respondents were left. The results showed that 114 i.e., 56.4% out of these 202 respondents had some prior experience with cryptocurrencies. 46 (22.8%) out of these reported of having

extensive experience in using cryptocurrencies, while 68 (33.7%) respondents considered they had beginner level experience with cryptocurrencies. On the other hand, 88 (43.6%) stated they had no prior usage experience with cryptocurrencies but were well informed about them. This indicates that more than half of the respondents were cryptocurrency users while the rest could be considered as potential users. Hence the results of this study would represent perceptions of both users and potential users. Table 5.4 and Figure 5.4 below represent this information.

Table 5.4 Distribution of respondents based on usage experience

Experience	Frequency	Percent (%)
Well informed about cryptocurrencies but have no prior experience with them	88	43.6
Have beginner level experience with trading, using, or investing in cryptocurrencies	68	33.7
Have extensive experience with trading, using, or investing in cryptocurrencies	46	22.8
Total	202	100.0

Figure 5.4 Distribution of respondents based on usage experience

There are various cryptocurrencies in the market such as Bitcoin, Ethereum, Ripple etc. With regards to the number of cryptocurrencies possessed by the respondents of this survey, 96 of

them which is 47.5% presently did not possess any cryptocurrency, 15 respondents forming 7.4% possessed 1, 29 which is 14.4% possessed 2, 13 that is 6.4% possessed 3, 4 respondents which is 2.0% of them possessed 4, and 44 i.e., 21.8% possessed 5 or more cryptocurrencies. This implies that most users who currently hold cryptocurrencies possess more than 5 cryptocurrencies. The number of cryptocurrencies possessed is depicted in Table 5.5 and Figure 5.5 below.

Table 5.5 Number of cryptocurrencies respondents possess

Number	Frequency	Percent (%)
0	96	47.5
1	15	7.4
2	29	14.4
3	13	6.4
4	4	2.0
5 and above	44	21.8
Total	201	99.5

Figure 5.5 Number of cryptocurrencies respondents possess

In terms of the amount invested in cryptocurrencies in USD, 190 respondents chose to share their information. It was seen that most of the respondents that is 111 (55.0%) of them had

either not invested or invested up to \$500, 36 respondents (17.8%) mentioned that they had invested \$500 - \$2,000, 13 respondents (6.4%) had invested \$2,000 - \$5,000, 8 respondents (4.0%) had invested \$5,000 - \$10,000 and 22 respondents mentioned (10.9%) that they had invested more than \$10,000. The above information is shown in Table 5.6 and Figure 5.6.

Table 5.6 Amount invested in of cryptocurrencies by the respondents

Amount (\$)	Frequency	Percent (%)
USD 0 - 500	111	55.0
USD 500 - 2,000	36	17.8
USD 2,000 - 5,000	13	6.4
USD 5,000 -10,000	8	4.0
More than USD 10,000	22	10.9
Total	190	94.1

Figure 5.6 Amount invested in of cryptocurrencies by the respondents

Information was also gathered regarding the respondent’s purpose of using cryptocurrency and it was found that most users intended to use cryptocurrencies for more than one purpose. There were four options provided to the respondents Monetary Transactions, Long Term Trading, Short Term Trading, Other. Out of the 202 eligible respondents, 193 answered this question. The results indicated that 58 (28.7%) respondents were interested in using

cryptocurrencies for monetary transactions out of which 17 (8.4%) wanted to use them only for this purpose. 102 (50.5%) respondents were interested in using cryptocurrencies for long term investment while 63 (31.2%) were using them for short term investment. Out of the respondents who were interested in long term investment, 50 (24.8%) i.e., a quarter of all respondents, wanted to use cryptocurrencies for the sole purpose of long-term investment while 27 (13.4%) only wanted them for short term investments. In total, 135 (66.8%) were interested in cryptocurrencies as an instrument for investment either long term or short term or both. Furthermore, 34 respondents (18.8%) were neither interested in using cryptocurrencies for monetary transactions nor for the purpose of investments. The results indicate most respondents are interested in using cryptocurrencies for the purpose of investment rather than as a medium for monetary transactions. This information is summarised in the Table 5.7 and Figure 5.7 below.

Table 5.7 Purpose of using cryptocurrencies by the respondents

Monetary Transactions	Long Term Trading	Short Term Trading	Other	Frequency	Percent (%)
•				17	8.4
•	•			14	6.9
•	•	•		15	7.4
•	•	•	•	2	1.0
•	•		•	3	1.5
•		•		4	2.0
•			•	3	1.5
	•			50	24.8
	•	•		11	5.4
	•	•	•	2	1.0
	•		•	5	2.5
		•		27	13.4
		•	•	2	1.0
			•	38	18.8
Total				193	95.5

A • represents intention to use cryptocurrencies for that purpose.

Figure 5.7 Purpose of using cryptocurrencies by the respondents

5.3 Descriptive Statistics

5.3.1 Mean Statistic

The mean of the data provides an opportunity to gauge the average opinion of all the respondents towards each measurement item. The mean is computed using the formula

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

Where $\bar{X}$ is the mean,

x_i are the individual data points and

n is the total number of data points

Since a 7-point Likert scale is utilised for measuring the responses, so the numerical mean values can be interpreted using the following

- | | | | |
|-----------------------------|--------------------|-----------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1: Strongly Disagree | 2: Disagree | 3: Somewhat Disagree | 4: Neither Agree nor Disagree |
| 5: Somewhat Agree | 6: Agree | 7: Strongly Agree | |

5.3.2 Standard Deviation Statistic

The “standard deviation” measures the variation in the data i.e., “it is an indicator of the spread of the data w.r.t the mean value”. The “square of the standard deviation” is the variance of the dataset. The standard deviation for a sample dataset is computed using the following

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{X})^2}{n}}$$

Where s is the standard deviation,

$\bar{X}$ is the mean

x_i are the individual data points and

n is the total number of data points

On the basis of the Table 5.8 it is observed that the constructs measuring intention to adopt cryptocurrencies have a mean value close to 5 with a standard deviation close to 1.6. A value of 5 corresponds to Somewhat Agree on the 7-point Likert scale. This indicates that the average opinion of the respondents of the survey tends to somewhat agree that they either use or intend to use cryptocurrencies. The standard deviation indicates that the opinion of most respondents lies between somewhat disagree to strongly agree. Similarly, the average of the opinions of the respondents also indicate that they tend to have a somewhat agreeable attitude towards using cryptocurrencies.

The following table shows the descriptive statistics for the 202 eligible data points while summarising the mean, standard deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis for the 40 measurement items.

Table 5.8 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Personal Innovativeness	PI1	5.41	1.223	-0.949	1.39
	PI2	4.77	1.469	-0.38	-0.513
	PI3	5.08	1.502	-0.474	-0.674

	PI4	5.37	1.252	-0.892	0.879
Proactive Personality	PP1	5.55	1.201	-1.161	1.603
	PP2	5.38	1.18	-1.072	1.198
	PP3	5.56	1.213	-1.107	1.165
	PP4	4.95	1.269	-0.423	0.107
Perceived Ease of Use	PEOU1	4.47	1.597	-0.312	-0.9
	PEOU2	3.88	1.604	0.144	-0.951
	PEOU3	4.46	1.599	-0.539	-0.662
Perceived Usefulness	PU1	4.45	1.627	-0.432	-0.44
	PU2	5.13	1.656	-0.872	-0.025
	PU3	4.68	1.555	-0.567	-0.192
	PU4	4.17	1.624	-0.275	-0.568
Technology anxiety	TA1	5.07	1.521	-0.744	-0.21
	TA2	4.15	1.771	-0.181	-1.095
	TA3	3.92	1.855	-0.032	-1.158
	TA4	3.76	1.78	0.057	-1.126
Bandwagon Effect	BE1	4.73	1.528	-0.613	-0.277
	BE2	4.74	1.576	-0.568	-0.294
	BE3	4.9	1.558	-0.806	-0.036
Perceived Trust	PT1	5.11	1.372	-0.499	-0.511
	PT2	4.92	1.317	-0.552	-0.216
	PT3	5.02	1.444	-0.645	-0.213

	PT4	4.58	1.626	-0.441	-0.529
Legal Risk	LR1	4.73	1.702	-0.522	-0.671
	LR2	5.3	1.552	-0.926	0.31
	LR3	4.71	1.648	-0.325	-0.974
	LR4	4.61	1.82	-0.288	-1.114
Privacy Risk	PR1	3.8	1.776	0.115	-1.04
	PR2	3.88	1.71	0.02	-0.999
	PR3	3.83	1.797	0.044	-1.17
Attitude	ATT1	5.11	1.45	-0.755	0.103
	ATT2	5.01	1.409	-0.501	-0.257
	ATT3	5.11	1.482	-0.643	-0.261
	ATT4	4.73	1.406	-0.252	-0.441
Intention to Adopt	IA1	4.99	1.671	-0.591	-0.653
	IA2	5.06	1.681	-0.686	-0.534
	IA3	5.09	1.693	-0.675	-0.433

5.4 Assumptions of Multivariate Analysis

Before performing structural equation modelling analysis on the proposed model, first the data needs to be analysed in order to ensure that it satisfies the assumptions of multivariate analysis.

5.4.1 Normality

As per Hair et al. (2019) normality denotes “the extent to which a distribution resembles a normal distribution”. The normal distribution is a “bell-shaped” curve that is symmetrical about its mean value. For a sufficiently large sample taken from any population, the

distribution of the sample tends to a normal distribution with its mean and standard deviation approaching those of the population (Sekaran, 2003). While the normality of the distribution of data is a crucial assumption for any multivariate analysis (Hair et al., 2019), according to (Ghasemi and Zahediasl, 2012) for sufficiently large (>40) values of the sample size, violation of the normality assumption is not a significant issue. This is further backed by (Hair et al., 2019) which comments that for sample size exceeding 200, the effect of deviations from normality is negligible. Nevertheless, it is wise to examine the data for indications of non-normality before proceeding to analyse it using multivariate analysis. The non-normality of a distribution is characterised using two quantities Skewness and Kurtosis.

$$SI = \frac{n}{(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \bar{X}}{s} \right)^3$$

Where SI is the skewness,

$\bar{X}$ is the mean of the sample

x_i are the individual data points

n is the sample size and

s is the standard deviation of the sample

Skewness measures the asymmetry of a distribution. A distribution with zero skewness is symmetrical like the Normal distribution, while a positively or negatively skewed distribution is denser on one side and tails in the right or the left direction (Hair et al., 2019). Further Kline (2011) commends that the range of the skewness could lie in the range of -3 to +3 is satisfactory, while according to Field (2013) and Kim (2013) the value for skewness should not be more than ± 2 . The values of Skewness for the measurement scales in this study are listed in Table 5.8. As can be noted all items in this study have Skewness in the range less than 2, and most have values even less than 1.

$$K = \frac{n-1}{(n-2)(n-3)} [(n+1)g_2 + 6]$$

Where K is the kurtosis,

n is the sample size

$$g_2 = \frac{m_4}{m_2^2}$$

m_r is the r^{th} moment of the sample

Kurtosis is another property of a distribution that can be used to gauge its deviation from normality. The kurtosis of a distribution reflects its flatness or peakedness with reference to a normal distribution. Hair et al. (2019) stipulated that “a kurtosis value of zero reflects a distribution akin to the normal distribution, while a positive or negative value implies a more peaked or a comparatively flat distribution”. This value of kurtosis is also referred to as the “excess” kurtosis and is the value calculated by programs like SPSS (Kim, 2013). This is the value mentioned in the table above. Field (2013) states that an adequate value for kurtosis is less than 2. Furthermore, Kim (2013) stipulates that a measure called “proper” kurtosis can be obtained by adding 3 to the value of “excess” kurtosis. According to Kline (2011) a “proper” kurtosis value of more than 7 would indicate a significant deviation from normality. Hence the “excess” kurtosis value should be less than 4. The value of Kurtosis for all the measurement items of this study is stated in Table 5.8. As can be seen all items have a Kurtosis value less than 2. Hence, it can be concluded that the data used in this research poses sufficient degree of normality. Furthermore, Hair et al. (2019) also noted that since the sample size of the study is greater than 200 hence the implications of any deviation from normality are also not very important.

5.4.2 Univariate and Multivariate Outliers

As per Hair et al. (2019) outliers are observations that have values that are extreme in one or several aspects as compared to the rest of the observations, thereby making them significantly different from most of the other observations. Having outliers in the sample can substantially distort statistical quantities including mean, correlations etc computed from it and affect their ability to fairly represent the underlying population. Therefore, it becomes important to identify and take care of outliers in the data.

The outliers in the sample can be categorised as univariate outliers or multivariate outliers. The univariate outlier is a data point that is extreme in a single variable (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013) whereas a multivariate outlier is an observation that has an abnormal value on two or more variables (Kline, 2015). Most of the analysis concerning the detection and identification of univariate and multivariate outlier relates to coming up with a metric to objectively detect and classify observations as outliers (Hair et al., 2019). For Univariate Outliers, the usual

approach to detect an abnormal value is by evaluating standard scores (z) from the data values and then observing if any data point has unusually high value of z (Hair et al., 2019; Kline, 2015).

$$z = \frac{x_i - \bar{X}}{s}$$

Where z is the standard score,

$\bar{X}$ is the mean of the sample

x_i are the individual data points and

s is the standard deviation of the sample

The z score for a data point indicates how many standard deviations away it is from the mean value. Based on this, there are several suggested cut off values of z in literature for identifying univariate outliers. According to Tabachnick & Fidell (2007) data points with value of z greater than $z = \pm 3.2$ should be considered outliers and discarded. For dataset that has a normal distribution, 99.7% of the observations are presumed to lie within the three standard deviations from the mean. This cut off value runs into problem when dealing with large sample size. Larger samples are naturally expected to have more data points with larger z scores compared to smaller samples. Hence, Hair et al. (2019) proposed a cut off value of $z = \pm 4$ for research with sample size greater than 200. As a consequence of the larger sample size of this study, this cut off criteria was utilised.

The present study utilizes 40 measurement items to measure 11 constructs. The z score was computed corresponding to each of these measured variables and then analysed. The most extreme z score for any data point was found to be -3.7 for a particular data point in PP1. This aligns with the observation that PP1 also has the largest value of Kurtosis ($K = 1.603$), as can be seen in the table above. This indicates that the distribution of PP1 data deviates the most from a normal distribution when compared to other measured items, although it is still within the acceptable range and hence nearly normal. Since this value of z-score still satisfies the $z < \pm 4$ criteria proposed by Hair et al. (2019), hence it is not categorised as an outlier. Therefore, no univariate outliers were identified in the data of this study.

Now, the data is analysed for identification of multivariate outliers. As discussed previously, multivariate outliers have atypical values in multiple variables and so the previous method of

z-score cannot be directly applied. This is because an outlier data point can be far from mean for multiple variables, i.e. have high z-scores for multiple variables, while still satisfying the univariate cut off criteria. Such a data point will not reveal itself as a univariate outlier, rather it will require multivariate outlier analysis for its detection (Kline, 2015). For such multivariate outliers a method utilising Mahalanobis distance is most often used (Hair et al., 2019). Mahalanobis distance (D^2), named after Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis, is a quantity to measure the separation between a distribution and a point in multidimensional space (Hair et al., 2019).

$$D^2 = (\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{X}})^t C^{-1} (\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{X}})$$

Where D^2 is the Mahalanobis distance,

$\bar{\mathbf{X}} = (\bar{X}_1, \bar{X}_2, \bar{X}_3 \dots)$ is a vector composed of the mean values for each variables

$\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots)$ is the vector corresponding to the individual data points

C^{-1} is the inverse of the covariance matrix and

t represents the transpose of the vector

In case of uncorrelated variables, Mahalanobis distance is equal to the Euclidean distance between the vectors $\mathbf{x}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$ (De Maesschalck, Jouan-Rimbaud and Massart, 2000). In the univariate case, the general criteria for detecting outliers was by looking at how far away a data point was from the mean value, measured using the z-score. In the multivariate case, a similar approach is tried where the Mahalanobis distance is computed between each observation and the mean point in the multivariate space (Kline, 2015). As per Hair et al. (2019), a data point can be considered multivariate outlier if the value of D^2/df for the data point is greater than 2.5 if the sample is small and greater than 3 if the sample is large. Here df signifies the number of variables involved.

By using SPSS, Mahalanobis distance (D^2) was computed for each observation. Since the number of measured variables (df) is 40, so the computed distance was divided by 40 to calculate D^2/df . The largest value of D^2/df was found to be 2.45. This is below the cut off value of 2.5 proposed by Hair et al. (2019). Thus, multivariate outliers were also not found in the dataset of this study.

5.4.3 Linearity

Linearity refers to the property that the relation between the dependant and the independent variables follow a straight line. In other words, a unit change of the independent variable leads to a proportionate and constant change in the dependant variable. A linear relation between a dependent variable y and an independent variables x_1 can be represented as

$$y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + e$$

Where b_0 is a constant and b_1 represent coefficients corresponding to the variables x_1 and e represents the error term.

Hair et al. (2019) postulated that the assumption concerning linearity is important in all multivariate methods that are based on utilising correlational measures such as Multilinear Regression, Factor Analysis, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) etc. This is because the correlation measures do not capture the contribution of non-linearity in the relation between variables. Therefore, if the data does not portray the requisite linearity between the dependent and independent variables, it is possible that one may be led to an incorrect estimate of the strength of relationships among them (Hair et al., 2019). Hence if linearity is violated, the coefficients and regression weights computed using the multivariate techniques will not be reliable (Kline, 2015). Moreover, unlike other issues, such as lack of normality in the data, that can be effectively tackled by increasing the sample size of the study, if the assumption of linearity is not satisfied then increasing the sample size will also be futile (Hair et al., 2019). In such cases, where the sample exhibits significant non-linearity appropriate alternative methods such as Nonlinear Regression, Polynomial models, Exponential models etc needs to be utilised.

A straightforward way to check linearity of relation between two variables is by looking at the bivariate scatterplot (Kline, 2015). A scatterplot can aide in recognizing nonlinear pattern in the relation by making them visually apparent. If the scatter plot between the dependent variable and the independent variables approximates a straight line or an oval then it implies there exists a linear relation or no relation, thereby satisfying the linearity assumption for multivariate analysis (Hair et al., 2009; Anderson, 2013). However, if the relationship is nonlinear then the scatter plot would appear like a nonlinear curve for example similar to a polynomial curve or an exponential curve.

Below in Figure 5.8 the scatter plots are drawn between Intention to adopt cryptocurrencies (IA) and the remaining variables. The sum of the measurement items is used to represent the corresponding constructs.

Figure 5.8 Scatterplot between Intention to Adopt (IA) and the remaining variables

As can be observed all scatter plots either approximate a straight line or an oval and so the linearity assumption is satisfied by the study. Furthermore, while linearity is an essential assumption of multivariate analysis, it was found by Schreiber et al. (2006) that most studies using structural equation modelling do not explicitly discuss linearity in their research articles.

5.4.4 Collinearity and Multicollinearity

As per Hair et al. (2019) the two variables are considered to be collinear if the correlation between them is high. An extreme case of this is complete collinearity which occurs when the correlation coefficient among the two variables is exactly 1. On the other hand, if the variables have a correlation coefficient of 0 then they are said to exhibit a lack of collinearity (Hair et al., 2009). Collinearity poses an issue since if the two variables are extremely correlated then they do not capture independent information. This indicates that variables might exhibit collinearity if despite appearing distinct, they are actually measuring the same quantity (Kline, 2015). Therefore, collinearity naturally causes problems in determining the contribution of each of the independent variables (Hair et al., 2009) and having high collinearity reduces the reliability of the computed regression weights (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The way to deal with collinearity is then to keep only one of the two variables in the analysis, since the other is essentially redundant (Kline, 2015). In order to detect occurrences of collinearity, Hair et al. (2009) proposed that if the bivariate correlation coefficient is greater than 0.9 then one may claim that the pair of variables exhibit collinearity. In the data of the present study, the bivariate correlation for all constructs were found to be less than 0.9. Hence no collinearity was observed between any pair of constructs. The bivariate correlation for the constructs used in this research is given in Table 5.9.

Table 5.9 Bivariate Correlation Matrix

	PI	PP	PEOU	PU	TA	BE	PT	LR	PR	ATT	IA
PI	1	0.44*** (< 0.001)	0.15* (0.034)	0.38*** (< 0.001)	-0.22*** (0.001)	0.23*** (0.001)	0.29*** (< 0.001)	-0.07 (0.325)	-0.14* (0.050)	0.35*** (< 0.001)	0.36*** (< 0.001)
PP		1	0.20** (0.005)	0.37*** (< 0.001)	-0.03 (0.713)	0.19** (0.006)	0.27*** (< 0.001)	0.01 (0.882)	0.03 (0.628)	0.28*** (< 0.001)	0.29*** (< 0.001)
PEOU			1	0.43*** (< 0.001)	-0.13 (0.065)	0.27*** (< 0.001)	0.40*** (< 0.001)	-0.20** (0.005)	-0.13 (0.059)	0.33*** (< 0.001)	0.30*** (< 0.001)
PU				1	-0.13 (0.075)	0.31*** (< 0.001)	0.47*** (< 0.001)	-0.24*** (0.001)	-0.19** (0.007)	0.65*** (< 0.001)	0.59*** (< 0.001)
TA					1	-0.16* (0.020)	-0.13 (0.066)	0.43*** (0.001)	0.42*** (< 0.001)	-0.24*** (0.001)	-0.28*** (< 0.001)
BE						1	0.33*** (< 0.001)	0.10 (0.167)	-0.13 (0.060)	0.47*** (< 0.001)	0.56*** (< 0.001)
PT							1	-0.14* (0.050)	-0.34*** (< 0.001)	0.49*** (< 0.001)	0.41*** (< 0.001)
LR								1	0.37*** (< 0.001)	-0.25*** (< 0.001)	-0.15* (0.034)
PR									1	-0.30*** (< 0.001)	-0.31*** (< 0.001)
ATT										1	0.80*** (< 0.001)
IA											1

Values in bold are the correlation values and values in brackets represent the p-values.

*** Represents significance at the 0.001 level (2-tailed)

** Represents significance at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* Represents significance at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

An extension of the concept of collinearity is multicollinearity, which occurs when an independent variable exhibits a high degree of correlation with two or more variables together (Kline, 2015). In other words, it is the collinearity due to the collective contribution of multiple variables (Hair et al., 2009). An example of this would be to consider an independent construct created from the sum of two or more constructs (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In this case while the individual constructs may not display collinearity with the composite construct, the composite construct would be completely collinear with their combination and hence cannot be treated as independent variable and used alongside the individual constructs (Kline, 2015). This also reveals that just looking at the bivariate correlations is not sufficient to identify instances of multicollinearity. So, to detect these, new

measures called Tolerance Value and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) are introduced (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Tolerance Value for an independent variable is defined by Hair et al. (2019) as “the extent of its variance that is not explained by the remaining independent variables”. Mathematically it is $1 - R^2$. Where R^2 represents the coefficient of determination that is described as the fraction of explained variance. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is just the inverse of the Tolerance Value, that is, $VIF = 1/(1 - R^2)$. (Kline, 2015) described the method to identify multicollinearity using these quantities. First each of the independent variable is regarded as the dependent variable as well as regressed with the remaining independent variables. The R^2 from this is examined and the tolerance value and VIF is calculated for each independent variable. Then if the value of tolerance is found to be less than 0.10 or in other words $VIF > 10.0$ then this indicates the existence of multicollinearity. This is because if tolerance is less than 0.10 then R^2 is greater than 0.90 which denotes that over 90% of the variance of the independent variable is explained by the rest of the variables. Another more stringent criteria of VIF greater than 5 is suggested by (Hair et al., 2019).

For this study, the tolerance value and VIF corresponding to the independent variables is computed and mentioned in Table 5.10 below. As can be observed the tolerance value comes out to be greater than 0.10 for all the variables and the VIF is less than 5. Hence the condition regarding lack of multicollinearity for reliable interpretation of the regression coefficients in multivariate analysis is satisfied.

Table 5.10 Conditions for Lack of Multicollinearity

Construct		R^2 (< 0.90)	Tolerance (> 0.10)	VIF (< 10.0)
Personal Innovativeness	PI	0.302	0.698	1.43
Proactive Personality	PP	0.284	0.716	1.40
Perceived Ease of Use	PEOU	0.261	0.739	1.35
Perceived Usefulness	PU	0.520	0.480	2.08
Technology Anxiety	TA	0.300	0.700	1.42
Bandwagon Effect	BE	0.328	0.672	1.49
Perceived trust	PT	0.384	0.616	1.62
Legal Risk	LR	0.339	0.661	1.51
Privacy Risk	PR	0.315	0.685	1.46
Attitude	ATT	0.558	0.442	2.26

5.5 Factor Analysis

A factor is defined as a construct that is a reduced statement for the relationships among the variables (Kline, 1994). Also, Royce (1963) explained that a factor can be understood as a true variable or a determinant that justifies the covariation in that particular field of observation. Factors are defined corresponding to their factor loadings and the factor loadings are defined as the correlations of a factor or a construct corresponding to their measured variables or items. Factor analysis is the method of deriving factor loadings on the basis of which factors are assessed and is helpful in simplifying the correlation matrices (Kline, 1994). There are mainly two ways in which factor analysis can be conducted (Hair et al., 2019). It can be either Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), where the primary goal is to explore the concepts and come up with new constructs, or it can be Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) wherein the variables corresponding to constructs have already been specified based on either theory or prior research (Kline, 1994) and the aim is to confirm them. Factor analysis was initially conceived as EFA by Spearman (1904) for their research in psychology and is one of the earliest statistical methods for analysing unobserved constructs (Kline, 2015). CFA was then later proposed by Joreskog (1969) and is now a crucial part of structural equation modelling (SEM) which is

discussed later is Section 5.6 (Kline, 1994). For the purpose of this present research, the technique of CFA is used for conducting factor analysis.

5.5.1 Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)

Confirmatory factor analysis is a method of examining if the already specified measurement theory, comprised of the measured variables, fits the actual reality as represented by the collected data (Hair et al., 2019). It is a method of confirming the theory where the analysis is conducted based on the relations defined by the theory among the unobserved and observed constructs. A “hypothesised model” is utilised to compute an estimated covariance matrix which is then matched with the corresponding matrix obtained from the covariances in the sample. It must be noted that the difference between the two matrices must be minimum (Schreiber et al., 2006). It can be said that the CFA method is applied to determine whether or not there is a relationship between the measured scale items or constructs and the latent variables that underlie these variables, or unobserved variables. It also measures whether or not the hypothesised structure offers a satisfactory match to the data (Child, 1990).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is distinct from the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) because in CFA the number of factors as well as the factors or the constructs on which each measured item will load on are already defined based on the theory before computing the results. In the statistical method of CFA, there is no assignment of measured variables to the constructs (Hair et al., 2019) whereas in EFA method, the measurement takes place by determination of the number of factors that are needed for the representation of the data and it also determines the factor loadings for all the variables on every factor (Hair et al., 2019). Hence, in this research, method of CFA must be applied to the data since the number of factors or constructs and the measured items that will load on each construct are already specified based on the theoretical explanations which are given in the section 4 of the literature review. It can also be said that this research rather looks for confirming or testing of the predefined theories. Also, when using the statistical analysis method of SEM in a research, CFA is considered to be more useful because it is a confirmatory method (Schreiber et al., 2006).

In order to perform confirmatory factor analysis, first all the constructs are tested for their unidimensionality, reliability and validity. Then the goodness of fit of the CFA model is assessed. The CFA model is made by treating all the measurement models as correlated. Measurement model refers to “the model that signifies the relation between the unobserved measured items and the corresponding constructs they represent” (Hair et al., 2019). In this research, the AMOS software from IBM was utilised for performing confirmatory factor analysis. The research model proposed for this study consists of 11 constructs that are measured using a total of 40 measured variables. These constructs were selected based on their role in consumer psychology theories, theories of technology adoption, and theories of risk and trust. Their corresponding measured variables were taken from pre-existing literature in these fields. These constructs and their items, along with their codes have been listed in Table 5.11. Using AMOS, the factor loadings were calculated for these. All of these loadings were found to be statistically significant at the level of $p < 0.001$.

Table 5.11 Factor Loadings

Factors	Items	Factor Loadings
Personal Innovativeness	→ PI1	0.924
	→ PI2	0.726
	→ PI3	0.304
	→ PI4	0.764
Proactive Personality	→ PP1	0.653
	→ PP2	0.831
	→ PP3	0.747
	→ PP4	0.720
Perceived Ease of Use	→ PEOU1	0.592
	→ PEOU2	0.815
	→ PEOU3	0.709

Perceived Usefulness	→	PU1	0.820
	→	PU2	0.679
	→	PU3	0.920
	→	PU4	0.764
Technology anxiety	→	TA1	0.611
	→	TA2	0.747
	→	TA3	0.752
	→	TA4	0.701
Bandwagon Effect	→	BE1	0.888
	→	BE2	0.904
	→	BE3	0.910
Perceived Trust	→	PT1	0.819
	→	PT2	0.761
	→	PT3	0.880
	→	PT4	0.487
Legal Risk	→	LR1	0.652
	→	LR2	0.473
	→	LR3	0.906
	→	LR4	0.905
Privacy Risk	→	PR1	0.836
	→	PR2	0.894
	→	PR3	0.962

Attitude towards Using Cryptocurrencies	→	ATT1	0.961
	→	ATT2	0.948
	→	ATT3	0.883
	→	ATT4	0.782
Intention to Adopt	→	IA1	0.948
	→	IA2	0.980
	→	IA3	0.870

Following the calculation of the factor loadings, the next step is to ascertain that the requirement of unidimensionality is satisfied. This is then followed by verifying the reliability and validity of the factors (Hair et al., 2009). Finally, the goodness of fit of the factor analysis model is determined.

5.5.2 Unidimensionality

Unidimensionality is one of the crucial assumptions of confirmatory or even exploratory statistical techniques (Segars, 1997; McGartland Rubio, Berg-Weger and Tebb, 2001; Gerbing and Anderson, 1988). Unidimensionality is defined by Hattie (1985) as “the existence of a single trait or construct underlying a set of measures”. Unidimensional measures refer to those measured variables that are described by just one fundamental construct. The assumption of unidimensionality becomes essential in the case of multiple constructs in the analysis (Hair et al., 2019). Unidimensionality is also considered important for the construct validity (McGartland Rubio, Berg-Weger and Tebb, 2001), it is said that the data lacks construct validity when there are substantial cross loadings in the model (Hair et al., 2019). The cross-loadings which refer to the loadings of one measured variable on more than one construct in the same model are assumed to be zero. Also, there are no connections among the error terms (Hair et al., 2019). When considering the covariances among the error terms of the measured variables, they are of two types (1) “within construct error covariances” which means that there are covariances between the error terms of the measurement items

representing a single construct. (2) “between construct error terms” which means that covariance exists among the two error terms of the measurement items representing distinct constructs (Hair et al., 2019). It is observed that by applying (1) or (2) in the model will improve the chi square test but simply bring up questions regarding their construct validity or discriminant validity.

It is suggested that Unidimensionality can be determined using both Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) (Hair et al., 2019). Although, it is explained by Gerbing and Anderson (1988) that CFA is one of the best ways of determining unidimensionality. Since this research performs CFA, so the same is also used for evaluating unidimensionality. Furthermore, Janssens et al. (2009) has elucidated that when the value of factor loadings for any measurement items is less than 0.5, then the model is not considered to adhere to the assumption of unidimensionality. So, the factor loadings determined through CFA in this research are verified for confirming unidimensionality. It was determined that the factor loadings for most of the measurement variables are more than 0.5 or are closer to this value. The exception to this is the factor loading corresponding to Personal Innovativeness and PI3, which shows a value of 0.304. This is much lower than the limit of 0.5. Hence, the item PI3 is deleted from any further calculation for the development of the model. Regarding the factor loadings for LR2 which is 0.428 and PT4 which is 0.486, they are not deleted from the model since Kline (1994) mentioned that the factor loadings are considered to be high when they are more than 0.6 and moderately high when they are more than 0.3. Due to this reason, values corresponding to LR2 and PT4 are considered for further analysis.

Once unidimensionality is established, the new factor loadings that do not contain the item PI3 are calculated using AMOS. These remaining measurement items and the new factor loadings, henceforth simply called factor loadings, are now used for the purpose of all following calculations. These are mentioned in Table 5.13 later.

5.5.3 Reliability

Reliability is defined as “the extent to which variables in the study are consistent as well as stable for what they are expected to measure” (Hair et al., 2019; Carmines and Zeller, 1979). It can be said that reliability involves repeatability (Moser and Kalton, 1985). Stability and

consistency are the two major components of reliability. When a measure remains the same over a period of time despite the changes in the circumstances, it is considered to be stable. For instance, if the questionnaire with the same items is distributed to the same respondents again on another occasion i.e., after a certain amount of time. The tests of stability comprise of test-retest reliability and the other parallel-form reliability (Sekaran, 2003). Whereas internal Consistency is associated with the homogeneity in the items such that all the items measuring the same concept are highly correlated. This implies that all the items representing a variable, if measured independently should reflect the same overall meaning to the respondent. The most commonly and extensively used test for reliability is Cronbach's α . It is used for determining the internal consistency of the instrument (Sekaran, 2003; Hair et al., 2019). Another commonly used measure is Composite Reliability (CR). In a research by Hair et al. (2011) of highly reputed studies that used Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), it was found that most of the recent studies used either Composite Reliability or both Composite Reliability and Cronbach's α to gauge the internal consistency.

5.5.3.1 Cronbach's alpha

Cronbach's α , also referred to as Cronbach's alpha, was first proposed by L. J. Cronbach in 1946 as a measure of reliability coefficient (Sekaran, 2003). It is defined as the average of all correlations from the split-half tests taking every combination of splittings (Cronbach, 1951). The result for this test ranges between 0 to 1. A drawback of using Cronbach's alpha is that it may underestimate the reliability (Hair et al., 2019). According to Nunnally (1978); Hair et al. (2019), the value of Cronbach's alpha must be more than 0.7 for instruments used in basic research. Although Hair et al. (2019) reported that variables with α in the range 0.6 – 0.7 may also be considered acceptable for exploratory studies.

Table 5.12 summarises the values of Cronbach's alpha for the variables used in this study. It was found that all the constructs satisfy the criteria of $\alpha > 0.7$ and thereby display strong internal reliability. Following the descriptors mentioned in Taber (2017) the α values for the constructs Attitude towards using cryptocurrencies and Intentions to adopt can be considered as excellent. Further, Bandwagon Effect and Privacy Risk have a strong α , while Proactive Personality, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Innovativeness, Perceived Trust, Legal Risk has α that are robust and reliable. The α for Technology anxiety is high and for Perceived Ease of Use it is good and acceptable.

5.5.3.2 Composite Reliability

Composite Reliability (CR) is another coefficient used for measuring the internal consistency reliability of the constructs in a survey instrument. Unlike Cronbach α it does not assume equally weighted loadings in factor analysis (Hair et al., 2019). Composite reliability is the preferred measure of internal consistency in Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analysis and is generally computed using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Netemeyer, Sharma and Bearden, 2003). Although, generally the different measures of reliability are expected to give similar estimates for reliability (Hair et al., 2019). The calculation of CR is based on utilising the squared factor loadings and error variances. Mathematically, the formula for computing CR for a construct is

$$CR = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i)^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - \lambda_i^2)}$$

Where,

λ_i is the factor loading of the i^{th} item on the construct and

$(1 - \lambda_i^2)$ is the error variance

The values used for the calculation of CR are given in the table below. For a construct to be appropriate, the value for Composite reliability that is acceptable is generally higher than 0.70 although a value of 0.60 can also be considered acceptable (Hair et al., 2011). In this study all variables were found to have a value for CR that satisfies this criterion. The values are shown in Table 5.12.

Table 5.12 Reliability and Validity Coefficients for the Constructs

Construct		Cronbach's α (> 0.7)	AVE (> 0.5)	CR (> 0.7)
Personal Innovativeness	PI	0.841	0.655	0.849
Proactive Personality	PP	0.823	0.549	0.828
Perceived Ease of Use	PEOU	0.734	0.506	0.751
Perceived Usefulness	PU	0.871	0.641	0.876
Technology anxiety	TA	0.796	0.498	0.798
Bandwagon Effect	BE	0.928	0.811	0.928
Perceived Trust	PT	0.815	0.565	0.833
Legal Risk	LR	0.837	0.559	0.824
Privacy Risk	PR	0.924	0.808	0.926
Attitude	ATT	0.942	0.795	0.939
Intention to Adopt	IA	0.950	0.872	0.953

5.5.4 Validity

Validity ensures “how accurately the items in the instrument are able to measure what they are intended to measure” i.e., the scale is able to measure the intended constructs (Sekaran, 2003; Hair et al., 2019). It is crucial that the data collected encompasses the actual details of the survey research. Validity is different from reliability as it concerns with what is to be measured rather than how it should be measured (Hair et al., 2019). Usually, the content validity and construct validity are considered.

5.5.4.1 Content Validity

The content validity determines if the measures or the instrument appropriately includes the entire content or domain that it needs to cover concerning the variable. Greater the content validity, more the measurement items are able to correspond to the domain of the concept under investigation (Sekaran, 2003). It is assessed with the help of ratings provided by expert judges such as Professors and other groups since it is not just an empirical issue but also a theoretical concern and a practical aspect (Hair et al., 2019). For this research also, the measurement items representing the variables in the questionnaire were examined by the Lead supervisor and respondents of the pilot study.

5.5.4.2 Construct Validity

Construct Validity estimates how well the inferences drawn by using the measure relate to the theories or concept for which the tests are constructed (Sekaran, 2003). It is assessed using Convergent Validity and Discriminant Validity. Existence of Construct Validity reinforces the assumption that the views represented by the observations from the sample are an accurate reflection of the opinions of the population at large (Hair et al., 2019). These concepts were introduced by Campbell and Fiske (1959) for evaluating the validity. They explained that it is important to use both the tests for gauging validity of the new measures.

5.5.4.3 Convergent Validity

Convergent Validity (CV) is said to be confirmed when the two items that measure the same concept or construct are strongly correlated (Sekaran, 2003; Hair et al., 2019). Two approaches can be taken to ascertain convergent validity. The first one involves looking at the factor loadings while the second involves computing the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) coefficient and the Composite Reliability (Hair et al., 2019). Existence of convergent validity implies that the items of a construct converge towards the factor. In order for this to be true two conditions on the factor loadings are proposed by Hair et al. (2019). The factor loadings should be significant and should have a value above 0.5. For this study, as can be seen from the calculated factor loadings, all of them are statistically significant, with $p < 0.001$, and most are above 0.5 satisfying the requirements for Convergent Validity. The other approach to computing CV is via constraints on AVE and CR. The quantities used to compute AVE and CR are mentioned in Table 5.13 below. Here λ refers to the factor loadings, λ^2 is the square loadings, also known as communality, and $1 - \lambda^2$ is the error variance. Note that these factor loadings are computed after eliminating PI3 based on unidimensionality requirements.

Table 5.13 Factor Loadings, Communalities and Error Variances

Factors	Items	Factor Loadings (λ)	Communality (λ^2)	Error Variance ($1 - \lambda^2$)
Personal Innovativeness	PI1	0.924	0.854	0.146
	PI2	0.722	0.521	0.479
	PI4	0.768	0.590	0.410

Proactive Personality	PP1	0.653	0.426	0.574
	PP2	0.831	0.691	0.309
	PP3	0.747	0.558	0.442
	PP4	0.721	0.520	0.480
Perceived Ease of Use	PEOU1	0.591	0.349	0.651
	PEOU2	0.814	0.663	0.337
	PEOU3	0.711	0.506	0.494
Perceived Usefulness	PU1	0.820	0.672	0.328
	PU2	0.679	0.461	0.539
	PU3	0.920	0.846	0.154
	PU4	0.763	0.582	0.418
Technology anxiety	TA1	0.611	0.373	0.627
	TA2	0.746	0.557	0.443
	TA3	0.754	0.569	0.431
	TA4	0.702	0.493	0.507
Bandwagon Effect	BE1	0.888	0.789	0.211
	BE2	0.904	0.817	0.183
	BE3	0.910	0.828	0.172
Perceived Trust	PT1	0.819	0.671	0.329
	PT2	0.761	0.579	0.421
	PT3	0.880	0.774	0.226
	PT4	0.486	0.236	0.764

Legal Risk	LR1	0.627	0.393	0.607
	LR2	0.428	0.183	0.817
	LR3	0.921	0.848	0.152
	LR4	0.901	0.812	0.188
Privacy Risk	PR1	0.836	0.699	0.301
	PR2	0.894	0.799	0.201
	PR3	0.962	0.925	0.075
Attitude towards Using Cryptocurrencies	ATT1	0.966	0.933	0.067
	ATT2	0.950	0.903	0.098
	ATT3	0.872	0.760	0.240
	ATT4	0.764	0.584	0.416
Intention to Adopt	IA1	0.948	0.899	0.101
	IA2	0.980	0.960	0.040
	IA3	0.870	0.757	0.243

5.5.4.4 Average Variance Extracted

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is “the amount of variance encapsulated in items relative to the measurement error” (Netemeyer, Sharma and Bearden, 2003). It is the average of the variance that is extracted from the factor loadings of a factor and signals the convergence of the items (Hair et al., 2019). Mathematically speaking, the AVE for a particular construct is calculated as

$$AVE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2}{n}$$

Where,

λ_i is the factor loading of the i^{th} item on the construct and

n is the number of items loading on that construct

AVE for each of the construct is mentioned in the Table 5.12 along with CR and Cronbach's alpha. To ensure convergent validity, the value for AVE should be more than 0.50, while the value of composite reliability (CR) should be greater than 0.70 (Hair et al., 2011; Bagozzi and Yi, 1988). In this study nearly all variables were found to satisfy this requirement except the variable Technology anxiety for which AVE was 0.498. According to Fornell & Larcker (1981) an AVE value of less than 0.5 but greater than 0.4 can still be considered acceptable as long as the corresponding composite reliability is greater than 0.6. For the case of Technology anxiety, the CR was found to be 0.798, hence this construct is acceptable. Therefore, convergent validity was established for factors in this study.

5.5.4.5 Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity measures the degree to which two separate constructs are differentiable from each other (Hair et al., 2019). It means that for discriminant validity to hold, two theoretically similar concepts must be distinct and each factor should uniquely represent an idea. A consequence of this is that the constructs should be uncorrelated from each other. Furthermore, as discussed previously while looking at unidimensionality, if cross-loadings exist i.e., items of one construct load highly on another, then discriminant validity will not be established (Hair et al., 2019). As per Fornell and Larcker (1981) "the AVE of every variable should be greater than the square of the correlation between the variable and every other variable for discriminant validity to hold" (Hair et al., 2011). This is because one expects the variance in the items of a construct to be explained by it more than the variance the construct shares with another construct (Hair et al., 2019). The Table 5.14 displays the squared correlation matrix, without the diagonal elements, along with the maximum square correlation (max SC) and the AVE for each construct.

Table 5.14 Squared Correlation Matrix

	PI	PP	PEOU	PU	TA	BE	PT	LR	PR	ATT	IA
PI		0.206	0.028	0.111	0.017	0.088	0.073	0.000	0.005	0.138	0.146
PP	0.206		0.039	0.138	0.001	0.037	0.074	0.000	0.001	0.079	0.082
PEOU	0.028	0.039		0.186	0.017	0.074	0.157	0.038	0.018	0.110	0.089
PU	0.111	0.138	0.186		0.016	0.094	0.223	0.057	0.036	0.417	0.343
TA	0.017	0.001	0.017	0.016		0.027	0.017	0.183	0.173	0.057	0.080
BE	0.088	0.037	0.074	0.094	0.027		0.112	0.010	0.018	0.219	0.315
PT	0.073	0.074	0.157	0.223	0.017	0.112		0.019	0.115	0.239	0.171
LR	0.000	0.000	0.038	0.057	0.183	0.010	0.019		0.137	0.062	0.022
PR	0.005	0.001	0.018	0.036	0.173	0.018	0.115	0.137		0.091	0.093
ATT	0.138	0.079	0.110	0.417	0.057	0.219	0.239	0.062	0.091		0.632
IA	0.146	0.082	0.089	0.343	0.080	0.315	0.171	0.022	0.093	0.632	
Max SC	0.206	0.206	0.186	0.417	0.183	0.315	0.239	0.183	0.173	0.632	0.632
AVE(>sc)	0.655	0.549	0.506	0.641	0.498	0.811	0.565	0.559	0.808	0.795	0.872

As can be observed the AVE for each construct is greater than the corresponding maximum value of squared correlation thereby satisfying the Fornell and Larcker criteria mentioned above. Hence, discriminant validity was found to hold true for the constructs used in this study. Since all constructs were found to display Convergent as well as Discriminant Validity therefore, construct validity is also established in this study.

5.5.5 Assessment of Model Fit

Before proceeding to test the fit of the measurement model for the purpose of confirmatory factor analysis, how to assess the fit of models first needs to be explored. Unlike several other analysis techniques, the estimation of the fit of a model in structural equation modelling and CFA is not determined by a single quantity (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). Instead, there are various indices that together provide a summary indicating the goodness of fit of the model.

Goodness of fit signifies how well the model is able to describe the relations in the underlying population based on the sample data. For a model to be considered a good fit it should be able to explain the variances and covariances in the constructs that are measured (Hair et al., 2019). As mentioned earlier the model is used to estimate the covariance matrix among the constructs. This is then compared with the covariance matrix calculated from the data. The

differences between these two matrices are known as the residuals. In the ideal situation where the model exactly predicts the covariances in the data the residuals would be zero. This is not the case with real world data. The fit indices are the measures that mathematically represent how close the residuals are to zero (Hair et al., 2019). For models where the residuals are sufficiently close to zero i.e., models where the estimated covariance matrix is sufficiently close to the covariance matrix observed based on data are considered fit models.

The commonly used fit indices are categorised in three types, “absolute fit indices”, “incremental fit indices” and “parsimony fit indices”. The absolute fit indices stipulate a direct assessment of how well the model reflects the data, independent of reference to any other model. The incremental fit indices measure how good is the fit of the estimated model in comparison to the null model. Here, the null model is the model in which the covariances between the constructs are zero. Parsimony fit indices are used for comparing between different models based on their complexity. A simpler model or a better fitting model has a higher parsimony index (Hair et al., 2019).

5.5.5.1 Chi-Square (χ^2)

The standard measure for comparing the “observed covariance matrix” and the “estimated covariance matrix” is the chi-square (χ^2) statistic. The chi-square statistic is an example of an absolute fit index and is essential in computation of most of the other fit indices discussed here. The chi-square test is a type of test that checks the hypothesis which states that the “estimated covariance matrix and the observed covariance matrix are same” (Kline, 2015). Therefore, chi-square test is an example of the accept-support test where accepting the null hypothesis implies that the model is correct. This differs from the case with other tests generally utilized in multivariate analysis which are reject-support tests in which rejection of the null hypothesis is desired (Kline, 2015). Thus, for a model to be considered a good fit one desires the chi-square value to be small and the associated p-value to be larger than 0.05 (Hair et al., 2019). The chi-square statistic (χ^2) is calculated as follows

$$\chi^2 = (N - 1)f[(S - \Sigma)]$$

Where,

N is the sample size,

S is the covariance matrix of the sample data

Σ is the estimated covariance matrix based on the model and

f is the fit function that uses maximum likelihood estimation technique

As can be noticed from the formula the chi-square (χ^2) value is dependent on the sample size. A consequence of this is that for an increasing sample size, even if the distinction between the estimated and observed covariance remains fixed, the chi-square value increases. This is an undesirable property in a measure of goodness of fit. Another issue with simply using the bare chi-square value is that on increasing the number of measured variables the value of chi-square tends to increase (Hair et al., 2019). Hence, the chi-square value, or the associated p-value, by itself is not generally used to decide on the goodness of fit of the model. These problems lead to the development of other fit indices that account for the mentioned issues.

5.5.5.2 Normed Chi-Square (χ^2/df)

The “normed chi-square”, also called “relative chi-square”, is defined as “the chi-square (χ^2) value divided by the degrees of freedom of the theory (df)” (Hair et al., 2019). The normed chi-square is also an absolute fit index and it was developed with the aim to decrease the reliance of the chi-square value on the size of the sample (Kline, 2015). As per Hair et al. (2019) a normed chi-square (χ^2/df) value of less than 3 denotes a good fitting model till the sample size is not too large (not exceeding 750), while Schumacker and Lomax (2004) suggest that a normed chi-square value that is less than 5 is also acceptable.

The degree of freedom (df) used to define normed chi-square above, is a measure of the statistical information that is available (Hair et al., 2019). The (df) for a model is computed based on the difference between the known covariance information from the data and the number of free parameters in the model (Hair et al., 2019). The variance-covariance matrix for a model with q observed variable contains q different variances corresponding to each variable and $q(q - 1)/2$ different covariances corresponding to each pair of variables. Mathematically the degree of freedom (df) can be computed as,

$$df = \frac{q(q + 1)}{2} - k$$

Where df is the degree of freedom,

q is the number of observed variables in the model and

k is the number of parameters to be estimated

5.5.5.3 Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)

Root Mean Square of Approximation (RMSEA) is another absolute fit index that is developed for the purpose of tackling the issues with chi-square surrounding data with large sample size and models with large number of observables (Hair et al., 2019). This is done by incorporating these quantities in its calculations. Mathematically, the RMSEA can be calculated using the following formula (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003)

$$RMSEA = \sqrt{\max\left\{\frac{1}{(N-1)}\left(\frac{\chi^2}{df}\right), 0\right\}}$$

Where,

$\max\{, \}$ represents the maximum between the two quantities

N is the sample size

χ^2 is the chi-square statistic and

df is the degree of freedom

It is the most commonly used fit measure and is reported by most studies that use structural equation modelling and confirmatory factor analysis (Schreiber et al., 2006). The advantage of using RMSEA is that it not only accounts for the model fit over the sample data, it also better reflects the fitness of the model on the population. The value of RMSEA can vary from 0 to infinity but being a measure of the error, a lower RMSEA value is considered better for the fit of a model. Although recent research indicates that it is unwise to have a strict cut off for RMSEA, generally the acceptable value of RMSEA indicating a good fitting model is less than 0.08 or less than 0.05 (Hair et al., 2019; Browne and Cudeck, 1992). It should also be stated that a model with RMSEA above 1.0 should be considered a bad fit and mostly be rejected. Due to the way it is defined, RMSEA has the drawback that it tends to disfavour simpler models with fewer measured variables (Kline, 2015).

5.5.5.4 Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)

The goodness of fit index (GFI) was one of the first indices that were developed to overcome chi-square's limitation of sensitivity to sample size of the data. Although designed for this purpose, the GFI still has some dependence on the sample size due to its effect on the distribution of the sample (Hair et al., 2019). The GFI is an absolute fit index and it is designed to measure the amount of the covariances in the sample data relative to the estimated

covariances. In other words, it measures how much better the model fits in comparison to having no model at all (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). Mathematically GFI is calculated as

$$GFI = 1 - \frac{\chi^2}{\chi_0^2}$$

Where,

χ^2 is the chi-square of the model and

χ_0^2 is the chi-square of the null model with covariances zero

The value of the GFI lies between 0.0 and 1.0 with 1.0 being considered an ideal fit. Generally, a fit model was recommended to have the value of GFI above 0.90 (Hair et al., 2019). With the development of other fit indices in recent times the usage of GFI has reduced (Hair et al., 2019). It is not included in the suggested minimum set of indices (Kline, 2015) and it is not usually recommended (Schreiber et al., 2006).

5.5.5.5 Comparative Fit Index (CFI)

Comparative fit index is the most commonly reported fit metric alongside chi-square static (Hair et al., 2009). It is an incremental fit index and it measures how much the model of the research deviates from a close fit as compared to the null model (Kline, 1995). Similar to the other fit indices mentioned previously, CFI was developed to combat the issues with chi-square statistics. One of the advantages of CFI over other indices is that it is not very sensitive to the complexity of the model or the number of observables, in addition to being insensitive to the sample size (Hair et al., 2009). The value of CFI lies between 0.0 and 1.0 with 1.0 reflecting the best fittings. According to Kline (2015) the CFI is designed such that for models where $\chi^2 \leq df$ CFI has the value of 1.0. For cases where df is smaller the following formula from Hu and Bentler (1999) is applied.

$$CFI = 1 - \frac{\max[(\chi^2 - df), 0]}{\max[(\chi^2 - df), (\chi_0^2 - df_0)]}$$

Where,

$\max\{ , \}$ is the maximum out of the two values

χ^2 is the chi-square value for the research model

df is the degree of freedom of the research model

χ_0^2 is the chi-square value for the null model

df_0 is the degree of freedom of the null model

In real data CFI is not generally found to be 1.0. The cutoff value of CFI for an acceptable model fit is 0.9 although a value above 0.95 is would be preferred (Hair et al, 2009) (Hu and Bentler, 1999). A CFI of 0.9 implies that the fit of the model of the research is 90% better than the fit of the baseline null model.

5.5.5.6 Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)

Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), also called “non-normed fit Index” (NNFI) is another incremental fit index. TLI measures the relative fit and is computed from the difference between “normed chi-square value” of the research model and the “null model” (Hair et al., 2019). The TLI model accounts for the complexity of the model by considering the normed chi-square values (Kline, 2015) although TLI values tend to be lower for more complex models compared to less complex (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). The mathematical formula for TLI is given by Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller (2003)

$$TLI = \frac{\chi^2/df - \chi_0^2/df_0}{\chi^2/df - 1}$$

Where,

χ^2 refers to the chi-square value of the research model

df refers to the degrees of freedom of the research model

χ_0^2 refers to the chi-square value of the null model and

df_0 refers to the degrees of freedom of the null model

Unlike CFI, the value of TLI is not restricted to lie between 0 and 1. Being non-normed, the value of TLI can exceed 1 as well as be lower than 0. Generally, a value near 1.0 is considered a sign of a good fitting model and between two models, the model with higher value of TLI is considered a better fit (Hair et al., 2019). Models with TLI above 0.9 are generally considered acceptable although values over 0.95 are preferred (Hu and Bentler, 1999) (Hair et al., 2019).

The Tucker Lewis index and comparative fit index are related indices and their values are highly correlated. Due to this it is generally recommended that only one of these is presented (Kline, 2015).

5.5.5.7 Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)

The adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI) is a parsimonious fit index created to take into attention the complication of the research model (Hair et al., 2019). As the name suggests, the adjusted goodness of fit index was developed by modifying the goodness of fit index by dividing the chi-square values in the formula by their corresponding degrees of freedom (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). Doing this was meant to reduce the effect of models with more free paths that are to be estimated. Due to this, AGFI generally tends to have lower values for more complex models and higher values for simpler models. Moreover, AGFI generally have lower values compared to the GFI for that model (Hair et al., 2019). The formula for AGFI is

$$AGFI = 1 - \frac{\chi^2/df}{\chi_0^2/df_0}$$

Where,

χ^2 refers to the chi-square value of the research model

df refers to the degrees of freedom of the research model

χ_0^2 refers to the chi-square value of the null model and

df_0 refers to the degrees of freedom of the null model

The values of AGFI normally lie in the range of 0 and 1, although values outside this range are also possible in some extreme situations. Models with AGFI values above 0.9 are taken to be good fit and values above 0.85 are taken to be satisfactory (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). Due to its dependence on sample size and its inability to successfully account for model complexity, similar to GFI, the use of AGFI is no longer recommended (Hair et al., 2019).

Out of these various measures of model fitness discussed above Kline (2015) suggests that the minimum set of indices that are needed to be reported should include the chi-square value (χ^2) for the research model, the associated degrees of freedom (df) and p-values ($p > 0.05$), Root Mean Square Error Approximation ($RMSEA < 0.08$), and Comparative Fit Index ($CFI > 0.90$).

5.5.6 Analysis of CFA Model

After having examined the unidimensionality, reliability, and the validity of constructs and having reviewed the commonly used fit indices, an assessment of the goodness of fit of the CFA model is now presented. The CFA model consists of the measurement models for the 11 constructs used in this study, connected via covariances to each other. The constructs present in the model are Perceived Usefulness (PU), Attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT), Perceived Trust (PT), Bandwagon Effect (BE), Proactive Personality (PP), Intention to Adopt Cryptocurrencies (IA), Technology anxiety (TA), Legal Risk (LR), Privacy Risk (PR), Personal Innovativeness (PI), and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). The AMOS software program by IBM is used in association with SPSS for assessing the CFA model. The factor loadings for the constructs are mentioned in the Table 5.13 above. All the loadings were found to be statistically significant with p-value 0.001. A model summary is presented in the Table 5.15 followed by a discussion of the values. The Figure 5.9 is the CFA model created using AMOS. The paths from the constructs to the measured variables also have the corresponding factor loading indicated.

Table 5.15 Model Fit Summary for Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Fit Indices	Values	Suggested Value	Reference
Chi-square (χ^2)	1250.17	-	-
<i>df</i>	645	-	-
p-value	0.001	> 0.05	(Hair et al., 2019)
Normed Chi-square (χ^2/df)	1.94	< 3.00	(Hair et al., 2019)
RMSEA	0.07	< 0.08	(Hair et al., 2019)
CFI	0.90	> 0.95	(Kline, 2015)
TLI	0.89	> 0.95	(Kline, 2015)

Following the suggestion from Kline (2015) regarding the expected set of fit indices mentioned previously, the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) model is assessed on the basis of “chi-square” (χ^2), “degrees of freedom” (*df*) and p-value, “normed chi-square”, RMSEA, CFI, and TLI. It is observed that the chi-square statistic for the model is 1250.17 and the degrees of freedom is 645. The p-value associated to the chi-square is found to be 0.001. This

would imply the rejection of null hypothesis, indicating a bad model fit. As discussed earlier, the p-value is extremely sensitive to the sample size and so for a study like this with sample size over 200, $p < 0.05$ does not lead to any issue (Hair et al., 2019). The normed chi-square value is found to be 1.94 which is considerably less than the desired limit of 5 proposed according to Schumacker and Lomax (2004) as well as the more constraining limit of 3 according to Hair et al. (2019). Hence, this indicates a good model fit. Further, the root mean square error approximation (RMSEA) value is suggested to lie below 0.08 although a value smaller than 0.05 is preferred in modern times (Hair et al., 2019; Kline, 2015). The RMSEA value for the CFA model is 0.07 which is less than 0.08 but greater than 0.05, implying a marginal fit of the model. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is the most commonly mentioned fit index and according to Hair et al. (2009) while a value above 0.90 was considered adequate for a good fit in the 1990s (Hu and Bentler, 1999), modern recommended standard value for CFI should be above 0.95 to indicate a good fitting model. For the CFA model CFI has a value of 0.90 which indicates marginal fit rather than a good fit. Similarly, the value of TLI is now recommended to be above 0.95 for a good fit. For the CFA model TLI has a value of 0.89 which is even slightly below the 0.9 threshold. The most probable reason for the lack of a good fit is discussed later in section 5.6.1.1. Taking into consideration the results from all the fit indices it can be concluded that CFA model shows an acceptable marginal fit.

Figure 5.9 Confirmatory Factor Analysis Model

5.6 Structural Equation Model

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is a technique that is used in determining multiple relationships among the variables simultaneously in a model along with its validation. SEM can be perceived as a combination of “multiple linear regression” and “factor analysis” at the same time. This technique helps in statistically discussing even the complex models (Dash and Paul, 2021; Haenlein and Kaplan, 2004). The statistical method of SEM intends to examine the relationships among the endogenous and exogenous variables. The endogenous variable refers to the outcome constructs whose variance are explained by the predictor constructs, called the exogenous constructs. The exogenous constructs are determined by variables present outside the model (Hair et al., 2019). Structural equation modelling presents a structure of interrelationships put across through the use of equations like the multiple regression equations.

The equations represent all kinds of relationships between the independent variables and dependent variables that are part of analysis (Hair et al., 2019). The two types of models addressed by SEM are measurement model and path analysis. The measurement of the unobserved variables does not take place directly. First, many observed variables are evaluated and then unobserved variables are obtained from those observed indicators (Hayes, Montoya and Rockwood, 2017). The method of CFA discussed previously is used for assessing the measurement model. Path Analysis is conducted through analysing multiple regression equations simultaneously. Here, the structural relationships are established among the constructs using the measured variables, hence these are also called the structural model (Hancock and Mueller, 2018; Hair, Babin and Krey, 2017; Dash and Paul, 2021).

The question that is answered by using the technique of SEM comprises of a comparative analysis between the sample covariance matrix i.e., produced using the data and the estimated covariance matrix provided as a function of the model parameter estimations. When the parameter estimates produced by the estimated covariance matrix are similar to the sample covariance matrix, in that case the model is accepted and considered reasonably good (Ullman and Bentler, 2012). The model fit is tested based on a comprehensive evaluation of various fit indices such as chi square test, GFI, CFI, TLI, RMSEA, etc. Furthermore, there are two methods of applying SEM, one of them is covariance-based method and the other one is

partial least squares technique of SEM (Hair et al., 2011). Covariance based SEM, often called CB-SEM or just SEM, uses covariance statistics to maximize the fit between the observed and estimated covariance matrices, while the other method called PLS-SEM uses partial least squares to enhance the model fit (Dash and Paul, 2021). In case of PLS-SEM, the primary objective is similar to CB-SEM which is maximising the explained variance in the constructs while at the same time estimating the quality of the data based on the measurement model (Hair, Babin and Krey, 2017). CB-SEM is the most commonly used form of SEM and is used for confirmatory studies (Hair et al., 2011). The present research also uses the CB-SEM approach. The ability of SEM of assessing the latent variables at the level of observation i.e., the measurement model and testing the relationships between the latent variables as observed in the theories i.e., the structural model is much appreciated by the researchers (Bollen, 2010). Consequently, structural equation modelling has been used widely in the research in marketing and consumer behaviour (Martínez-López, Gázquez-Abad and Sousa, 2013; Baumgartner and Homburg, 1996), allowing the researchers to test their theories. A number of software packages are used for conducting SEM like LISREL and AMOS (Hair et al., 2019). In this research, AMOS has been used for applying the technique of CB-SEM and interpreting the results.

5.6.1 Analysis of the Structural Model

For understanding the consumer's intention to adopt cryptocurrencies, extensive literature review was conducted. It was inferred that the theories of technology adoption, theories of consumer psychology, and risk and trust theories would provide the correct framework to tackle this problem. These theories and constructs are reviewed in section 2.3 of Chapter 2. From these theories relevant constructs were identified and based on the literature relevant hypotheses were developed in section Chapter 3 indicating the expected relations between the constructs of the research. From these hypotheses a model was proposed and SEM was identified as the appropriate statistical technique to test these hypotheses. In the previous section confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to confirm that the variables that were measured using the survey questionnaire correctly represented the corresponding constructs. Here, structural equation modelling is deployed for testing of hypotheses, finding the magnitude of the relationships and assessing the fitness of the model.

The proposed model comprises of the following types of variables:

Observed, endogenous variables: IA, ATT, PU, PEOU

Observed, exogenous variables: BE, PP, PI, LR, PT

Summated scales composed from the corresponding measured items are used to represent these constructs. The proposed model is shown in Figure 5.10. Here, the variables in yellow signify the constructs of the theory of technology acceptance model (TAM), the constructs in pink are those based on the risk and trust theory, the construct in green is the social factor while the blue constructs represent psychological traits. The hypotheses corresponding to the relations between the constructs are also mentioned. The + or – sign along with the label of the hypotheses represent whether the relation is positive or negative. The exogenous variables were allowed to covariate with each other although this is not shown in the diagram.

Figure 5.10 Proposed Structural Model of the Study

5.6.1.1 Fitness of the proposed model

A model fit summary for the proposed model is presented below along with a discussion of the observed value.

Table 5.16 Model Fit Summary for Structural Model

Fit Indices	Values	Suggested Value	Reference
Chi-square (χ^2)	21.820	-	-
<i>df</i>	9	-	-
p-value	0.009	> 0.05	(Hair et al., 2019)
Normed Chi-square (χ^2/df)	2.42	< 3.00	(Hair et al., 2019)
RMSEA	0.08	< 0.08	(Hair et al., 2019)
CFI	0.98	> 0.95	(Kline, 2015)
TLI	0.89	> 0.95	(Kline, 2015)
GFI	0.98	> 0.95	(Kline, 2015)

The model fitness is evaluated based on the fit indices “chi-square” (χ^2), “degrees of freedom” (*df*) and “p-value”, “normed chi-square”, RMSEA, CFI, TLI and GFI. As per Ullman (2001) and Schumacker and Lomax (2004), the value for “normed chi-square” which is (χ^2/df) should be less than 5, while Hair et al. (2019) suggests a value less than 3. In this model, the value is 2.42, hence it can be said that the value is under the desired limit. Regarding the p-value, the results are said to show a significant model fit if the p-value is more than 0.05 (Hair et al., 2019). This is because for SEM, the researcher makes an effort to accept the null hypothesis since it signifies a good fit of the model and denotes that there is minimum difference between the estimated and observed matrices. For the proposed model, the p-value is 0.009 which is not more than 0.05 and hence it might raise questions regarding the fitness of the model. Although as mentioned previously, in case of larger sample sizes and large number of constructs, as in the present situation, the test for p-value becomes less useful (Hair et al., 2019). Hence, based on the normed chi-square it can still be established that the model has a good fit.

As discussed previously, the modern recommended values for the goodness of fit indices like CFI, TLI, and GFI should be close to 1 and preferably above 0.95 to represent good fit of the model (Hair et al., 2009; Hu and Bentler, 1999; Schreiber et al., 2006). For this model, the values of CFI and GFI are both above 0.95 but the value for TLI is not above 0.90 but is very close to it. This indicates a good fit from the perspective of CFI and GFI and marginal fit from TLI’s perspective. For RMSEA, it is suggested that the value should lie between 0.03 to 0.08

(Hair et al., 2019), although a value below 0.05 is preferred (Kline, 2015). With regards to this model the value for RMSEA is 0.08 implying that the model shows a very marginal fit. Taking a comprehensive look at all the values it can be concluded that the model shows a marginal fit.

This is primarily due to the fact that many hypotheses in the proposed model were rejected. As will be discussed later, all the hypotheses associated with the constructs Technology Anxiety and Privacy Risk were rejected. Inclusion of the items of these constructs in the CFA and SEM model naturally brings down the overall fitness of these models and thereby leads to values indicating marginal fit instead of good fit. If the model fitness was evaluated for the model without the rejected hypotheses, both the CFA and the SEM model would likely indicate good fit. This is because without the rejected constructs the estimated covariance matrix from the models should more closely resemble the observed covariance matrix. This would imply that the residuals would be smaller, so the chi-square value would also be smaller and consequently the fit indices would have a better value, leading to a good model fit. Now since the fit of the model is established, conclusions can be drawn based on the SEM results.

5.6.1.2 Squared Multiple Correlations (R^2)

The squared multiple correlation for a variable refers to “the fraction of the variable’s variance explained by all the other factors that are claimed to be its cause”. This is similar to the coefficient of determination in multilinear regression with the factor being treated as the outcome variable and all its predictors treated as independent variables (Kline, 2015). Since R^2 is the fraction of the explained variance w.r.t the total variance of the construct, hence $1 - R^2$ represents the unexplained variance. In the table below, the squared multiple correlation for the endogenous variables is listed.

Table 5.17 Squared Multiple Correlations (R^2)

Constructs	Squared Multiple correlations (R^2)
IA	0.674
ATT	0.545
PU	0.383
PEOU	0.191

As can be observed a significant fraction of the variance of attitude towards using cryptocurrency and the intention to adopt cryptocurrencies is successfully explained by the research model. The model explains more than 67% of the variance in the intention to adopt cryptocurrencies. This reflects a substantial improvement over an unmodified technology acceptance model (TAM) since as per Venkatesh and Bala (2008) the technology acceptance model has been generally found to explain approximately 40% of the variance in consumer intentions to use an information technology system.

5.6.1.3 Testing of Hypothesis

The figure below represents the research model after hypothesis testing. The solid green lines represent the hypotheses that are accepted based on their statistical significance, while the red dotted lines represent the hypotheses that are rejected. As stated previously, it can be observed that all hypotheses involving the constructs Technology anxiety and Privacy Risk were rejected. In the figure, the numbers on the path are the standardised path coefficients while the numbers in brackets near the endogenous variables are the squared multiple covariance which represents the explained variance.

Figure 5.11 Hypothesis Testing of the Research Model

The Table 5.18 below shows the statistical significance and the regression estimates for the hypotheses of the theory. Rows highlighted in green represent hypotheses that were established to be statistically significant with $p < 0.05$ and were thus accepted, while the rows in red represent the hypotheses that were rejected for not being statistically significant.

Table 5.18 Hypothesis Testing and Results

Hypothesis	Relations between Constructs			Regression weights	S.E.	Standardised Regression Weights	C.R.	p-value	Results
H1	ATT	→	IA	0.55	0.05	0.61	10.80	***	Accept
H2	PU	→	ATT	0.42	0.06	0.44	7.30	***	Accept
H3	PU	→	IA	0.11	0.04	0.13	2.43	0.015	Accept
H4	PEOU	→	ATT	-0.05	0.07	-0.04	-0.63	0.527	Reject
H5	PEOU	→	PU	0.33	0.09	0.24	3.81	***	Accept
H6	PT	→	ATT	0.15	0.07	0.14	2.23	0.026	Accept
H7	PT	→	PU	0.31	0.08	0.27	3.99	***	Accept
H8	PT	→	PEOU	0.30	0.06	0.36	5.02	***	Accept
H9	LR	→	PU	-0.17	0.06	-0.17	-2.63	0.009	Accept
H10	LR	→	PEOU	-0.11	0.05	-0.15	-2.11	0.035	Accept
H11	LR	→	ATT	-0.11	0.05	-0.12	-2.04	0.041	Accept
H12	PR	→	PU	-0.02	0.07	-0.02	-0.31	0.761	Reject
H13	PR	→	PEOU	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.79	0.429	Reject
H14	PR	→	ATT	-0.09	0.06	-0.08	-1.44	0.151	Reject
H15	PI	→	PU	0.22	0.10	0.14	2.16	0.031	Accept
H16	PI	→	PEOU	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.42	0.677	Reject
H17	PI	→	ATT	0.17	0.09	0.11	2.03	0.043	Accept
H18	PP	→	PU	0.27	0.09	0.20	3.04	0.002	Accept
H19	PP	→	PEOU	0.08	0.07	0.08	1.15	0.252	Reject
H20	PP	→	ATT	-0.01	0.08	-0.01	-0.17	0.864	Reject
H21	BE	→	ATT	0.32	0.06	0.27	4.98	***	Accept
H22	BE	→	IA	0.27	0.05	0.25	5.51	***	Accept
H23	TA	→	PU	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.66	0.512	Reject

H24	TA	→	PEOU	-0.03	0.05	-0.04	-0.50	0.619	Reject
H25	TA	→	ATT	-0.03	0.05	-0.03	-0.53	0.593	Reject

*** represents $p < 0.001$

S.E. is the standard error

C.R. (t-value) is the critical ratio between regression weights and S.E.

There are 11 constructs in the study including intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies (IA), attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT), perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU), perceived trust (PT), privacy risk (PR), legal risk (LR), personal innovativeness (PI), proactive personality (PP), bandwagon effect (BE), and technology anxiety (TA). For testing of the relationships among the variables based on the hypothesis framed in chapter 2, their significance according to their corresponding p-values and standardised regression weights is tested. The p-value should be less than 0.05 i.e., ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) in order to accept the hypothesis being tested whereas in case where p-value is more than 0.05 i.e., ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$) the hypothesis will be rejected (Hair et al., 2010). From the table above it can be observed that there are certain relationships that are not found to be significant, which include the relationships between perceived ease of use (PEOU) and attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT) representing H4, personal innovativeness (PI) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) representing H16, proactive personality (PP) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) representing H19, proactive personality (PP) and attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT) representing H20. Since the p-value corresponding to H4, H16, H19 and H20 is more than 0.05, it can be said that these hypotheses are rejected. Furthermore, it must be noted that there are certain factors that are found insignificant which are privacy risk (PR) and technology anxiety (TA). This is because privacy risk does not show a significant relationship with perceived usefulness (PU) representing H12, or with perceived ease of use (PEOU) representing H13, and even with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT) representing H14. As the p-value corresponding to H12, H13 and H14 is more than 0.05, these hypotheses are rejected. Also, technology anxiety does not show a statistically significant relationship with perceived usefulness (PU) representing H23, or with perceived ease of use (PEOU) representing H24, and even with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies (ATT) representing H25. As the p-value corresponding to H23, H24 and H25 is more than 0.05, these hypotheses are also rejected. All other relationships among the other constructs show significant p-value i.e., ($p < 0.05$), hence all the other hypotheses are accepted.

Furthermore, on the basis of the standardised regression weights or coefficients the significant hypotheses are analysed. Standardised regression coefficients denoted by Beta (β) provide with “comparison between the coefficients as to their relative explanatory power of the dependent variable” (Hair et al., 2019). On the basis of the standardised regression weights, it was observed that attitude towards using cryptocurrencies was one of the strongest predictors of intentions to adopt them having $\beta = 0.61$ and p-value less than 0.001. This implies that there is a statistically significant and positive relationship between attitude towards using cryptocurrencies and intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies and therefore (H1) is accepted. This strong relationship is backed by many other studies (Kulviwat et al., 2007; Hussein, 2017; Weng et al., 2018). The results show that perceived usefulness has a strong relationship with the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, a major relationship in the model, with a strong regression weight i.e., $\beta = 0.44$ and a p-value less than 0.001 and therefore H2 is accepted. This is an important relationship of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989). Another relationship represented by TAM in the model of this study which is between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use shows a significant positive relationship having $\beta = 0.24$ and p-value less than 0.001 and therefore H5 is accepted. Therefore, it can be said that all the relations as represented by TAM show a significant relationship in the model except for the relation between perceived ease of use and attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, which is a weak relationship in the TAM itself (Davis, 1989). Furthermore, many studies utilizing TAM have found this relation to be insignificant in their models (Roussou, Stiakakis and Sifaleras, 2019; Yang and Yoo, 2004). Moreover, perceived usefulness is indicated to have a significant relationship with intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies having $\beta = 0.12$ and p-value less than 0.05 leading to acceptance of H6. Thus, it can be said that perceived usefulness has a direct as well as indirect effect on intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies. The indirect effect is partially mediated through the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies.

The relationship between perceived trust has been exhibited to have an impactful and positive relationship with perceived usefulness having $\beta = 0.26$ and p-value less than 0.001. Perceived trust also has a positive and a stronger relationship with perceived ease of use with $\beta = 0.36$ and p-value less than 0.001. Furthermore, perceived trust has a significant relationship with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies with $\beta = 0.14$ and p-value .026 ($p <$

0.05). Hence all the hypotheses corresponding to perceived trust i.e., H6, H7 and H8 are accepted. The construct of perceived trust was also observed to be a crucial factor in several studies (Belanche, Casaló and Flavián, 2012; Patil et al., 2020). The relationship between legal risk and perceived usefulness showed a significant influence, reflecting that H9 has a p-value less than 0.01 and $\beta = -0.17$, leading to acceptance of H9. Likewise, the results express that legal risk has a negative influence on perceived ease of use denoting H10 with $\beta = -0.15$ and p-value < 0.05 . Further, legal risk also shows a negative relationship with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies indicating H11, with $\beta = -0.12$ and p-value less than 0.05. Consequently, both H10 and H11 are accepted. Similarly, the hypothesis corresponding to bandwagon effect implying H21 and H22, both were accepted since they exhibited great meaningful regression weights, $\beta = 0.27$ and $\beta = 0.25$ respectively and importantly had p-values less than 0.001. This implies that the bandwagon effect showed a strong and positive effect on both the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies and the intentions to adopt them.

The construct of personal innovativeness was hypothesized to positively have an impact on perceived usefulness denoting H15, perceived ease of use representing H16 and attitude towards using cryptocurrencies signifying H17. Out of these, personal innovativeness was found to have an effect on perceived usefulness with $\beta = 0.14$ and p-value less than 0.05 as well as it showed a relationship with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies with $\beta = 0.11$ and p-value less than 0.05. Hence, H15 and H17 were accepted. Though H16 was rejected since the corresponding p-value was greater than 0.05. These results are similar to some other studies regarding adoption of technology (Jackson, Yi and Park, 2013; Yi et al., 2006). Moreover, as it was previously seen that perceived usefulness has a relationship with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, it would imply that personal innovativeness has both direct and indirect effect on attitude towards using cryptocurrencies. The indirect effect is partially mediated through the construct of perceived usefulness. Reflecting on the hypothesis showing a relationship between proactive personality and perceived usefulness denoted by H18 was accepted because it presented a p-value less than 0.01 and $\beta = 0.20$. This displays that proactive personality has a positive impact on perceived usefulness. Although, the other two hypotheses i.e., H19 and H20 were rejected showing no relationship between proactive personality and attitude toward using cryptocurrencies as well as between proactive personality and perceived ease of use. Since it was earlier noticed that perceived usefulness

has a relationship with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies and now it is seen that proactive personality has a positive impact on perceived usefulness and no direct influence on attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, it can be inferred that the effect of proactive personality on attitude towards using cryptocurrencies is fully mediated through perceived usefulness.

On the basis of above analysis, the model represents an acceptable fit and therefore hypotheses testing was conducted regarding the relations among the constructs. It was found that out of 25 hypotheses, 10 hypotheses were rejected and the remaining 15 were accepted based on the p-value criteria. Most of the hypotheses that were rejected were related to two constructs which are privacy risk and technology anxiety. The key findings based on these results are discussed in the next chapter along with their logical reasonings.

Chapter 6 Discussion and Findings

6.1 Overview of the chapter

Based on the previous section that dealt with the data analysis, this chapter details the findings emanating from studying consumer preferences and attitudes towards the adoption of cryptocurrencies. These findings are centred on the results based on the analytics derived above with cross-references made to relevant corroborative literature in order to achieve triangulation. The results obtained after testing of hypotheses in the previous chapter are discussed here in detail along with their corresponding reasons.

6.2 Discussion of the Results

It has been established that the adoption of cryptocurrencies is increasing consistently and there are numerous factors that have influenced the acceptance of this innovative financial product. In this research, a new model was developed which was an extension of the technology acceptance model that deals with perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude towards adoption of cryptocurrencies and intentions towards adoption of cryptocurrencies. In developing the new model with the aim of making this research holistic, additional constructs such as perceived trust, legal risk, privacy risk, proactive personality, personal innovativeness, bandwagon effect and technology anxiety were also added to the existing TAM model.

This novel research model was developed based on the testing of 25 hypotheses for which the data were collected using the questionnaire. The collected dataset was then analysed and the resulting outputs reported in the previous chapter. It was determined that the constructs used in the study satisfied the criteria for validity and reliability. The new model developed explains 67% of the variance in the intention to adopt cryptocurrencies. Additionally, this new model indicates that the explanatory power of the model is relatively high. Consequently, the results suggested that attitude towards using the cryptocurrencies is the strongest predictor of intentions to adopt them.

In accordance with the results reported in the previous chapter, the new model explained 53% of variance in the attitude towards adoption of cryptocurrencies. Here, it was observed that privacy risk and technology anxiety were not significant factors, while perceived usefulness, perceived trust, legal risk, personal innovativeness had an impact on the attitude towards adoption of cryptocurrencies. In addition, it was also noted that bandwagon effect had a direct significant impact both on intention to adopt and attitude towards their adoption. It is interesting to note that some factors like proactive personality only had an impact on the perceived usefulness of the cryptocurrencies. In the discussions that follow in this section, these significant and non-significant relations are reviewed in-depth and their implications within the context of cryptocurrencies are thoroughly discussed.

It must be noted that most of the respondents to the survey had experience of using cryptocurrencies. The respondents that had no prior cryptocurrency usage experience were well informed about them. Among the participants, it was noticed that nearly half of them belonged to the age group of 21-30, showing that most of the participants were young investors, users, or people who were interested in cryptocurrencies. Regarding the gender of the respondents, it was identified that the majority of the participants that had experience or knowledge of cryptocurrencies were males, while only a quarter of them were females. Furthermore, most of the respondents to the survey held an education up to master's level which indicates that consumers showing awareness or having prior experience about cryptocurrencies possessed higher level of education. It was also observed that there was quite a bit of variation concerning the amount invested in cryptocurrencies. Though a large proportion of cryptocurrency users mentioned that they invested up to USD 500 in cryptocurrencies, there were some who had invested up to USD 2,000 and some who even stated that they had invested more than USD 10,000. For the purposes of using cryptocurrencies, long term trading and in the broader sense investment in cryptocurrencies was mostly preferred by the users rather than using them as a medium of exchange or for any other purpose such as for savings.

6.2.1 Key Findings of the Study

1. The current study established that attitude has a very strong impact on intention to adopt. What this means is that the intention to adopt cryptocurrencies very strongly depends on attitude towards their usage. This finding is in accordance with other studies in various

fields such as consumer adoption of technology (Kulviwat et al., 2007), e-Learning (Hussein, 2017), adoption of multimedia (Weng et al., 2018), and the acceptance of mobile learning technology (Andoh, 2018). The considerable effect of attitude on intention to adopt is also evident in literature associated with cryptocurrencies (Agustina, 2019; Alaklabi and Kang, 2021; Schaupp and Festa, 2018).

To elaborate on the above initial finding, the study has established that attitude correlates with the perceptions of people, in which, fundamentally, the significant impact of attitude on intention to adopt cryptocurrencies would denote that when individuals believe that adopting cryptocurrencies would be favourable to them, they will have a positive attitude towards their adoption and hence they will have stronger intentions towards their adoption. In effect, if people strongly like the idea of using cryptocurrencies and feel that using them is wise, evidently, they will naturally tend to have a more favourable opinion about them and therefore will most likely patronize them or plan to use them in the future. Hence, it is essential from marketing a viewpoint that the companies involved in the cryptocurrency space that desire to increase their adoption must lay focus on influencing the attitude of consumers towards cryptocurrencies. It is important to highlight that there are numerous factors that influence the consumer attitude towards using cryptocurrencies which are discussed in-depth further.

2. Another important finding centred on the fact that the factor that has the strongest explanatory power on attitude towards usage of cryptocurrencies is perceived usefulness. The interrelationship between attitude and perceived usefulness was well established in the technology acceptance model (TAM) by Davis (1989) and was subsequently observed in most of TAM applications and extensions (Yang and Yoo, 2004; Porter and Donthu, 2006). The perceived usefulness of cryptocurrencies follows from the fact that they have several tangible benefits. These benefits include their feature of immutability (Zheng et al., 2017) and their applications such as smart contracts, coloured coins, crypto assets and their ability to maintain data integrity.

Following from the above finding, conversely, there are certain disadvantages associated with cryptocurrencies as well such as the instability in their prices compared to other fiat currencies, and their contribution to wastage of resources and the consequent negative effects on the environment (Berentsen and Schar, 2018). Significant impact of perceived

usefulness on attitude implies that when the consumers realize the benefits of cryptocurrencies and believe that using cryptocurrencies would increase their productivity, efficiency, profitability and overall performance, they will tend to develop a positive attitude towards their usage. This relationship is also determined to be crucial in various studies conducted on cryptocurrencies (Grover et al., 2019; Folkinshteyn and Lennon, 2016; Sanchez, Saura and Ayestaran, 2021). Moreover, perceived usefulness directly has an effect on intentions to adopt. Thus, the construct of perceived usefulness becomes all the more important in the adoption of cryptocurrencies.

3. A third corroborative finding deals with the bandwagon effect which is a rather novel construct in the technology adoption context and has been introduced in this study. It has not been explicitly studied as an adoption factor while investigating consumer behaviour towards cryptocurrencies in particular. It is found to have a significant effect on an individual's attitude towards usage of cryptocurrencies as well as a direct impact on intentions to adopt them. Based on the findings of this study it can be claimed that people who invest in cryptocurrencies follow the bandwagon which means that individuals are putting their resources into cryptocurrencies simply because others are also investing in them. This kind of behaviour has been observed in various domains such as fashion, luxury, politics, economics etc and it can now be established that it is very much evident in the use of cryptocurrencies as well (Lo and Weng, 2012; Xu et al., 2012; Sabir et al., 2020).

The reason for the above finding could be due to various factors such as investors belonging to the younger age group (Yelowitz and Wilson, 2015; Naeem, Mbarki and Shahzad, 2021) who generally tend to follow the herd behaviour. Likewise, it may likely be because these classes of young patrons lack the proper knowledge and awareness (Calderón, 2018) and are just ready to invest in cryptocurrencies only because they want to remain associated with the groups that they are part of. Essentially, social media and discussion platforms in today's era play a critical role in capturing the attention of people and creating hype for the financial products like cryptocurrencies (Calderón, 2018). The results of this research assure that bandwagon effect must be considered as an important adoption factor for cryptocurrencies. It signifies that when substantial number of individuals in a group approve of or recognize the usage of cryptocurrencies, individuals associated or related to those groups will certainly like

the idea of using cryptocurrencies as well as possibly have the intentions to use them in present or in the near future.

4. Additionally, another construct that showed statistically significant results was perceived trust on perceived usefulness, attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, and perceived ease of use. This finding supported the observation that perceived trust is an extremely crucial factor in large number of studies where adoption of new and innovative technologies is considered, such as mobile payment systems (Patil et al., 2020), online shopping (Faqih, 2016), banking and social media (Hansen, Saridakis and Benson, 2018), and the use of social media platforms (Hansen, Saridakis and Benson, 2018). Trust is also manifested in studies concerning with cryptocurrencies (Marella et al., 2020) since people need to feel that the financial transactions made by them are processed fairly and safely as there are no financial institutions like banks involved to guarantee trust to the users (Nelms et al., 2017). It can therefore be assumed that perceived trust that has a positive influence on the attitude towards their usage is due to the reason that cryptocurrency transactions are not simple to be forged since the recording of transactions takes place on a distributed ledger system using cryptographic methods (Cordero, Sánchez and Cortés, 2020). This provides transparency in transactions without any involvement of intermediaries (Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018).

The implication of this finding is that, if the system is credible and trustworthy, it will lead to having a positive attitude towards their usage. Regarding the impact of perceived trust on perceived usefulness, it is due to the reason that in an online interface where consumers do not have face-to-face transactions as in the case of cryptocurrencies, consumers are able to perceive the useability of such systems if they have trust in those technologies. To a greater extent, this can be accurate in case of perceived ease of use since it is observed that when people do not have enough trust in technologies like cryptocurrencies regarding their technical and financial aspects, people will likely assume that the technology is complex and difficult to use, implement and control (Albayati, Kim and Rho, 2020). The results reveal that perceived trust is thus a critical factor while studying the adoption of cryptocurrencies. An implication of this is that when consumers perceive those transactions that use cryptocurrencies are trustworthy, secure and guarantee privacy, these same customers will

instinctively suppose that using cryptocurrencies is a wise idea; consequently, this will increase their efficiency and interaction with these platforms.

5. Another obvious finding and construct discovered from the analysis is the perceived ease of use which had a significant explanatory power on perceived usefulness. This relationship is a validation of the well-established relationship of the technology acceptance model (Davis, 1989) which had been further witnessed in many other related studies (Ma, Gam and Banning, 2017; Amin, Rezaei and Abolghasemi, 2014; Nadeem et al., 2021; Alqaryouti et al., 2020; Sohaib et al., 2020). The strong impact of perceived ease of use on perceived usefulness of cryptocurrencies denotes that if the transactions using cryptocurrencies are simple to make while not requiring a humongous amount of mental effort, they will naturally become more useful for the users. It will eventually increase the productivity of the consumers and bring efficiency in their work. It has been observed that there are issues with the basic serviceability like accessibility of the blockchain facilities (Glomann, Schmid and Kitajewa, 2019) and the fact that cryptocurrency exchanges are based on those blockchain services, the issues lead to poor serviceability and hence impede their usefulness (Jang et al., 2020).

6. Next, the results reveal that legal risk is also a significant factor that has influence on the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, their perceived usefulness, and even their perceived ease of use. The same is observed in the literature review that risk appears to be an important factor when evaluating the adoption of technologies (Im, Kim and Han, 2008; Martins, Oliveira and Popovič, 2014). Furthermore, the results obtained in this study are consistent with the other research conducted in the context of cryptocurrencies (Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018; Gazali, Ismail and Amboala, 2018). This is due to the reason that cryptocurrencies are still a novel financial product for many users and the transactions take place through an unregulated online system. The results confirmed that particular legal risk poses a major impediment in the adoption of cryptocurrencies since cryptocurrencies are not controlled by any form of financial intermediary or authority like the central Federal Reserve banks or financial institutions.

There are several possible explanations for this result. Since cryptocurrencies are just available virtually and cannot be seen in any kind of physical form, it raises the question regarding the legal rights related to the holding of cryptocurrencies (Low and Teo, 2018). Law

scholars working in the area of cryptocurrencies have not yet arrived at an agreement in regards to the status and nature of such virtual currencies (Cvetkova, 2018). Moreover, the laws related to cryptocurrencies are not efficiently defined. Besides, laws regarding cryptocurrencies are different for different nations with some countries approving the use of cryptocurrencies while other nations put bans on the adoption and usage of cryptocurrencies (Shovkhalov and Idrisov, 2021; Novikov, 2018; Cvetkova, 2018). To overcome the problem of control, some of the countries have even launched their own cryptocurrencies that would be regularised by the central banking institutions popularly referred to as the Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDC) (Shovkhalov and Idrisov, 2021).

Following the above background to the finding, the study results show a negative influence of legal risk on the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. This denotes that if individuals entertain legal uncertainties in relation to the use and adoption of cryptocurrencies, such individuals will most likely believe that investing or purchasing cryptocurrencies will not be a wise idea. It will also not be easy to operate the use of cryptocurrencies on a freelance scale if there are legal issues pertaining to cryptocurrencies. Available and enforceable legal regimes governing cryptocurrencies will hamper customer perceptions regarding their usability even if there are numerous advantages allied to the use of cryptocurrencies. These effects suggest that legal risk factors must be considered while studying the adoption of cryptocurrencies.

7. There were two psychological factors that were also studied and their importance in cryptocurrency adoption were measured. One such psychological factor pertains to personal innovativeness that proved as a meaningful factor in the adoption and usage of cryptocurrencies. Personal innovativeness had an influence on attitude towards using the cryptocurrencies and their perceived usefulness. This result matches with many studies conducted in technology adoption (Yi, Fiedler and Park, 2006; Yi et al., 2006; Jackson, Yi and Park, 2013). This is due to the reason that the individuals who are intuitively innovative tend to have an optimistic attitude and mindset towards the new technologies and so are able to relate to their usefulness. This can be true in case of cryptocurrencies since they are relatively a new technology, and the curiosity and confidence towards them helps in amplifying the perceptions regarding their benefits (Lu, Yao and Yu, 2005).

This result further supports the idea that innovative users will have a positive attitude and will try to use the cryptocurrencies in their daily routines (Abbasi et al., 2021). Since it was also noticed that younger people are more interested in the adoption of cryptocurrencies (Yelowitz and Wilson, 2015) and their inquisitiveness levels to explore new technologies is generally more than the older people, this might also be the reason that personal innovativeness is a crucial factor in the adoption of cryptocurrencies. Hence, it can be said that people who like to experiment with new technologies or look out for ways to try out the innovative products, will have an optimistic outlook towards using cryptocurrencies and even have confidence in their proficiency.

From the data analysis, the results additionally show that personal innovativeness did not appear to have a strong relationship with perceived ease of use. This means that people with higher level of innovativeness did not place much prominence on the efforts required to learn the use of cryptocurrencies. It is critical to note that in most of the studies that the external factors tend to have an influence on perceived usefulness and not on perceived ease of use (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000).

8. Another psychological trait that was investigated in this research was the construct of proactive personality. As mentioned in the hypothesis development section, proactive personality was assumed to have a relationship with attitude towards using the cryptocurrencies, their perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Out of these, surprisingly, the construct of proactive personality only showed an impact on perceived usefulness. It was determined that this construct has not been studied in context of adoption of financial products and specifically cryptocurrencies. Since it was established in the literature review that personality plays a role in adoption of technologies (Devaraj, Easley and Crant, 2008), proactive personality was incorporated in this study. The results confirmed that people with proactive personalities do not get affected by changes in situations in their surrounding environments. In contrast to this, people who do not show such behaviours are not able to cultivate habits of seizing viable opportunities of investing in such financial products (Crant, 1996). In effect, the findings reveal that proactive personality only affected the perception of usefulness of the users. This indicates that people who have an eye for viable opportunities, who can take hold of any new opportunities and can overcome challenges, will identify and rely on the productivity and efficiency provided by the use of

cryptocurrencies. Further, the results established that having a proactive personality will not directly impact the attitude of using cryptocurrencies of the users.

9. It is worth highlighting that the above findings confirmed significant relationships per the results from the data analysis. It is also important to discuss the factors that did not prove to be statistically significant. The relation between perceived ease of use and attitude towards using cryptocurrencies appeared to be statistically insignificant thereby opposing the hypothesis earlier defined in the study. This statistically insignificant relationship is seen in many other related studies (Roussou, Stiakakis and Sifaleras, 2019; Holden and Karsh, 2010; Yang and Yoo, 2004). A comparative and corroborative research by Davis (1989) who introduced the model of technology acceptance established that the correlation between perceived ease of use and attitude towards usage comes out to be rather weak. Furthermore, in a study by Keil, Beranek and Konsynski (1995) it was decided that perceived usefulness is considered to be a more important factor than the perceived ease of use. In the context of cryptocurrencies, this is driven by the fact that many users do not give credence to the simplicity of using the cryptocurrencies; instead, they focus on their functionality or usefulness (Roussou, Stiakakis and Sifaleras, 2019). This might also be due to the fact that people often tend to form strong opinions about cryptocurrencies based on how much they perceive it to be risky, trustworthy, useful etc. Once they have an opinion, the ease of using cryptocurrencies does not really have a significant effect on their views. This is the reason why perceived usefulness had a strong significant impact on attitude towards using cryptocurrencies while perceived ease of use showed that it does not have a significant relationship with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies.

Once again, noting that the majority of the participants in the study belonged to younger age groups and that these younger generations generally tend to learn new technologies easily given their familiarity with the new innovations, this could possibly be the reason that such younger folks might or did not consider the mental effort required to operate cryptocurrencies. It is also known that in today's world people are generally quite familiar and comfortable using the digital payments framework and other such innovations, so they are not hesitant to learn to use cryptocurrencies which are also not very difficult to interact with. This could be another justification for ease of use not being a significant factor. Furthermore, from the potential users' point of view, it can be understood that when people have limited

or no experience of using or trading cryptocurrencies, they simply do not base their attitude on the ease of using them rather they concentrate on other factors. Subsequently, this research enhances the literature regarding cryptocurrencies, by indicating that the users or potential users lay importance to their perception of trust, legal status, and usefulness rather than the efforts needed to use cryptocurrencies.

10. Lastly, there were two additional factors namely privacy risk and technology anxiety, that did not seem to have a statistically strong relationship with attitude towards using cryptocurrencies, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Surprisingly, the results of the study show that privacy risk is not a significant factor in the adoption of cryptocurrencies. This might be due to the reason that participants who responded to the survey believed that cryptocurrencies are trustworthy and had confidence that their personal information will not be exploited while using or trading in cryptocurrencies. Individuals who are aware of the fact that cryptocurrencies that are based on and driven by blockchain technology perceive that this system operates as a distributed ledger real time network and could, thus, be considered a secure and trustworthy system (Inci and Lagasse, 2019). Accordingly, users believe that if they make transactions using cryptocurrencies, it will not lead to any kind of misuse of their financial or personal information. It might also be possible that the users as well as potential users are more concerned about the legal aspect of cryptocurrencies rather than their privacy issues as shown in the results. Since they do not have issues related to privacy risk, it does not have an impact on their perceptions of functionality and efforts required to use cryptocurrencies and, therefore, on their likeability of the cryptocurrencies. However, this does not indicate that privacy risk is not an important factor. Sometimes, due to features like pseudonymity and disposal of controlling authorities that cryptocurrencies involve, they might conceivably be utilized for crimes including money laundering, unlawful transactions, etc. (Juels, Kosba and Shi, 2016). The attribute of anonymity withholds the identity of users by offering an encrypted public address. This is beneficial in concealing any kind of personal information but at the same time makes ideal situations for unlawful usage of cryptocurrencies (Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018). This might also be a reason that privacy risk is not a significant factor as without proper laws and policies, cryptocurrencies are often utilised for illegal activities. In addition to this, studies related to cryptocurrency adoption like research conducted by Mendoza-Tello et al. (2018) and J Walton and A. Johnston (2018), the

suggested findings are similar to this study. There is a uniformity in responses and findings suggesting that perceived risk and perceived security risk are not significant factors in understanding the intentions of adopting cryptocurrencies. In addition to this, most people are now very used to sharing their private information with technology companies like Google, Facebook, or third-party banking apps etc. Therefore, it is possible that most users and potential users also don't assume their privacy is at risk when dealing with crypto-exchanges, especially considering the security and anonymity granted by cryptocurrencies. Furthermore, as privacy risk with respect to cryptocurrencies is rather a contentious factor and is quite dependent on the kind of intentions the users hold, it calls for further research with larger sample size to be conducted on matters of privacy risk and their impact on consumer behaviour towards cryptocurrencies.

11. Regarding the issue of technology anxiety, results show that it is not a significant factor and does not have an impact on the users' perceptions of usability, ease of use, and even their attitude towards cryptocurrencies. It is known that technology anxiety relates to that feeling of nervousness while using or thinking of using a technology (Saadé and Kira, 2006). In the context of cryptocurrencies, it was observed that people do not show feelings of anxiety towards using cryptocurrencies and they are not intimidated to use them. This might be due to the reason that cryptocurrency applications are not difficult to deal with since the transactions can be made using mobile phones and internet access that are not difficult to access nor operate (Härdle, Harvey and Reule, 2020). Another point to be noted is that even perceived ease of use did not have a significant impact on the attitude towards adoption of cryptocurrencies, so it might be possible if users or potential users are not focusing on the efforts required to interact with cryptocurrencies, they are also not apprehensive to use them. Furthermore, in this global innovative era, the use of new technologies has become part of everyone's lifestyle, so instead of being intimidated or worrying about using new innovations like cryptocurrencies, people are rather curious about them. Furthermore, due to various reasons such as the simplicity of using cryptocurrencies and continuous interaction of users and potential users with new technological interfaces like digital payments framework, etc., the respondents of the survey might not have considered the aspect of technology anxiety as important relative to the other important factors. Hence technology anxiety showed a statistically insignificant relationship in the analysis.

Chapter 7 Conclusion

7.1 Overview of the Chapter

This study set out to identify the motivating factors and interrelationships that drive customers to perceive and adopt cryptocurrencies as means of trading or engaging in regular financial transactions. In the previous sections, the background to the development of cryptocurrencies and supporting theoretical frameworks have been discussed in-depth. In addition, statistical analysis has been conducted based on survey information generated from a large pool of respondents who potentially patronize cryptocurrencies. In this chapter of the thesis, conclusions deriving from the analysis of the data and findings are drawn. Here, the focus is on discussing how the study was successful in answering the research question and achieving the objectives of the research as laid down in the introductory chapter. In addition, this chapter throws more light on the theoretical contributions, managerial and social implications of this study. Lastly, this chapter supplies the limitations of this research and provides the reviewer of this study with some directions for future research work.

7.2 Conclusions

Cryptocurrencies that are based on the blockchain technology are quickly attracting a lot of interest as an innovation that could possibly be historic and disruptive for the financial industry on a worldwide scale. However, the fate of cryptocurrency is exceptionally muddled as there are various uses to which it could be put in the wake of the varied and divergent needs and requirements of different consumers. It is essential to understand those factors that drive cryptocurrency adoption for gaining insights into the future aspects and understand the potential factors that might lead to their wider adoption. To accomplish this, the main aim of this research was to investigate the factors or the behavioural patterns of the consumers that play a crucial role in the adoption of cryptocurrencies. A model was developed that incorporated various factors from the literature concerning the theories of acceptance of technology, domain of social psychology, theories of trust and risk. Through

the development of this model, the major research question for this study was addressed, which was to find those exogenous factors that influence the adoption of consumer behaviour. The factors that were found to be significant included attitude towards using the cryptocurrencies, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived trust, bandwagon effect, legal risk, personal innovativeness and proactive personality. The study was conducted through the lens of four objectives which included the review of existing literature on technology adoption of new innovations including financial technologies, understanding the concept of cryptocurrencies and applying the theories of technology adoption to the context of cryptocurrencies, developing a multi-criterion model presenting the relationships among the most crucial constructs that have an impact on consumers' perceptions of cryptocurrencies, and identifying the significant factors that play a role in consumers' adoption of cryptocurrencies.

The study critically examined the literature on adoption of technology and consumers' intentions towards buying and investing in cryptocurrencies. Various studies were scrutinized thoroughly to comprehend the adoption of new technologies and consequently, theories like theory of reasoned action (TRA), theory of planned behaviour (TPB), and technology acceptance model (TAM) were reviewed and it was determined that TAM, the most commonly and widely adopted theory, was also the most appropriate for this research. Additionally, it was comprehended that constructs like risk, trust and socio-psychological factors also play a critical role in the acceptance of technologies. The constructs of perceived trust, legal risk, privacy risk, bandwagon effect, personal innovativeness, proactive personality and technology anxiety were then integrated with the core constructs of TAM being perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude towards usage of technology, and intentions of adopting the technology.

The concept of cryptocurrencies was understood as currency units generated digitally through cryptography and used as a medium of exchange without the involvement of any controlling central authority. Various cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin, Litecoin, Ripples and Ethereum were discussed in-depth. The functionality, characteristics, advantages and disadvantages of cryptocurrencies were also studied to have clearer understanding of the functionalities of cryptocurrencies. The TAM and other concepts or theories were then applied to the context of cryptocurrencies in order to understand the factors that influence

the adoption of cryptocurrencies. The development of hypotheses took place where each variable was well defined along with their corresponding hypothesis.

The research methodology employed in this research was that of a positivist philosophy and quantitative approach wherein the collection of data involved a survey questionnaire that had items composed from studies conducted in the same field. To address the objective of developing a multi-criterion model, the data that was then analysed through structural equation modelling (SEM) using software like SPSS and AMOS. The developed model provided statistically significant results and the model fit was checked using the various fit indices.

Finally, the factors that influence the adoption of cryptocurrencies were identified through the testing of hypotheses. The factors that appeared to have a positive and significant relationship with intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies were attitude towards using cryptocurrencies and bandwagon effect. The constructs including perceived usefulness, perceived trust, legal risk, personal innovativeness and again bandwagon effect were found to have a significant influence on the attitude towards using cryptocurrencies. Some constructs like proactive personality only had an impact on perceived usefulness of cryptocurrencies. The factors that were found to be statistically insignificant for the adoption of cryptocurrencies were privacy risk and technology anxiety.

In conclusion, it can be said that cryptocurrencies are major disruptive and innovative financial products that have the potential to substitute the current financial payment methods and eliminate the governing financial institutions and banks. Their adoption is increasing tremendously all around the world and it is crucial to identify those factors that have significant effects on their adoption to be able to predict their future scenarios in the market. This study was able to recognize the perceptions, opinions and emotions of both users and potential users towards the usage and adoption of cryptocurrencies by drawing literature from various fields and analysing the data in order to identify the factors that play a role in the adoption of cryptocurrencies.

7.3 Contributions to the Theory

Cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin, Ethereum, Litecoin, Ripple, etc. have gained a lot of attention from academicians and the media. Cryptocurrency is not the same as other technologies as it has financial perspectives, legal issues, social-psychological components, risks, etc. Accordingly, a far-reaching model comprising of socio-technical factors was suitable to give a comprehensive perspective on the reception of cryptocurrencies. In spite of the hype and worldwide publicity of cryptocurrencies, the literature regarding their consumer adoption is limited. This study attempts to address the significant gaps by utilizing the technology acceptance model (TAM) and the outcomes derived are important addition to the developing literature surrounding cryptocurrencies. All the more explicitly, this is the pioneer attempt expanding the technology acceptance model by integrating important constructs from theories of trust, risk and most importantly from the domain of consumer psychology.

One prominent discovery from this research is that the bandwagon effect or herd behaviour in the context of cryptocurrencies is being given a lot of importance; however, it was discovered that no study to the knowledge of the researcher has examined the impact of bandwagon effect in the adoption of cryptocurrencies. Moreover, bandwagon effect appeared to have a significant relationship with the intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies as well as on attitude towards using the cryptocurrencies. This is a major theoretical contribution since the construct of bandwagon effect can later be integrated in various research work related to disruptive technology adoption. The other psychological constructs which are personal innovativeness and proactive personality were also novel additions to the factors of adoption of cryptocurrencies. Moreover, it was observed that there is very limited research work that covers a comprehensive literature regarding the adoption of cryptocurrencies.

A noteworthy effort was made in this study to provide a comprehensive review of the extant literature that looks at adoption of cryptocurrencies. This worthwhile contribution to the field of cryptocurrency adoption also highlights the theories that have been used by other studies. Furthermore, since the analysis was conducted using high level statistical technique of structural equation modelling to test the hypothesis and assess the model fit, the results can be considered as viable and generalizable. The results and findings of the study can be extended to research conducted in related fields while opening new possibilities for future

research. Overall, this study brings major contributions by extending the theories of technology adoption and expanding the boundaries relating to the literature in adoption of cryptocurrencies.

7.4 Managerial and Social Implications

The findings of this research provide many practical and empirical inferences. They are useful for many stakeholders including the users, brokers, crypto exchanges, investors or managers, companies or businesses accepting payments in the form of cryptocurrencies, companies launching their own cryptocurrencies, cryptocurrency miners, etc. Regarding the managerial implications, this research will aid in understanding the requirements of consumers and investors, thereby assisting in development of innovative and productive ways to deliver the paramount cryptocurrency services. Companies or firms looking to issue their own cryptocurrencies can extract the lessons learnt and patterns seen in consumer behaviour of cryptocurrencies in this research. In addition, some findings would even prove to be useful for governments, banks or other financial institutions by highlighting the importance of designing policies regarding cryptocurrencies and upgrading their services. Moreover, the results of the study can aid the users and potential users of cryptocurrencies in anticipating the prospects and threats that might emerge later on.

Since the results revealed that perceived usefulness was a significant factor, it is recommended that crypto service providers should emphasize on enhancing the usability and efficiency of cryptocurrencies as well reducing their disadvantages. By providing effective services and adding value to them, the attitude of the consumers towards usage of cryptocurrencies can become positive (Jang et al., 2020). Usefulness of the cryptocurrencies can be improved through a number of ways. For instance, by reducing the transaction time, reducing transaction charges, creating a crypto network coupled to a stable coin, enhancing the safety and security of the crypto network etc. According to this research, such actions can positively affect the attitude towards cryptocurrency adoption.

Substantial efforts can be made by the marketers in order to make sure that the value of cryptocurrencies is perceived by the users and potential users. It is recommended that potential users be made aware of the benefits of cryptocurrencies so that more people become interested in getting involved in the cryptocurrencies. Marketers need to explain why

using their coin is advantageous, and what is the intrinsic value of their coin. One of the ways to convert potential users to the user group could be by informing them about the bigger picture or the vision of cryptocurrencies in the near future. Also, the significant impact of perceived ease of use on perceived usefulness recommends that the focus of the crypto exchanges and developers should be to make the cryptocurrency platforms and wallets easy to handle and simple to interact with. This will help in bringing out the usability of the system and ultimately lead to growth in the adoption of cryptocurrencies. Also, to make cryptocurrency usage smooth and stress-free, marketers could adopt simple and user-friendly methods to educate potential consumers about cryptocurrencies (VISA, 2021).

The findings reported in this study shed new light on the bandwagon effect showing a strong influence on intentions and attitude of consumers towards cryptocurrencies. Hence, the crypto brokers and exchanges dealing in cryptocurrencies can take the opportunity of the bandwagon effect and develop strategies to attract large number of investors who can provide them with high market capitalisations (Calderón, 2018). Social media and online discussion groups can play a role in this regard for being a magnet for a large scale of users.

From the consumers' point of view, they must be aware of the risks and disadvantages related to cryptocurrencies and must be well-informed about where they are putting their resources. Crypto being deeply social and cultural phenomenon, people jump on to the bandwagon without analysing the important aspects of investing in cryptocurrencies. It is crucial that people do not blindly follow the groups that they are associated with when investing in cryptocurrencies, they should understand the timing of trading, potential of cryptocurrencies, the risk-reward ratio, etc.

As it is seen that adoption of cryptocurrencies has various perspectives including trust factors, financial aspects, legal issues, psychological components, risks, etc. This implies that this research has social implications associated with it. For instance, the Terra network, a cryptocurrency network, recently experienced a massive crash that led to nearly USD 60 billion being wiped out within four days (Bloomberg, 2022). The associated crypto coins TerraUSD, Luna etc were considered to be a safe avenue to invest and as a consequence of the bandwagon effect, within less than two years the Luna, UST coins had become one of the most traded digital coins. This incident reinforces the fact that instead of following the herd behaviour, it is important that people do their due diligence before investing in

cryptocurrencies. Major crashes like this adversely affect consumer's perception of trust in cryptocurrencies. Moreover, such events also highlight the lack of legal recourse and reinforce the need for clarity with the policies and laws regarding cryptocurrencies. These factors negatively affect the consumers view of cryptocurrencies and hamper their adoption.

The legal status of cryptocurrencies is still uncertain and this research finds that legal risk has a significant influence on adoption of cryptocurrencies. It is recommended that the governments should work on framing the laws regarding cryptocurrencies such that their usability is enhanced. The laws should be designed to address the risky and illicit aspects of cryptocurrency usage, such as their usage for scams, criminal activities, unregulated speculations etc. While on the other hand their positive usage should be encouraged. Also, the increase in knowledge and information on innovation and the compliances encompassing cryptocurrencies among financial institutions will alleviate the perception of complexity (EY, 2021). The financial institutions must work in this regard to redesign the policies as well as bring clarity for use of cryptocurrencies which will also increase the security level among the users of cryptocurrencies. By providing appropriate guidelines, use of cryptocurrencies in illicit and illegal activities can then be avoided. A study conducted by VISA (2021) showed that if cryptocurrencies are made more accessible by the financial institutions and banks, it will have a significant impact on the engagement of users.

Furthermore, looking at the significant impact of personal innovativeness towards the attitude and usefulness, the crypto brokers and marketers should draw the attention of innovative users towards the cryptocurrencies. Addition of such innovative and intriguing elements to the crypto applications can stimulate stakeholders to adopt them in their daily lives. The target group can include people who like to experiment with the new innovations, the younger generations, tech-savvy people, information technology experts, etc.

Increasing trustworthiness and integrity of cryptocurrency transactions must be considered by the developers and crypto exchanges. Trust can be stimulated by using consensus protocols like proof of work (PoW) and proof of stake (PoS) that are based on blockchains. There is a platform called IBM Hyperledger which was developed for applications based on blockchain. This platform brings in a system of management that has a feature of collaboration which ensures security and trustworthiness to the users (Albayati, Kim and Rho,

2020). It should also be noted that the users of cryptocurrencies are more likely to have trust in them if they are regulated by the governments (Arli et al., 2020).

In conclusion, from a managerial point of view the key proposal is to put resources into the improvement of the usability of the crypto services and delivery of those important features that increase trust to a significant level. Without this, potential users will not be able to realise the value of cryptocurrencies. Hence, their possible take-up and the user's satisfaction will be restricted. The opportunity of the bandwagon effect should be taken advantage of by the marketers through media and online social platforms. Additionally, regulations surrounding cryptocurrencies can be drafted so as to maximize their positive impact, and thereby affecting the user's acknowledgement of cryptocurrencies. Hence, it is important that laws are made clearer at national as well as international levels. All things considered, a holistic approach must be adopted by the players of the market in digital innovation and financial domain if the cryptocurrencies are to disrupt the trading, payments, loans and credits, and much more in the near future.

7.5 Limitations of the Study and Future Research Ideas

As the major objective of the study was to get a comprehensive outlook regarding the factors contributing to adoption of cryptocurrencies from a multidisciplinary perspective, a lot of constructs were examined and therefore several hypotheses were developed. This research aimed to investigate numerous constructs and their relations with the aim to make novel contributions to the field of consumer behaviour. As a natural consequence of this, many factors were found to not have significant relationships, thereby resulting in several hypotheses being rejected. This can be considered as one of the limitations of this research. This also indicates that factors like privacy risk, perceived ease of use and technology anxiety in association with cryptocurrencies should be further researched.

Regardless of the fact that this study has looked into various constructs and factors that lead to adoption of cryptocurrencies at an international level, it would be intriguing to see how adoption of cryptocurrencies is perceived within different countries. A natural progression will be to conduct a comparative study of developed, developing and under developed countries for understanding the opinions and views of people regarding cryptocurrencies.

Though the study covers many aspects of adoption of cryptocurrencies, and provides stakeholders of this thesis with generalizable results and models , it still lacks some elements. The sample size of the study was limited to 202 legitimate participants. Researchers can focus on conducting large-scale studies including diverse populations in order to draw inferences at an advanced level by replicating the model used in this research.

The study was also limited by the scope of risk identification. The theory of risk could be expanded and more types of risks affecting the intentions to adopt cryptocurrencies can be studied. As it was seen that the aspect of bandwagon effect proved to be significant, a similar construct known as Fear of Missing out (FOMO) and other socio-psychological constructs could be included in future research work. Since it was observed that there are many studies associated with Bitcoin, many different types of cryptocurrencies like Litecoin, Ethereum, ripples and their brand perception could also be studied.

One more aspect that can be examined by the scholars in the future research work is including the usage of cryptocurrencies in illicit activities like tax evasion, money laundering, buying illegal products, etc (Nadeem et al., 2021). Since it is known that there is a lot of wastage of energy and resources in the mining of some cryptocurrencies (Krause and Tolaymat, 2018), future research can include the elements of sustainability and environmental concerns. The model should be recurrently updated based on the new trends as well as innovative sustainable technologies.

References

- Aarts, H., Verplanken, B. and Knippenberg, A. (1998) Predicting Behavior From Actions in the Past: Repeated Decision Making or a Matter of Habit? Journal of Applied Social Psychology. Vol.28 (15), pp.1355-1374.
- Abbasi, G., Tiew, L., Tang, J., Goh, Y. and Thurasamy, R. (2021) The adoption of cryptocurrency as a disruptive force: Deep learning-based dual stage structural equation modelling and artificial neural network analysis. PLOS ONE. Vol.16 (3), article no: e0247582.
- Abramova, S. and Böhme, R. (2016) Perceived Benefit and Risk as Multidimensional Determinants of Bitcoin Use: A Quantitative Exploratory Study. International Conference on Information Systems. pp.1-20.
- Adams, J., Khan, H. T. A. and Raeside, R. (2014) Research methods for business and social science students. Second edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications.
- Agarwal, R. and Prasad, J. (1998) A Conceptual and Operational Definition of Personal Innovativeness in the Domain of Information Technology. Information Systems Research. Vol.9 (2), pp.204-215.
- Aggarwal, S. and Kumar, N. (2020) Cryptocurrencies. In: Advances in Computers. Elsevier, pp.227–266.
- Agustina, D. (2019) Extension of Technology Acceptance Model (Etam): Adoption of Cryptocurrency Online Trading Technology. Jurnal Ekonomi. Vol.24 (2), pp.272-287.
- Ajzen, I. (1985) From Intentions to Actions: A Theory of Planned Behavior. In Action Control. pp.11-39.
- Ajzen, I. (1987) Attitudes, Traits, and Actions: Dispositional Prediction of Behavior in Personality and Social Psychology. Advances in Experimental Social Psychology. Vol.20, pp.1-63.

- Ajzen, I. (1988) Attitudes, personality, and behavior. 2nd ed. Chicago: Dorsey Prints.
- Ajzen, I. (1991) The theory of planned behavior. Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes. Vol.50 (2), pp.179-211.
- Ajzen, I. (2021) The Theory of Planned Behavior: A Bibliography [Online]. Available: <https://people.umass.edu/aizen/tpbrefs.html> [Accessed 17 Jun 2021].
- Ajzen, I. and Fishbein, M. (1980) Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall.
- Ajzen, I. and Fishbein, M. (2005) The handbook of attitudes. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Ajzen, I. and Madden, T. (1986) Prediction of goal-directed behavior: Attitudes, intentions, and perceived behavioral control. Journal of Experimental Social Psychology. Vol.22 (5), pp.453-474.
- Akar, S. and Akar, E. (2020) Is it a New Tulip Mania Age?. Journal of Information Technology Research. Vol.13 (1), pp.44-67.
- Alaklabi, S. and Kang, K. (2021) Perceptions towards Cryptocurrency Adoption: A case of Saudi Arabian Citizens. Journal of Electronic Banking Systems. Vol.21, pp.1-17.
- Alarcon, G. M., Lyons, J. B., Christensen, J. C., Klosterman, S. L., Bowers, M. A., Ryan, T. J., Jessup, S. A. and Wynne, K. T. (2018) The effect of propensity to trust and perceptions of trustworthiness on trust behaviors in dyads. Behavior Research Methods. Vol.50 (5), pp.1906–1920.
- Alavi, M. and Henderson, J. C. (1981) An Evolutionary Strategy for Implementing a Decision Support System. Management Science. Vol.27 (11), pp.1309–1323.
- Albayati, H., Kim, S. and Rho, J. (2020) Accepting financial transactions using blockchain technology and cryptocurrency: A customer perspective approach. Technology in Society. Vol.62, article no: 101320.

- Aljabr, A., Sharma, A. and Kumar, K. (2019) Mining Process in Cryptocurrency Using Blockchain Technology: Bitcoin as a Case Study. Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience. Vol.16 (10), pp.4293-4298.
- Alqaryouti, O., Siyam, N., Alkashri, Z. and Shaalan, K. (2020) Cryptocurrency Usage Impact on Perceived Benefits and Users' Behaviour. Information Systems. Vol.381, pp.123-136.
- Amin, M., Rezaei, S. and Abolghasemi, M. (2014) User satisfaction with mobile websites: the impact of perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU) and trust. Nankai Business Review International. Vol.5 (3), pp.258-274.
- Amoroso, D. and Lim, R. (2015) Exploring the Personal Innovativeness Construct: The Roles of Ease of Use, Satisfaction and Attitudes. Asia Pacific Journal of Information Systems. Vol.25 (4), pp.662-685.
- Anderson, A. (2014) Business statistics for dummies. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Andoh, C. (2018) Predicting students' intention to adopt mobile learning. Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning. Vol.11 (2), pp.178-191.
- Andoni, M., Robu, V., Flynn, D., Abram, S., Geach, D., Jenkins, D., McCallum, P. and Peacock, A. (2019) Blockchain technology in the energy sector: A systematic review of challenges and opportunities. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. Vol.100, pp.143-174.
- Antonopoulos, A. (2017) Mastering Bitcoin. Sebastopol, California: O'Reilly.
- AR, S. and Banik, B. (2020) A Comprehensive Study of Blockchain Services: Future of Cryptography. International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications. Vol.11 (10), pp.279-288.

- Arias-Oliva, M., Pelegrín-Borondo, J. and Matías-Clavero, G. (2019) Variables Influencing Cryptocurrency Use: A Technology Acceptance Model in Spain. Frontiers in Psychology. Vol.10, article no: 475.
- Arli, D., Esch, P., Bakpayev, M. and Laurence, A. (2020) Do consumers really trust cryptocurrencies?. Marketing Intelligence & Planning. Vol.39 (1), pp.74-90.
- Armitage, C. and Conner, M. (2001) Efficacy of the Theory of Planned Behaviour: A meta-analytic review. British Journal of Social Psychology. Vol.40 (4), pp.471-499.
- Armknecht, F., Karame, G., Mandal, A., Youssef, F. and Zenner, E. (2015) Ripple: Overview and Outlook. Trust and Trustworthy Computing. Vol.9229, pp.163-180.
- Athey, S., Parashkevov, I., Sarukkai, V. and Xia, J. (2016) Bitcoin Pricing, Adoption, and Usage: Theory and Evidence. Stanford Graduate School of Business Research Paper Series. pp.16-42.
- Atkinson, M. and Kydd, C. (1997) Individual characteristics associated with World Wide Web use: an empirical study of playfulness and motivation. ACM SIGMIS Database: the DATABASE for Advances in Information Systems. Vol.28 (2), pp.53–62.
- Axsen, J., Orlebar, C. and Skippon, S. (2013) Social influence and consumer preference formation for pro-environmental technology: The case of a U.K. workplace electric-vehicle study. Ecological Economics. Vol.95, pp.96–107.
- Bagozzi, R. (1992) The Self-Regulation of Attitudes, Intentions, and Behavior. Social Psychology Quarterly. Vol.55 (2), pp.178-204.
- Bagozzi, R. (2007) The Legacy of the Technology Acceptance Model and a Proposal for a Paradigm Shift. Journal of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.8 (4), pp.244–254.
- Bagozzi, R. and Yi, Y. (1988) On the evaluation of structural equation models. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. Vol.16 (1), pp.74-94.

- Bahmanziari, T., Pearson, J. M. and Crosby, L. (2016) Is Trust Important in Technology Adoption? A Policy Capturing Approach. Journal of Computer Information Systems. Vol.43 (4), pp.46-54.
- Bambrough, B. (2021) Crypto Price Prediction: Bitcoin Could Be Left In The Dust By Ethereum In 2021 [Online]. Forbes. Available: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/billybambrough/2021/07/28/crypto-price-prediction-bitcoin-could-be-left-in-the-dust-by-ethereum-in-2021/> [Accessed 20 Aug 2021].
- Bamert, T., Decker, C., Elsen, L., Wattenhofer, R. and Welten, S. (2013) Have a snack, pay with Bitcoins. In: IEEE P2P 2013 Proceedings. Presented at the IEEE P2P 2013 Proceedings, pp.1–5.
- Bandura, A. (1982) Self-efficacy mechanism in human agency. American Psychologist. Vol.37 (2), pp.122-147.
- Barakat, A. and Hussainey, K. (2013) Bank governance, regulation, supervision, and risk reporting: Evidence from operational risk disclosures in European banks. International Review of Financial Analysis. Vol.30, pp.254–273.
- Barber, S., Boyen, X., Shi, E. and Uzun, E. (2012) Bitter to Better — How to Make Bitcoin a Better Currency. In: Keromytis, A. D. (ed.). Financial Cryptography and Data Security. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, Vol.7397, pp.399–414.
- Barkhi, R. and Wallace, L. (2007) The impact of personality type on purchasing decisions in virtual stores. Information Technology and Management. Vol.8 (4), pp.313-330.
- Barnfield, M. (2020) Think Twice before Jumping on the Bandwagon: Clarifying Concepts in Research on the Bandwagon Effect. Political Studies Review. Vol.18 (4), pp.553–574.
- Basak, S., Govender, D. and Govender, I. (2016) Examining the impact of privacy, Security, and trust on the TAM and TTF models for e-commerce consumers: A pilot study. 2016 14th Annual Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust (PST). pp.19-26.

- Bateman, T. and Crant, J. (1993) The proactive component of organizational behavior: A measure and correlates. Journal of Organizational Behavior. Vol.14 (2), pp.103-118.
- Bauer, R. (1960) Consumer behavior as risk taking. In: Hancock, R. Dynamic marketing for a changing world. Chicago: American Marketing Association, pp.389-98.
- Baumgartner, H. and Homburg, C. (1996) Applications of structural equation modeling in marketing and consumer research: A review. International Journal of Research in Marketing. Vol.13 (2), pp.139-161.
- Baur, A., Bühler, J., Bick, M. and Bonorden, C. (2015) Cryptocurrencies as a Disruption? Empirical Findings on User Adoption and Future Potential of Bitcoin and Co. In: Open and Big Data Management and Innovation. pp.63-80.
- Bearden, W. and Mason, J. (1978) Consumer-perceived risk and attitudes toward generically prescribed drugs. Journal of Applied Psychology. Vol.63 (6), pp.741-746.
- Béjaoui, A., Mgadmi, N., Moussa, W. and Sadraoui, T. (2021) A short-and long-term analysis of the nexus between Bitcoin, social media and Covid-19 outbreak. Heliyon. Vol.7 (7), article no: e07539.
- Belanche, D., Casaló, L. and Flavián, C. (2012) Integrating trust and personal values into the Technology Acceptance Model: The case of e-government services adoption. Cuadernos de Economía y Dirección de la Empresa. Vol.15 (4), pp.192-204.
- Benton, T. and Craib, I. (2010) Philosophy of social science: the philosophical foundations of social thought. 2nd ed., 10th anniversary ed. Houndsmill, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Berentsen, A. and Schar, F. (2018) A Short Introduction to the World of Cryptocurrencies. Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Review. Vol.100 (1), pp.1-19.

- Bhaskar, N. and Chuen, D. (2015) Bitcoin Exchanges. In: Handbook of Digital Currency. pp.559-573.
- Bhattacharjee, A. (2000) Acceptance of e-commerce services: the case of electronic brokerages. IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans. Vol.30 (4), pp.411–420.
- Bloomberg (2022). How \$60 Billion in Terra Coins Went Up in Algorithmic Smoke. [Online] Available: <https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2022-crypto-luna-terra-stablecoin-explainer/> [Accessed 27 May 2022].
- Blue, C. (1995) The predictive capacity of the theory of reasoned action and the theory of planned behavior in exercise research: An integrated literature review. Research in Nursing & Health. Vol.18 (2), pp.105-121.
- Böhme, R., Christin, N., Edelman, B. and Moore, T. (2015) Bitcoin: Economics, Technology, and Governance. Journal of Economic Perspectives. Vol.29 (2), pp.213–238.
- Bohr, J. and Bashir, M. (2014) Who Uses Bitcoin? An exploration of the Bitcoin community. 2014 Twelfth Annual International Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust. pp. 94-101.
- Bollen, K. (2010) Structural equations with latent variables. New York: Wiley.
- Brody, R. P. and Cunningham, S. M. (1968) Personality Variables and the Consumer Decision Process. Journal of Marketing Research. Vol.5 (1), pp.50–57.
- Brown, S. (2016) Cryptocurrency and criminality. The Police Journal: Theory, Practice and Principles. Vol.89 (4), pp.327-339.
- Browne, M. and Cudeck, R. (1992) Alternative Ways of Assessing Model Fit. Sociological Methods & Research. Vol.21 (2), pp.230-258.
- Bryman, A. and Bell, E. (2011) Business research methods. 3rd ed. New York: Oxford University Press Inc.

- Buabeng-Andoh, C. (2018) Predicting students' intention to adopt mobile learning. Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning. Vol.11 (2), pp.178-191.
- Burton-Jones, A. and Hubona, G. S. (2006) The mediation of external variables in the technology acceptance model. Information & Management. Vol.43 (6), pp.706–717.
- Business Insider (2021). The estimated number of global crypto users has passed 100 million - and boomers are now getting drawn to bitcoin too, reports find. [Online]. Available: <https://www.businessinsider.in/stock-market/news/the-estimated-number-of-global-crypto-users-has-passed-100-million-and-boomers-are-now-getting-drawn-to-bitcoin-too-reports-find/articleshow/81210262.cms> [Accessed 22 May 2021].
- Business Standard (2021) Bitcoin digital currency being considered by UK authorities. [Online]. Business-standard.com. Available: https://www.business-standard.com/article/international/bitcoin-digital-currency-being-considered-by-uk-authorities-121041900908_1.html [Accessed 28 Apr 2021].
- Cabanac, M. (2002) What is emotion? Behavioural Processes. Vol.60 (2), pp.69–83.
- Cai, C. (2018) Disruption of financial intermediation by FinTech: a review on crowdfunding and blockchain. Accounting & Finance. Vol.58 (4), pp.965-992.
- Calderón, O. (2018) Herding behavior in cryptocurrency markets [online]. [Preprint]. [Viewed 28 April 2021]. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1806.11348.pdf>
- Calisir, F., Altin Gumussoy, C., Bayraktaroglu, A. and Karaali, D. (2014) Predicting the Intention to Use a Web-Based Learning System: Perceived Content Quality, Anxiety, Perceived System Quality, Image, and the Technology Acceptance Model. Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries. Vol.24 (5), pp.515-531.
- Campbell, D. and Fiske, D. (1959) Convergent and discriminant validation by the multitrait-multimethod matrix. Psychological Bulletin. Vol.56 (2), pp.81-105.

- Campbell, M. C. and Goodstein, R. C. (2001) The Moderating Effect of Perceived Risk on Consumers' Evaluations of Product Incongruity: Preference for the Norm. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.28 (3), pp.439–449.
- Carmines, E. and Zeller, R. (1979) Reliability and validity assessment. Beverly Hills, California. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Casino, F., Dasaklis, T. and Patsakis, C. (2019) A systematic literature review of blockchain-based applications: Current status, classification and open issues. Telematics and Informatics. Vol.36, pp.55-81.
- Cazier, J., Wilson, E. and Medlin, B. (2007) The Role of Privacy Risk in IT Acceptance. International Journal of Information Security and Privacy. Vol.1 (2), pp.61-73.
- Chaiken, S. (1987) The heuristic model of persuasion. In: Social influence: the Ontario symposium. Vol.5, pp.3-39.
- Chan, S., Chu, J., Nadarajah, S. and Osterrieder, J. (2017) A Statistical Analysis of Cryptocurrencies. Journal of Risk and Financial Management. Vol.10 (2), pp. 1-23.
- Chang, M. (1998) Predicting Unethical Behavior: A Comparison of the Theory of Reasoned Action and the Theory of Planned Behavior. Journal of Business Ethics. Vol.17 (16), pp.1825-1834.
- Chatzoglou, P., Sarigiannidis, L., Vraimaki, E. and Diamantidis, A. (2009) Investigating Greek employees' intention to use web-based training. Computers & Education. Vol.53 (3), pp.877-889.
- Chen, Y. and Barnes, S. (2007) Initial trust and online buyer behaviour. Industrial Management & Data Systems. Vol.107 (1), pp.21-36.
- Cheng, T. C. E., Lam, D. Y. C. and Yeung, A. C. L. (2006) Adoption of internet banking: An empirical study in Hong Kong. Decision Support Systems. Vol.42 (3), pp.1558–1572.

- Cheng, Y. and Huang, T. (2013) High speed rail passengers' mobile ticketing adoption. Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies. Vol.30, pp.143-160.
- Cheon, J., Lee, S., Crooks, S. and Song, J. (2012) An investigation of mobile learning readiness in higher education based on the theory of planned behavior. Computers & Education. Vol.59 (3), pp.1054-1064.
- Child, D. (1990) The essentials of factor analysis. 2nd Ed. London: Cambridge University Press.
- Chohan, U.W. (2021). A History of Dogecoin. Discussion Series: Notes on the 21st Century.
- Christidis, K. and Devetsikiotis, M. (2016) Blockchains and Smart Contracts for the Internet of Things. IEEE Access. Vol.4, pp.2292-2303.
- Christin, N. (2013). Traveling the silk road: a measurement analysis of a large anonymous online marketplace. In: Proceedings of the 22nd international conference on World Wide Web. pp.213-224.
- Chung, N. and Kwon, S. (2009) Effect of trust level on mobile banking satisfaction: a multi-group analysis of information system success instruments. Behaviour & Information Technology. Vol.28 (6), pp.549-562.
- CoinDesk (2020) IMF, World Bank Plan Central Bank Digital Currency Rules - CoinDesk. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coindesk.com/imf-world-bank-g7-countries-to-create-central-bank-digital-currency-rules> [Accessed 28 Apr 2021].
- CoinMarketCap (2021) Cryptocurrency Prices, Charts and Market Capitalizations. [Online]. Available: <https://coinmarketcap.com> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Compeau, D. and Higgins, C. (1995) Computer Self-Efficacy: Development of a Measure and Initial Test. MIS Quarterly. Vol.19 (2), pp.189-211.

- Comte, A. and Bridges, J. H. (1865) A General View of Positivism [Online]. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511692888>.
- Conlon, T., Corbet, S. and McGee, R. J. (2020) Are cryptocurrencies a safe haven for equity markets? An international perspective from the COVID-19 pandemic. Research in International Business and Finance. Vol.54, article no:101248.
- Conner, M. (2001) Health Behaviors. In: International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences. pp.6506-6512.
- Conner, M. (2020) Theory of Planned Behavior. In: Handbook of Sport Psychology. pp.1-18.
- Conti, M., Sandeep Kumar, E., Lal, C. and Ruj, S. (2018) A Survey on Security and Privacy Issues of Bitcoin. IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials. Vol.20 (4), pp.3416-3452.
- Corbet, S., Lucey, B., Urquhart, A. and Yarovaya, L. (2019) Cryptocurrencies as a financial asset: A systematic analysis. International Review of Financial Analysis. Vol.62, pp.182-199.
- Corbetta, P. (2011) Social Research: Theory, Methods and Techniques. London: SAGE Publications.
- Cordero, E., Sánchez, J. and Cortés, M. (2020) Cryptocurrencies as a Financial Tool: Acceptance Factors. Mathematics. Vol.8 (11), article no: 1974.
- Cox, D. F. and Rich, S. U. (1964) Perceived Risk and Consumer Decision-Making—The Case of Telephone Shopping. Journal of Marketing Research. Vol.1 (4), pp.32–39.
- Crant, J. (1996) The proactive personality scale as a predictor of entrepreneurial intentions. Journal of Small Business Management. Vol.34 (3), pp. 42-49.
- Crant, J., Hu, J. and Jiang, K. (2017) Proactive Personality: A twenty-year review. In: Proactivity at Work. New York, NY: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group. pp.193-225.

- Cronbach, L. (1951) Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. Psychometrika. Vol.16 (3), pp.297-334.
- Cvetkova, I. (2018) Cryptocurrencies Legal Regulation. BRICS Law Journal. Vol.5 (2), pp.128-153.
- Dahl, D., White, K., Argo, J. J., Duclos, R., Wan, E. W., Jiang, Y., Shalev, E., Morwitz, V. G., Ordabayeva, N., Chandon, P., Wilcox, K. and Stephen, A. T. (2013) Social Influence and Consumer Behavior. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.40 (2), pp. iii–v.
- Damanpour, F. (1996) Organizational Complexity and Innovation: Developing and Testing Multiple Contingency Models. Management Science. Vol.42 (5), pp.693-716.
- Dash, G. and Paul, J. (2021) CB-SEM vs PLS-SEM methods for research in social sciences and technology forecasting. Technological Forecasting and Social Change. Vol.173, article no: 121092.
- Davis, F. (1989) Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology. MIS Quarterly. Vol.13 (3), pp.319-340.
- Davis, F. (1991) User acceptance of information technology: system characteristics, user perceptions and behavioral impacts. International Journal of Man-Machine Studies. Vol.38 (3), pp.475-487.
- Davis, F. (1993) User acceptance of information technology: system characteristics, user perceptions and behavioral impacts. International Journal of Man-Machine Studies. Vol.38 (3), pp.475-487.
- Davis, F. and Venkatesh, V. (1996) A critical assessment of potential measurement biases in the technology acceptance model: three experiments. International Journal of Human-Computer Studies. Vol.45 (1), pp.19-45.
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P. and Warshaw, P. R. (1992) Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation to Use Computers in the Workplace¹. Journal of Applied Social Psychology. Vol.22 (14), pp.1111–1132.

- Davis, F., Bagozzi, R. and Warshaw, P. (1989) User Acceptance of Computer Technology: A Comparison of Two Theoretical Models. Management Science. Vol.35 (8), pp.982-1003.
- Davis, F.D. (1985) A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: Theory and results. Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- De Maesschalck, R., Jouan-Rimbaud, D. and Massart, D. (2000) The Mahalanobis distance. Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems. Vol.50 (1), pp.1-18.
- Delfabbro, P., King, D. and Williams, J. (2021) The psychology of cryptocurrency trading: Risk and protective factors. Journal of Behavioral Addictions. Vol.10 (2), pp.201-207.
- Demir, E., Bilgin, M. H., Karabulut, G. and Doker, A. C. (2020) The relationship between cryptocurrencies and COVID-19 pandemic. Eurasian Economic Review. Vol.10 (3), pp.349–360.
- Devaraj, S., Easley, R. and Crant, J. (2008) Research Note—How Does Personality Matter? Relating the Five-Factor Model to Technology Acceptance and Use. Information Systems Research. Vol.19 (1), pp.93-105.
- Dhagarra, D., Goswami, M. and Kumar, G. (2020) Impact of Trust and Privacy Concerns on Technology Acceptance in Healthcare: An Indian Perspective. International Journal of Medical Informatics. Vol.141, article no: 104164.
- Diop, E., Zhao, S. and Duy, T. (2019) An extension of the technology acceptance model for understanding travelers' adoption of variable message signs. PLOS ONE. Vol.14 (4), article no: e0216007.
- Dönmez-Turan, A. and Kir, M. (2019) User anxiety as an external variable of technology acceptance model: A meta-analytic study. Procedia Computer Science. Vol.158, pp.715-724.

- Dowling, G. (1986) Perceived risk: The concept and its measurement. Psychology and Marketing. Vol.3 (3), pp.193-210.
- Dziembowski, S. (2015) Introduction to Cryptocurrencies. Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security. pp.1700-1701.
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Jackson, P. (2015) Management and business research. 5th ed. Sage Publications Ltd.
- Erdoğan, N. and Esen, M. (2011) An Investigation of the Effects of Technology Readiness on Technology Acceptance in e-HRM. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.24, pp.487-495.
- Ermakova, Tatiana & Fabian, Benjamin & Baumann, Annika & Izmailov, Mykyta & Krasnova, Hanna. (2017). Bitcoin: Drivers and Impediments. SSRN Electronic Journal. Available: 10.2139/ssrn.3017190.
- Escalas, J. and Bettman, J. (2003) You Are What They Eat: The Influence of Reference Groups on Consumers' Connections to Brands. Journal of Consumer Psychology. Vol.13 (3), pp.339-348.
- ESRC (2018) Our core principles - Economic and Social Research Council. [Online]. Available: <https://esrc.ukri.org/funding/guidance-for-applicants/research-ethics/our-core-principles/> [Accessed 23 May 2021].
- EY (2021) Unleashing cryptocurrency potential – four ways to increase institutional adoption. [Online] Available: https://www.ey.com/en_nl/banking-capital-markets/unleashing-cryptocurrency-potential-4-ways-to-increase-institutional-adoption [Accessed 23 May 2022].
- Fairley, P. (2019) Ethereum will cut back its absurd energy use. IEEE Spectrum. Vol.56 (1), pp.29–32.
- Fam, K., Foscht, T. and Collins, R. (2004) Trust and the online relationship—an exploratory study from New Zealand. Tourism Management. Vol.25 (2), pp.195-207.

- Faqih, K. (2016) An empirical analysis of factors predicting the behavioral intention to adopt Internet shopping technology among non-shoppers in a developing country context: Does gender matter?. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. Vol.30, pp.140-164.
- Featherman, M. and Pavlou, P. (2003) Predicting e-services adoption: a perceived risk facets perspective. International Journal of Human-Computer Studies. Vol.59 (4), pp.451-474.
- Featherman, M., Miyazaki, A. and Sprott, D. (2010) Reducing online privacy risk to facilitate e-service adoption: the influence of perceived ease of use and corporate credibility. Journal of Services Marketing. Vol.24 (3), pp.219-229.
- Ferrin, D. L. and Dirks, K. T. (2003) The Use of Rewards to Increase and Decrease Trust: Mediating Processes and Differential Effects. Organization Science. Vol.14 (1), pp.18–31.
- Field, A. (2013) Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics. SAGE Publications.
- Finklea, K. (2017) Dark Web. U.S. Congressional Research Service. No. R44101.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Folkinshteyn, D. and Lennon, M. (2016) Braving Bitcoin: A technology acceptance model (TAM) analysis. Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research. Vol.18 (4), pp.220-249.
- Fornell, C. and Larcker, D. (1981) Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. Journal of Marketing Research. Vol.18 (1), pp.39-50.
- Fowler, F. (2013) Survey research methods. 5th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Franklin, M. (2012) Understanding research: coping with the quantitative - qualitative divide. New York: Routledge.

- French, D., Sutton, S., Hennings, S., Mitchell, J., Wareham, N., Griffin, S., Hardeman, W. and Kinmonth, A. (2005) The Importance of Affective Beliefs and Attitudes in the Theory of Planned Behavior: Predicting Intention to Increase Physical Activity1. Journal of Applied Social Psychology. Vol.35 (9), pp.1824-1848.
- Freud, S. (1923) The Ego And The Id (1923). TACD Journal. Vol.17 (1), pp.5-22.
- Gagnon, M., Orruño, E., Asua, J., Abdeljelil, A. and Emparanza, J. (2012) Using a Modified Technology Acceptance Model to Evaluate Healthcare Professionals' Adoption of a New Telemonitoring System. Telemedicine and e-Health. Vol.18 (1), pp.54-59.
- Gao, X., Clark, G. and Lindqvist, J. (2016) Of Two Minds, Multiple Addresses, and One Ledger. Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. pp.1656-1668.
- Gazali, H., Ismail, C. and Amboala, T. (2018) Exploring the Intention to Invest in Cryptocurrency: The Case of Bitcoin. 2018 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology for the Muslim World (ICT4M). pp.64-68.
- Gefen, D. (2002) Customer Loyalty in E-Commerce. Journal of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.3 (1), pp.27–51. Available: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1197&context=jais> [Accessed 22 May 2022].
- Gefen, D. and Straub, D. (2000) The Relative Importance of Perceived Ease of Use in IS Adoption: A Study of E-Commerce Adoption. Journal of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.1 (1), pp.1-30.
- Gefen, D., Karahanna, E. and Straub, D. W. (2003) Trust and TAM in Online Shopping: An Integrated Model. MIS Quarterly. Vol.27 (1), pp.51–90.
- Gencer, A. E., Basu, S., Eyal, I., van Renesse, R. and Sirer, E. G. (2018) Decentralization in Bitcoin and Ethereum Networks. In: Meiklejohn, S. and Sako, K. (eds.). Financial Cryptography and Data Security. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin

Heidelberg, pp.439–457. Available: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-662-58387-6_24 [Accessed 22 May 2022].

- George Saadé, R. and Kira, D. (2006) The Emotional State of Technology Acceptance. Issues in Informing Science and Information Technology. Vol.3, pp.529-539.
- George, J. (2002) Influences on the intent to make Internet purchases. Internet Research. Vol.12 (2), pp.165-180.
- Gerbing, D. and Anderson, J. (1988) An Updated Paradigm for Scale Development Incorporating Unidimensionality and Its Assessment. Journal of Marketing Research. Vol.25 (2), pp.186-192.
- Gervais, A., Karame, G. O., Capkun, V. and Capkun, S. (2014) Is Bitcoin a Decentralized Currency? IEEE Security & Privacy. Vol.12 (3), pp.54–60.
- Ghasemi, A. and Zahediasl, S. (2012) Normality Tests for Statistical Analysis: A Guide for Non-Statisticians. International Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism. Vol.10 (2), pp.486-489.
- Ghimire, S. and Selvaraj, H. (2018) A Survey on Bitcoin Cryptocurrency and its Mining. In: 2018 26th International Conference on Systems Engineering (ICSEng)., pp.1–6.
- Giovanis, A., Binioris, S. and Polychronopoulos, G. (2012) An extension of TAM model with IDT and security/privacy risk in the adoption of internet banking services in Greece. EuroMed Journal of Business. Vol.7 (1), pp.24-53.
- Giudici, G., Milne, A. and Vinogradov, D. (2019) Cryptocurrencies: market analysis and perspectives. Journal of Industrial and Business Economics. Vol.47 (1), pp.1-18.
- Glaser, F., Zimmermann, K., Haferkorn, M., Weber, M. C. and Siering, M. (2014) Bitcoin - Asset or Currency? Revealing Users' Hidden Intentions [Online]. Rochester,

NY: Social Science Research Network. SSRN Scholarly Paper No. ID 2425247.

Available: <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2425247>.

- Glomann, L., Schmid, M. and Kitajewa, N. (2019) Improving the Blockchain User Experience - An Approach to Address Blockchain Mass Adoption Issues from a Human-Centred Perspective. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing. Vol.965, pp.608-616.
- Gonzalez, D. (2015) Chapter 8 - Currency and Campaigns. In: Gonzalez, D. (ed.). Managing Online Risk. Boston: Butterworth-Heinemann, pp.185–211.
- Goodhue, D. and Thompson, R. (1995) Task-Technology Fit and Individual Performance. MIS Quarterly. Vol.19 (2), pp.213-236.
- Grabner-Kraeuter, S. (2002) The Role of Consumers' Trust in Online-Shopping. Journal of Business Ethics. Vol.39 (1/2), pp.43-50.
- Grant, G. and Hogan, R. (2015) Bitcoin: Risks and Controls. Journal of Corporate Accounting & Finance. Vol.26 (5), pp.29-35.
- Gray, D. (2008) Doing research in the real world. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Griethuijsen, R., Eijck, M., Haste, H., Brok, P., Skinner, N., Mansour, N., Gencer, A. and BouJaoude, S. (2014) Global Patterns in Students' Views of Science and Interest in Science. Research in Science Education. Vol.45 (4), pp.581-603.
- Grinberg, R. (2011) Bitcoin: An Innovative Alternative Digital Currency. Hastings Science & Technology Law Journal. Vol.4 (1), pp.159-208.
- Grover, P., Kar, A., Janssen, M. and Ilavarasan, P. (2019) Perceived usefulness, ease of use and user acceptance of blockchain technology for digital transactions – insights from user-generated content on Twitter. Enterprise Information Systems. Vol.13 (6), pp.771-800.
- Guadamuz, A. and Marsden, C. (2015) Blockchains and Bitcoin: Regulatory responses to cryptocurrencies. First Monday. [Online]. Available:

<https://firstmonday.org/ojs/index.php/fm/article/view/6198>. [Accessed 23 May 2022].

- Gunawan, F. and Novendra, R. (2017) An Analysis of Bitcoin Acceptance in Indonesia. ComTech: Computer, Mathematics and Engineering Applications. Vol.8 (4), pp.241-247.
- Guo, X., Sun, Y., Wang, N., Peng, Z. and Yan, Z. (2012) The dark side of elderly acceptance of preventive mobile health services in China. Electronic Markets. Vol.23 (1), pp.49-61.
- Ha, S. and Stoel, L. (2009) Consumer e-shopping acceptance: Antecedents in a technology acceptance model. Journal of Business Research. Vol.62 (5), pp.565-571.
- Hackbarth, G., Grover, V. and Yi, M. (2003) Computer playfulness and anxiety: positive and negative mediators of the system experience effect on perceived ease of use. Information & Management. Vol.40 (3), pp.221-232.
- Haddouti, S. and Kettani, M. (2019) Analysis of Identity Management Systems Using Blockchain Technology. 2019 International Conference on Advanced Communication Technologies and Networking (CommNet). pp.1-7.
- Haenlein, M. and Kaplan, A. (2004) A Beginner's Guide to Partial Least Squares Analysis. Understanding Statistics. Vol.3 (4), pp.283-297.
- Haferkorn, M. and Quintana Diaz, J. M. (2015) Seasonality and Interconnectivity Within Cryptocurrencies - An Analysis on the Basis of Bitcoin, Litecoin and Namecoin. In: Lugmayr, A. (ed.). Enterprise Applications and Services in the Finance Industry. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp.106–120.
- Hair, J., Babin, B. and Krey, N. (2017) Covariance-Based Structural Equation Modeling in the Journal of Advertising: Review and Recommendations. Journal of Advertising. Vol.46 (1), pp.163-177.

- Hair, J., Black, B., Babin, B. and Anderson, R. (2010) Multivariate Data Analysis: A Global Perspective. 7th ed. London: Pearson.
- Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B. and Anderson, R. (2019) Multivariate data analysis. 8th ed. Andover, Hampshire: Cengage.
- Hair, J., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. and Mena, J. (2011) An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. Vol.40 (3), pp.414-433.
- Hamilton, P. (1992) Talcott Parsons: critical assessments (Vol. 1). Taylor & Francis.
- Hancock, G. and Mueller, R. (2018) The reviewer's guide to quantitative methods in the social sciences. New York: Routledge.
- Hansen, J., Saridakis, G. and Benson, V. (2018) Risk, trust, and the interaction of perceived ease of use and behavioral control in predicting consumers' use of social media for transactions. Computers in Human Behavior. Vol.80, pp.197-206.
- Härdle, W., Harvey, C. and Reule, R. (2020) Understanding Cryptocurrencies. Journal of Financial Econometrics. Vol.18 (2), pp.181-208.
- Hattie, J. (1985) Methodology Review: Assessing Unidimensionality of Tests and Items. Applied Psychological Measurement. Vol.9 (2), pp.139-164.
- Hawkins, D. I. and Mothersbaugh, D. L. (2010) Consumer behavior: building marketing strategy. 11th ed. Boston: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Hayes, A., Montoya, A. and Rockwood, N. (2017) The Analysis of Mechanisms and Their Contingencies: PROCESS versus Structural Equation Modeling. Australasian Marketing Journal. Vol.25 (1), pp.76-81.
- Heale, R. and Twycross, A. (2015) Validity and reliability in quantitative studies. Evidence Based Nursing. Vol.18 (3), pp.66-67.

- Heinssen, R., Glass, C. and Knight, L. (1987) Assessing computer anxiety: Development and validation of the Computer Anxiety Rating Scale. Computers in Human Behavior. Vol.3 (1), pp.49-59.
- Hjalmarsson, F., Hreioarsson, G., Hamdaqa, M. and Hjalmtysson, G. (2018) Blockchain-Based E-Voting System. 2018 IEEE 11th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD). pp.983-986.
- Holden, H. and Rada, R. (2011) Understanding the Influence of Perceived Usability and Technology Self-Efficacy on Teachers' Technology Acceptance. Journal of Research on Technology in Education. Vol.43 (4), pp.343-367.
- Holden, R. and Karsh, B. (2010) The Technology Acceptance Model: Its past and its future in health care. Journal of Biomedical Informatics. Vol.43 (1), pp.159-172.
- Holub, M. and Johnson, J. (2018) Bitcoin research across disciplines. The Information Society. Vol.34 (2), pp.114-126.
- Hong, I. (2018) Social and Personal Dimensions as Predictors of Sustainable Intention to Use Facebook in Korea: An Empirical Analysis. Sustainability. Vol.10 (8), article no: 2856.
- Hong, S., Thong, J. and Tam, K. (2006) Understanding continued information technology usage behavior: A comparison of three models in the context of mobile internet. Decision Support Systems. Vol.42 (3), pp.1819-1834.
- Hong, Z. and Yi, L. (2012) Research on the Influence of Perceived Risk in Consumer On-line Purchasing Decision. Physics Procedia. Vol.24, pp.1304–1310.
- Hsu, C., Wang, C. and Lin, J. (2011) Investigating customer adoption behaviours in Mobile Financial Services. International Journal of Mobile Communications. Vol.9 (5), pp.477-494.

- Hu, L. and Bentler, P. (1999) Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal. Vol.6 (1), pp.1-55.
- Hu, Z., Ding, S., Li, S., Chen, L. and Yang, S. (2019) Adoption Intention of Fintech Services for Bank Users: An Empirical Examination with an Extended Technology Acceptance Model. Symmetry. Vol.11 (3), article no: 340.
- Hudson, L. and Ozanne, J. (1988) Alternative Ways of Seeking Knowledge in Consumer Research. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.14 (4), pp.508-521.
- Hussein, Z. (2017) Leading to Intention: The Role of Attitude in Relation to Technology Acceptance Model in E-Learning. Procedia Computer Science. Vol.105, pp.159-164.
- Im, I., Kim, Y. and Han, H. (2008) The effects of perceived risk and technology type on users' acceptance of technologies. Information & Management. Vol.45 (1), pp.1-9.
- Inci, A. and Lagasse, R. (2019) Cryptocurrencies: applications and investment opportunities. Journal of Capital Markets Studies. Vol.3 (2), pp.98-112.
- Ionescu, R. and Rădulescu, I. (2019) Behavioral Finance and the Fast Evolving World of Fintech. Economic Insights – Trends and Challenges. Vol.4, pp.47-57.
- Iqbal, N., Fareed, Z., Wan, G. and Shahzad, F. (2021) Asymmetric nexus between COVID-19 outbreak in the world and cryptocurrency market. International Review of Financial Analysis. Vol.73, article no: 101613.
- Irani, Z., Dwivedi, Y. and Williams, M. (2009) Understanding consumer adoption of broadband: an extension of the technology acceptance model. Journal of the Operational Research Society. Vol.60 (10), pp.1322-1334.
- J Walton, A. and A. Johnston, K. (2018) Exploring Perceptions of Bitcoin Adoption: The South African Virtual Community Perspective. Interdisciplinary Journal of Information, Knowledge, and Management. Vol.13, pp.165-182.

- Jabotinsky, H. Y. and Sarel, R. (2020) How Crisis Affects Crypto: Coronavirus as a Test Case [Online]. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. SSRN Scholarly Paper No. ID 3557929. Available: <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3557929>
- Jackson, J., Yi, M. and Park, J. (2013) An empirical test of three mediation models for the relationship between personal innovativeness and user acceptance of technology. Information & Management. Vol.50 (4), pp.154-161.
- Jang, H., Han, S., Kim, J. and Kwon, K. (2020) Identifying and Improving Usability Problems of Cryptocurrency Exchange Mobile Applications Through Heuristic Evaluation. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing. pp.15-21.
- Janssens, W., Wijnen, K., Pelsmacker, P. and Kenhove, P. (2009) Marketing research with SPSS. Harlow, England: Prentice Hall/Financial Times Publications.
- Jarvenpaa, S. L. and Todd, P. A. (1996) Consumer Reactions to Electronic Shopping on the World Wide Web. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.1 (2), pp.59–88.
- Jarvenpaa, S., Tractinsky, N. and Vitale, M. (2000) Consumer trust in an Internet store. Information Technology And Management. Vol.1 (1), pp.45-71.
- Johnson, V., Kiser, A., Washington, R. and Torres, R. (2018) Limitations to the rapid adoption of M-payment services: Understanding the impact of privacy risk on M-Payment services. Computers in Human Behavior. Vol.79, pp.111-122.
- Jokić, S., Cvetković, A., Adamović, S., Ristić, N. and Spalević, P. (2019) Comparative analysis of cryptocurrency wallets vs traditional wallets. Ekonomika. Vol.65 (3), pp.65–75.
- Jonker, N. (2019) What drives the adoption of crypto-payments by online retailers?. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. Vol.35, article no: 100848.

- Jöreskog, K. (1969) A general approach to confirmatory maximum likelihood factor analysis. Psychometrika. Vol.34 (2), pp.183-202.
- Juels, A., Kosba, A. and Shi, E. (2016) The Ring of Gyges. Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security. pp. 283-295.
- Jung, K., Park, J., Phan, N., Bo, C. and Gim, G. (2018) An International Comparative Study on the Intension to Using Crypto-Currency. Applied Computing and Information Technology. Vol.788, pp.104-123.
- Kang, I. and Ma, I. (2020) A Study on Bandwagon Consumption Behavior Based on Fear of Missing Out and Product Characteristics. Sustainability. Vol.12 (6), article no: 2441.
- Kastanakis, M. N. and Balabanis, G. (2012) Between the mass and the class: Antecedents of the “bandwagon” luxury consumption behavior. Journal of Business Research. Vol.65 (10), pp.1399–1407.
- Keil, M., Beranek, P. and Konsynski, B. (1995) Usefulness and ease of use: field study evidence regarding task considerations. Decision Support Systems. Vol.13 (1), pp.75-91.
- Kethineni, S. and Cao, Y. (2019) The Rise in Popularity of Cryptocurrency and Associated Criminal Activity. International Criminal Justice Review. Vol.30 (3), pp.325-344.
- Khan, S., Loukil, F., Ghedira-Guegan, C., Benkhelifa, E. and Bani-Hani, A. (2021) Blockchain smart contracts: Applications, challenges, and future trends. Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications. Vol.14, pp.2901-2925.
- Kickul, J. and Gundry, L. (2002) Prospecting for Strategic Advantage: The Proactive Entrepreneurial Personality and Small Firm Innovation. Journal of Small Business Management. Vol.40 (2), pp.85–97.

- Kim, D., Ferrin, D. and Rao, H. (2008) A trust-based consumer decision-making model in electronic commerce: The role of trust, perceived risk, and their antecedents. Decision Support Systems. Vol.44 (2), pp.544-564.
- Kim, H. (2013) Statistical notes for clinical researchers: assessing normal distribution (2) using skewness and kurtosis. Restorative Dentistry & Endodontics. Vol.38 (1), pp.52-54.
- Kim, H., Hong, J., Hwang, H., Kim, S. and Han, D. (2020) Comparison of Psychological Status and Investment Style Between Bitcoin Investors and Share Investors. Frontiers in Psychology. Vol.11, article no: 502295.
- Kim, M. (2021) A psychological approach to Bitcoin usage behavior in the era of COVID-19: Focusing on the role of attitudes toward money. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. Vol.62, article no: 102606.
- Kim, M.-J., Chung, N. and Lee, C.-K. (2011) The effect of perceived trust on electronic commerce: Shopping online for tourism products and services in South Korea. Tourism Management. Vol.32 (2), pp.256–265.
- Kim, S. K., Ma, Z., Murali, S., Mason, J., Miller, A. and Bailey, M. (2018) Measuring Ethereum Network Peers. In: Proceedings of the Internet Measurement Conference 2018. Presented at the IMC '18: Internet Measurement Conference, Boston MA USA: ACM, pp.91–104.
- Kim, Y., Chun, J. and Song, J. (2009) Investigating the role of attitude in technology acceptance from an attitude strength perspective. International Journal of Information Management. Vol.29 (1), pp.67-77.
- King, W. R. and He, J. (2006) A meta-analysis of the technology acceptance model. Information & Management. Vol.43 (6), pp.740–755.
- Kline, P. (1994) An Easy Guide to Factor Analysis. 1st ed. London: Routledge.
- Kline, R. (2011) Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling, Third Edition. 3rd ed. New York: Guilford Publications.

- Kline, R. (2015) Principles and practice of structural equation modeling. New York: Guilford Press.
- Koutmos, D. and Payne, J. (2020) Intertemporal asset pricing with bitcoin. Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting. Vol.56 (2), pp.619-645.
- Krause, M. and Tolaymat, T. (2018) Quantification of energy and carbon costs for mining cryptocurrencies. Nature Sustainability. Vol.1 (11), pp.711-718.
- Krejcie, R. and Morgan, D. (1970) Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. Educational and Psychological Measurement. Vol.30 (3), pp.607-610.
- Kristoufek, L. (2015) What Are the Main Drivers of the Bitcoin Price? Evidence from Wavelet Coherence Analysis. PLOS ONE. Vol.10 (4), article no: e0123923.
- Krombholz, K., Judmayer, A., Gusenbauer, M. and Weippl, E. (2017) The Other Side of the Coin: User Experiences with Bitcoin Security and Privacy. Financial Cryptography and Data Security. pp.555-580.
- Kulviwat, S., Bruner II, G., Kumar, A., Nasco, S. and Clark, T. (2007) Toward a unified theory of consumer acceptance technology. Psychology and Marketing. Vol.24 (12), pp.1059-1084.
- Kuo Chuen, D., Guo, L. and Wang, Y. (2017) Cryptocurrency: A New Investment Opportunity?. The Journal of Alternative Investments. Vol.20 (3), pp.16-40.
- Lahmiri, S. and Bekiros, S. (2020) The impact of COVID-19 pandemic upon stability and sequential irregularity of equity and cryptocurrency markets. Chaos, Solitons, and Fractals. Vol.138, article no: 109936.
- Lam, S., Chiang, J. and Parasuraman, A. (2008) The effects of the dimensions of technology readiness on technology acceptance: An empirical analysis. Journal of Interactive Marketing. Vol.22 (4), pp.19-39.

- Laroche, M., McDougall, G. H. G., Bergeron, J. and Yang, Z. (2004) Exploring How Intangibility Affects Perceived Risk. Journal of Service Research. Vol.6 (4), pp.373–389.
- Laros, F. J. M. and Steenkamp, J.-B. E. M. (2005) Emotions in consumer behavior: a hierarchical approach. Journal of Business Research. Vol.58 (10), pp.1437–1445.
- Lee, A. (1991) Integrating Positivist and Interpretive Approaches to Organizational Research. Organization Science. Vol.2 (4), pp.342-365.
- Lee, C., Warkentin, M. and Choi, H. (2004) The Role of Technological and Social Factors on the Adoption of Mobile Payment Technologies. AMCIS 2004 Proceedings. Vol.3, pp.2781-2786.
- Lee, J. (2019) A decentralized token economy: How blockchain and cryptocurrency can revolutionize business. Business Horizons. Vol.62 (6), pp.773-784.
- Lee, M. (2009) Understanding the behavioural intention to play online games. Online Information Review. Vol.33 (5), pp.849-872.
- Lee, M. K. O. and Turban, E. (2001) A Trust Model for Consumer Internet Shopping. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.6 (1), pp.75–91.
- Lee, M.-C. (2009) Factors influencing the adoption of internet banking: An integration of TAM and TPB with perceived risk and perceived benefit. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. Vol.8 (3), pp.130–141.
- Lee, W., Lin, C. and Shih, K. (2018) A technology acceptance model for the perception of restaurant service robots for trust, interactivity, and output quality. International Journal of Mobile Communications. Vol.16 (4), p.361.
- Lee, Y., Kozar, K. and Larsen, K. (2003) The Technology Acceptance Model: Past, Present, and Future. Communications of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.12(50), pp.752-780.

- Legris, P., Ingham, J. and Colletette, P. (2003) Why do people use information technology? A critical review of the technology acceptance model. Information & Management. Vol.40 (3), pp.191–204.
- Leibenstein, H. (1950) Bandwagon, Snob, and Veblen Effects in the Theory of Consumers' Demand. The Quarterly Journal of Economics. Vol.64 (2), pp.183-207.
- Leone, L., Perugini, M. and Ercolani, A. (1999) A comparison of three models of attitude-behavior relationships in the studying behavior domain. European Journal of Social Psychology. Vol.29 (2-3), pp.161-189.
- Lewis, Agarwal and Sambamurthy (2003) Sources of Influence on Beliefs about Information Technology Use: An Empirical Study of Knowledge Workers. MIS Quarterly. Vol.27 (4), pp.657-678.
- Li, J., Li, N., Peng, J., Cui, H. and Wu, Z. (2019) Energy consumption of cryptocurrency mining: A study of electricity consumption in mining cryptocurrencies. Energy. Vol.168, pp.160–168.
- Li, Y. and Huang, J. (2009) Applying Theory of Perceived Risk and Technology Acceptance Model in the Online Shopping Channel. World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, International Journal of Social, Behavioral, Educational, Economic, Business and Industrial Engineering. Vol.3, pp.505-511.
- Lim, N. (2003) Consumers' perceived risk: sources versus consequences. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. Vol.2 (3), pp.216–228.
- Lo, H. and Weng, R. (2012) Bandwagon and new technology adoption in hospital industry: The moderating roles of positive performance experience and technology investment similarity. AFRICAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT. Vol.6 (27), pp.7987-7994.
- Lortie, J. and Castogiovanni, G. (2015) The theory of planned behavior in entrepreneurship research: what we know and future directions. International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal. Vol.11 (4), pp.935-957.

- Low, K. and Teo, E. (2018) Legal Risks of Owning Cryptocurrencies. Handbook of Blockchain, Digital Finance, and Inclusion, Volume 1. pp.225-247.
- Lu, J. (2014) Are personal innovativeness and social influence critical to continue with mobile commerce?. Internet Research. Vol.24 (2), pp.134-159.
- Lu, J., Yao, J. and Yu, C. (2005) Personal innovativeness, social influences and adoption of wireless Internet services via mobile technology. The Journal of Strategic Information Systems. Vol.14 (3), pp.245-268.
- Lu, Y., Zhao, L. and Wang, B. (2010) From virtual community members to C2C e-commerce buyers: Trust in virtual communities and its effect on consumers' purchase intention. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. Vol.9 (4), pp.346–360.
- Luhmann, N. (1979) Trust and power. Chichester, England: Wiley.
- Lyon, F., Möllering, G. and Saunders, M. (2012) Handbook of research methods on trust. Northampton, Mass.: Edward Elgar Publications.
- Ma, Y., Gam, H. and Banning, J. (2017) Perceived ease of use and usefulness of sustainability labels on apparel products: application of the technology acceptance model. Fashion and Textiles. Vol.4 (3), pp.1-20.
- Madden, T., Ellen, P. and Ajzen, I. (1992) A Comparison of the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Theory of Reasoned Action. Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin. Vol.18 (1), pp.3-9.
- Maditinos, D., Chatzoudes, D. and Sarigiannidis, L. (2013) An examination of the critical factors affecting consumer acceptance of online banking: A focus on the dimensions of risk. Journal of Systems and Information Technology. Vol.15 (1), pp.97–116.
- Malhotra, N. (2010) Marketing Research: An Applied Orientation. 6th ed. Pearson Education Limited.

- Manis, K. and Choi, D. (2019) The virtual reality hardware acceptance model (VR-HAM): Extending and individuating the technology acceptance model (TAM) for virtual reality hardware. Journal of Business Research. Vol.100, pp.503-513.
- Marangunić, N. and Granić, A. (2014) Technology acceptance model: a literature review from 1986 to 2013. Universal Access in the Information Society. Vol.14 (1), pp.81-95.
- Marella, V., Upreti, B., Merikivi, J. and Tuunainen, V. (2020) Understanding the creation of trust in cryptocurrencies: the case of Bitcoin. Electronic Markets. Vol.30 (2), pp.259-271.
- Martínez-López, F., Gázquez-Abad, J. and Sousa, C. (2013) Structural equation modelling in marketing and business research. European Journal of Marketing. Vol.47 (1/2), pp.115-152.
- Martins, C., Oliveira, T. and Popovič, A. (2014) Understanding the Internet banking adoption: A unified theory of acceptance and use of technology and perceived risk application. International Journal of Information Management. Vol.34 (1), pp.1-13.
- Mathieson, K. (1991) Predicting User Intentions: Comparing the Technology Acceptance Model with the Theory of Planned Behavior. Information Systems Research. Vol.2 (3), pp.173-191.
- Mayer, R., Davis, J. and Schoorman, F. (1995) An Integrative Model Of Organizational Trust. Academy of Management Review. Vol.20 (3), pp.709-734.
- Mazambani, L. and Mutambara, E. (2019) Predicting FinTech innovation adoption in South Africa: the case of cryptocurrency. African Journal of Economic and Management Studies. Vol.11 (1), pp.30-50.
- McCloskey, D. (2006) The Importance of Ease of Use, Usefulness, and Trust to Online Consumers. Journal of Organizational and End User Computing. Vol.18 (3), pp.47-65.

- McGartland Rubio, D., Berg-Weger, M. and Tebb, S. (2001) Using Structural Equation Modeling to Test for Multidimensionality. Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal. Vol.8 (4), pp.613-626.
- McGuire, W. J. (1976) Some Internal Psychological Factors Influencing Consumer Choice. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.2 (4), pp.302-319.
- Mendoza-Tello, J. C., Mora, H., Pujol-López, F. A. and Lytras, M. D. (2018) Social Commerce as a Driver to Enhance Trust and Intention to Use Cryptocurrencies for Electronic Payments. IEEE Access. Vol.6, pp.50737–50751.
- Mendoza-Tello, J., Mora, H., Pujol-López, F. and Lytras, M. (2019) Disruptive innovation of cryptocurrencies in consumer acceptance and trust. Information Systems and e-Business Management. Vol.17 (2-4), pp.195-222.
- Mettler, M. (2016) Blockchain technology in healthcare: The revolution starts here. 2016 IEEE 18th International Conference on e-Health Networking, Applications and Services (Healthcom). pp.1-3.
- Midgley, D. and Dowling, G. (1978) Innovativeness: The Concept and Its Measurement. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.4 (4), pp.229-242.
- Miglietti, C., Kubosova, Z. and Skulanova, N. (2019) Bitcoin, Litecoin, and the Euro: an annualized volatility analysis. Studies in Economics and Finance. Vol.37 (2), pp.229–242.
- Miller, P. (2016) The cryptocurrency enigma. Digital Forensics. pp.1-25.
- Mitchell, V. (1999) Consumer perceived risk: conceptualisations and models. European Journal of Marketing. Vol.33 (1/2), pp.163–195.
- Mohanta, B., Jena, D., Panda, S. and Sobhanayak, S. (2019) Blockchain technology: A survey on applications and security privacy Challenges. Internet of Things. Vol.8, article no: 100107.

- Moore, G. C. and Benbasat, I. (1991) Development of an Instrument to Measure the Perceptions of Adopting an Information Technology Innovation. Information Systems Research. Vol.2 (3), pp.192–222.
- Moore, T. and Christin, N. (2013) Beware the Middleman: Empirical Analysis of Bitcoin-Exchange Risk. In: Sadeghi, A.-R. (ed.). Financial Cryptography and Data Security. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, pp.25–33.
- Moorman, C., Deshpande, R. and Zaltman, G. (1993) Factors Affecting Trust in Market Research Relationships. Journal of Marketing. Vol.57 (1), pp.81-101.
- Mora, H., Mendoza-Tello, J., Pujol-Lopez, F. and Lytras, M. (2018) Social Commerce as a Driver to Enhance Trust and Intention to Use Cryptocurrencies for Electronic Payments. IEEE Access. Vol.6, pp.50737-50751.
- Moser, C. and Kalton, G. (1985) Survey methods in social investigation. New York: Routledge.
- Möser, M. and Böhme, R. (2015) Trends, Tips, Tolls: A Longitudinal Study of Bitcoin Transaction Fees. In: Brenner, M., Christin, N., Johnson, B., and Rohloff, K. (eds.). Financial Cryptography and Data Security. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, pp.19–33.
- Moser, M., Bohme, R. and Breuker, D. (2013) An inquiry into money laundering tools in the Bitcoin ecosystem. 2013 APWG eCrime Researchers Summit. pp.1-14.
- Mukherjee, A. and Nath, P. (2003) A model of trust in online relationship banking. International Journal of Bank Marketing. Vol.21 (1), pp.5-15.
- Mukherjee, A. and Nath, P. (2007) Role of electronic trust in online retailing. European Journal of Marketing. Vol.41 (9/10), pp.1173-1202.
- Mukhopadhyay, U., Skjellum, A., Hambolu, O., Oakley, J., Yu, L. and Brooks, R. (2016) A brief survey of Cryptocurrency systems. 2016 14th Annual Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust (PST). Vol.11 (1), pp.76-82.

- Murphy, H. and Rottet, D. (2009) An exploration of the key hotel processes implicated in biometric adoption. International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management. Vol.21 (2), pp.201-212.
- Musa, P. F. (2006) Making a case for modifying the technology acceptance model to account for limited accessibility in developing countries. Information Technology for Development. Vol.12 (3), pp.213–224.
- Nadeem, M., Liu, Z., Pitafi, A., Younis, A. and Xu, Y. (2021) Investigating the Adoption Factors of Cryptocurrencies—A Case of Bitcoin: Empirical Evidence from China. SAGE Open. Vol.11 (1), pp.1-15.
- Naeem, M., Mbarki, I. and Shahzad, S. (2021) Predictive role of online investor sentiment for cryptocurrency market: Evidence from happiness and fears. International Review of Economics & Finance. Vol.73, pp.496-514.
- Nakamoto, S., 2008. Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system. Decentralized Business Review, article no: 21260.
- Natarajan, H., Krause, S. and Gradstein, H. (2017) Distributed Ledger Technology and Blockchain [Online]. World Bank, Washington, DC. Available: <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/29053> [Accessed 12 May 2022].
- Navazio, R. (1977) An Experimental Approach to Bandwagon Research. Public Opinion Quarterly. Vol.41 (2), pp.217-225.
- Nelms, T., Maurer, B., Swartz, L. and Mainwaring, S. (2017) Social Payments: Innovation, Trust, Bitcoin, and the Sharing Economy. Theory, Culture & Society. Vol.35 (3), pp.13-33.
- Netemeyer, R., Sharma, S. and Bearden, W. (2003) Scaling procedures. Thousand Oaks: Sage.

- Nguyen, C., Hoang, D., Nguyen, D., Niyato, D., Nguyen, H. and Dutkiewicz, E. (2019) Proof-of-Stake Consensus Mechanisms for Future Blockchain Networks: Fundamentals, Applications and Opportunities. IEEE Access. Vol.7, pp.85727-85745.
- Novikov, A. (2018) LEGAL REGULATION OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES AND APPLICABLE RISKS. EUREKA: Social and Humanities. Vol.4, pp.32-35.
- Nunnally, J. (1978) Psychometric theory. New York: McGraw-Hill Book.
- Nuryyev, G., Wang, Y., Achyldurdyeva, J., Jaw, B., Yeh, Y., Lin, H. and Wu, L. (2020) Blockchain Technology Adoption Behavior and Sustainability of the Business in Tourism and Hospitality SMEs: An Empirical Study. Sustainability. Vol.12 (3), article no: 1256.
- Ogden, J. (2003) Some problems with social cognition models: A pragmatic and conceptual analysis. Health Psychology. Vol.22 (4), pp.424-428.
- Oh, S., Ahn, J. and Kim, B. (2003) Adoption of Broadband Internet in Korea: The Role of Experience in Building Attitudes. Journal of Information Technology. Vol.18 (4), pp.267-280.
- Orlikowski, W. and Baroudi, J. (1991) Studying Information Technology in Organizations: Research Approaches and Assumptions. Information Systems Research. Vol.2 (1), pp.1-28.
- Otieno, O. C., Liyala, S., Odongo, B. C. and Abeka, S. (2016) Theory of Reasoned Action as an Underpinning to Technological Innovation Adoption Studies. World Journal of Computer Application and Technology. Vol.4 (1), pp.1–7.
- Özbek, V., Alniaçık, Ü., Koc, F., Akkılıç, M. and Kaş, E. (2014) The Impact of Personality on Technology Acceptance: A Study on Smart Phone Users. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.150, pp.541-551.
- Pachauri, M. (2001) Consumer Behaviour: a Literature Review. The Marketing Review. Vol.2 (3), pp.319–355.

- Parasuraman, A. (2000) Technology Readiness Index (Tri). Journal of Service Research. Vol.2 (4), pp.307-320.
- Parasuraman, S. and Igarria, M. (1990) An examination of gender differences in the determinants of computer anxiety and attitudes toward microcomputers among managers. International Journal of Man-Machine Studies. Vol.32 (3), pp.327-340.
- Park, C., Kim, H. and Kim, Y. (2014) A study of factors enhancing smart grid consumer engagement. Energy Policy. Vol.72, pp.211-218.
- Park, E. and Kim, K. (2014) An Integrated Adoption Model of Mobile Cloud Services: Exploration of Key Determinants and Extension of Technology Acceptance Model. Telematics and Informatics. Vol.31 (3), pp.376-385.
- Park, Y., Konge, L. and Artino, A. (2020) The Positivism Paradigm of Research. Academic Medicine. Vol.95 (5), pp.690-694.
- Patil, P., Tamilmani, K., Rana, N. and Raghavan, V. (2020) Understanding consumer adoption of mobile payment in India: Extending Meta-UTAUT model with personal innovativeness, anxiety, trust, and grievance redressal. International Journal of Information Management. Vol.54, p.102144.
- Paul, J., Modi, A. and Patel, J. (2016) Predicting green product consumption using theory of planned behavior and reasoned action. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. Vol.29, pp.123-134.
- Pavlou, P. A. (2003) Consumer Acceptance of Electronic Commerce: Integrating Trust and Risk with the Technology Acceptance Model. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.7 (3), pp.101–134.
- Pavlou, P. and Fygenson, M. (2006) Understanding and Predicting Electronic Commerce Adoption: An Extension of the Theory of Planned Behavior. MIS Quarterly. Vol.30 (1), pp.115-143.

- Peter, J. and Ryan, M. (1976) An Investigation of Perceived Risk at the Brand Level. Journal of Marketing Research. Vol.13 (2), pp.184-188.
- Phares, E. and Chaplin, W. (1997) Introduction to personality. New York: Longman.
- Phillip, A., Chan, J. S. K. and Peiris, S. (2018) A new look at Cryptocurrencies. Economics Letters. Vol.163, pp.6–9.
- Plouffe, C., Hulland, J. and Vandenbosch, M. (2001) Research Report: Richness Versus Parsimony in Modeling Technology Adoption Decisions—Understanding Merchant Adoption of a Smart Card-Based Payment System. Information Systems Research. Vol.12 (2), pp.208-222.
- Polasik, M., Piotrowska, A., Wisniewski, T., Kotkowski, R. and Lightfoot, G. (2015) Price Fluctuations and the Use of Bitcoin: An Empirical Inquiry. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.20 (1), pp.9-49.
- Porter, C. and Donthu, N. (2006) Using the technology acceptance model to explain how attitudes determine Internet usage: The role of perceived access barriers and demographics. Journal of Business Research. Vol.59 (9), pp.999-1007.
- Prathap, M. (2021) Top 10 cryptocurrencies in the world — the story behind Bitcoin and other altcoins [Online]. Business Insider. Available: <https://www.businessinsider.in/investment/news/these-are-the-top-ten-most-popular-cryptocurrencies-in-the-world/slidelist/85174407.cms> [Accessed 10 Aug 2021].
- Presthus, W. and O'Malley, N. (2017) Motivations and Barriers for End-User Adoption of Bitcoin as Digital Currency. Procedia Computer Science. Vol.121, pp.89-97.
- Preston, J. (2004) Bird, Kuhn, and positivism. Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A. Vol.35 (2), pp.327–335.

- Raaij, E. and Schepers, J. (2008) The acceptance and use of a virtual learning environment in China. Computers & Education. Vol.50 (3), pp.838-852.
- Rafique, H., Almagrabi, A., Shamim, A., Anwar, F. and Bashir, A. (2020) Investigating the Acceptance of Mobile Library Applications with an Extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Computers & Education. Vol.145, article no: 103732.
- Raikwar, M., Mazumdar, S., Ruj, S., Sen Gupta, S., Chattopadhyay, A. and Lam, K. (2018) A Blockchain Framework for Insurance Processes. 2018 9th IFIP International Conference on New Technologies, Mobility and Security (NTMS). pp.1-4.
- Ramayah, T. and Lo, M. (2007) Impact of shared beliefs on “perceived usefulness” and “ease of use” in the implementation of an enterprise resource planning system. Management Research News. Vol.30 (6), pp.420-431.
- Ramsay, J. (1998) Problems with empiricism and the philosophy of science: Implications for purchasing research. European Journal of Purchasing & Supply Management. Vol.4 (2–3), pp.163–173.
- Rauniar, R., Rawski, G., Yang, J. and Johnson, B. (2014) Technology acceptance model (TAM) and social media usage: an empirical study on Facebook. Journal of Enterprise Information Management. Vol.27 (1), pp.6-30.
- Rawnsley, M. M. (1998) Ontology, Epistemology, and Methodology: A Clarification. Nursing Science Quarterly. Vol.11 (1), pp.2–4.
- Reid, F. and Harrigan, M. (2013) An Analysis of Anonymity in the Bitcoin System. In: Altshuler, Y., Elovici, Y., Cremers, A. B., Aharony, N., and Pentland, A. (eds.). Security and Privacy in Social Networks. [Online]. New York, NY: Springer, pp.197–223. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4139-7_10
- Renteria, N., Wilson, T. and Strohecker, K. (2021) In a world first, El Salvador makes bitcoin legal tender [Online]. Reuters. Available: <https://www.reuters.com/world/americas/el-salvador-approves-first-law-bitcoin-legal-tender-2021-06-09/> [Accessed 30 Jul 2021].

- Roca, J., García, J. and Vega, J. (2009) The importance of perceived trust, security and privacy in online trading systems. Information Management & Computer Security. Vol.17 (2), pp.96-113.
- Rogers, E. M. (1976) New Product Adoption and Diffusion. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.2 (4), pp.290–301.
- Rogers, E.M. (1995) Diffusion of innovations. 4th ed. New York: Free Press
- Rogers, Everett M. (1962). Diffusion of innovations. New York: Free Press of Glencoe
- Rogers, R. (1985) Attitude Change and Information Integration in Fear Appeals. Psychological Reports. Vol.56 (1), pp.179-182.
- Roscoe, J. (1975) Fundamental research statistics for the behavioral sciences. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Roussou, I., Stiakakis, E. and Sifaleras, A. (2019) An empirical study on the commercial adoption of digital currencies. Information Systems and e-Business Management. Vol.17 (2-4), pp.223-259.
- Rowley, J. (2014) Designing and using research questionnaires. Management Research Review. Vol.37 (3), pp.308-330.
- Royce, J. (1963) Factors as theoretical constructs. American Psychologist. Vol.18 (8), pp.522-528.
- Ryan, B., Scapens, R. and Theobald, M. (2002) Research method and methodology in finance and accounting. London: South Western Cengage Learning.
- Ryu, H. (2018) What makes users willing or hesitant to use Fintech?: the moderating effect of user type. Industrial Management & Data Systems. Vol.118 (3), pp.541-569.
- Ryu, H.-S. (2018) Understanding Benefit and Risk Framework of Fintech Adoption: Comparison of Early Adopters and Late Adopters. Presented at the Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences. pp.3864–3873.

- Ryu, H.-S. (2018) What makes users willing or hesitant to use Fintech?: the moderating effect of user type. Industrial Management & Data Systems. Vol.118 (3), pp.541–569.
- Saadé, R. and Kira, D. (2007) Mediating the impact of technology usage on perceived ease of use by anxiety. Computers & Education. Vol.49 (4), pp.1189-1204.
- Saberi, S., Kouhizadeh, M., Sarkis, J. and Shen, L. (2018) Blockchain technology and its relationships to sustainable supply chain management. International Journal of Production Research. Vol.57 (7), pp.2117-2135.
- Sabir, I., Azam, A., Majid, M., Mahmud, M. and Sabir, N. (2020) The Bandwagon Effect and Consumption of Fashion Goods: A Case of Young Consumers of Pakistan. Scholedge International Journal of Management & Development ISSN 2394-3378. Vol.7 (5), pp.88-98.
- Saiedi, E., Broström, A. and Ruiz, F. (2020) Global drivers of cryptocurrency infrastructure adoption. Small Business Economics. Vol.57, pp.353-406.
- Salahshour Rad, M., Nilashi, M. and Mohamed Dahlan, H. (2017) Information technology adoption: a review of the literature and classification. Universal Access in the Information Society. Vol.17 (2), pp.361-390.
- Saleh, F. (2020) Blockchain without Waste: Proof-of-Stake. The Review of Financial Studies. Vol.34 (3), pp.1156-1190.
- Sanchez, P., Saura, J. and Ayestaran, R. (2021) An Exploratory Approach to the Adoption Process of Bitcoin by Business Executives. Mathematics. Vol.9 (4), article no: 355.
- Sanka, A., Irfan, M., Huang, I. and Cheung, R. (2021) A survey of breakthrough in blockchain technology: Adoptions, applications, challenges and future research. Computer Communications. Vol.169, pp.179-201.

- Santander (2021) The bandwagon effect: Why we spend money on fads. [Online]. Available: <https://www.santander.com/en/stories/the-bandwagon-effect-why-we-spend-money-on-fads> [Accessed 19 May 2022].
- Sarantakos, S. (1993) Social research. Houndmills, Basingstoke: Macmillan Education UK.
- Sarkodie, S. A., Ahmed, M. Y. and Owusu, P. A. (2021) COVID-19 pandemic improves market signals of cryptocurrencies—evidence from Bitcoin, Bitcoin Cash, Ethereum, and Litecoin. Finance Research Letters. Vol.44, article no: 102049.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2007) Research methods for business students. 3rd ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2009) Research Methods for Business Students. 5th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Schaupp, L. and Festa, M. (2018) Cryptocurrency adoption and the road to regulation. Proceedings of the 19th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research: Governance in the Data Age. Article no: 78.
- Schermelleh-Engel, K., Moosbrugger, H. and Müller, H. (2003) Evaluating the Fit of Structural Equation Models: Tests of Significance and Descriptive Goodness-of-Fit Measures. Methods of Psychological Research. Vol.8, pp.23–74.
- Schmitt-Beck, R. (2015) Bandwagon Effect. In: The International Encyclopedia of Political Communication. [Online]. American Cancer Society, pp.1–5.
- Schreiber, J., Nora, A., Stage, F., Barlow, E. and King, J. (2006) Reporting Structural Equation Modeling and Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results: A Review. The Journal of Educational Research. Vol.99 (6), pp.323-338.
- Schumacker, R. and Lomax, R. (2004) A beginner's guide to structural equation monitoring. 2nd ed. Mahwah, N.J.: Lawrence Erlbaum.

- Segars, A. (1997) Assessing the unidimensionality of measurement: a paradigm and illustration within the context of information systems research. Omega. Vol.25 (1), pp.107-121.
- Sekaran, U. (2003) Research methods for business. 4th ed. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2016) Research Methods For Business. 7th ed. New York: Wiley.
- Shahzad, F., Xiu, G., Wang, J. and Shahbaz, M. (2018) An empirical investigation on the adoption of cryptocurrencies among the people of mainland China. Technology in Society. Vol.55, pp.33-40.
- Shalev, E. and Morwitz, V. G. (2012) Influence via Comparison-Driven Self-Evaluation and Restoration: The Case of the Low-Status Influencer. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.38 (5), pp.964–980.
- Sheeran, P. (2002) Intention—Behavior Relations: A Conceptual and Empirical Review. European Review of Social Psychology. Vol.12 (1), pp.1-36.
- Shehhi, A., Oudah, M. and Aung, Z. (2014) Investigating factors behind choosing a cryptocurrency. 2014 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management. pp.1443-1447.
- Sheppard, B., Hartwick, J. and Warshaw, P. (1988) The Theory of Reasoned Action: A Meta-Analysis of Past Research with Recommendations for Modifications and Future Research. Journal of Consumer Research. Vol.15 (3), pp.325-343.
- Shovkhalov, S. and Idrisov, H. (2021) Economic and Legal Analysis of Cryptocurrency: Scientific Views from Russia and the Muslim World. Laws. Vol.10 (2), article no: 32.
- Shropshire, J., Warkentin, M. and Sharma, S. (2015) Personality, attitudes, and intentions: Predicting initial adoption of information security behavior. Computers & Security. Vol.49, pp.177–191.

- Singh, S. and Srivastava, R. (2020) Understanding the intention to use mobile banking by existing online banking customers: an empirical study. Journal of Financial Services Marketing. Vol.25, pp.86-96.
- Slatten, L. (2012) Something old and something new: Using the technology acceptance model to evaluate nonprofit certification. International Journal of Organization Theory & Behavior. Vol.15 (3), pp.423-449.
- Sniehotta, F., Presseau, J. and Araújo-Soares, V. (2014) Time to retire the theory of planned behaviour. Health Psychology Review. Vol.8 (1), pp.1-7.
- Sobhanifard, Y. and Sadatfarizani, S. (2019) Consumer-based modeling and ranking of the consumption factors of cryptocurrencies. Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications. Vol.528, article no: 121263.
- Sohaib, O., Hussain, W., Asif, M., Ahmad, M. and Mazzara, M. (2020) A PLS-SEM Neural Network Approach for Understanding Cryptocurrency Adoption. IEEE Access. Vol.8, pp.13138-13150.
- Solomon, M. (2016) Consumer Behavior: Buying, Having, and Being. 12th edition. Boston: Pearson.
- Spearman, C. (1904) "General Intelligence," Objectively Determined and Measured. The American Journal of Psychology. Vol.15 (2), pp.201-292.
- Sriman, B., Ganesh Kumar, S. and Shamili, P. (2021) Blockchain Technology: Consensus Protocol Proof of Work and Proof of Stake. In: Dash, S. S., Das, S., and Panigrahi, B. K. (eds.). Intelligent Computing and Applications. Singapore: Springer, pp.395–406.
- Sriman, B., Kumar, S. and Shamili, P. (2020) Blockchain Technology: Consensus Protocol Proof of Work and Proof of Stake. Intelligent Computing and Applications. pp.395-406.

- Stewart, H. and Jürjens, J. (2018) Data security and consumer trust in FinTech innovation in Germany. Information & Computer Security. Vol.26 (1), pp.109-128.
- Stewart, H. and Jürjens, J. (2018) Data security and consumer trust in FinTech innovation in Germany. Information & Computer Security. Vol.26 (1), pp.109-128.
- Stewart, K. J. (2003) Trust Transfer on the World Wide Web. Organization Science. Vol.14 (1), pp.5–17.
- Sutton, S. (2001) Health Behavior: Psychosocial Theories. International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences. pp.6499-6506.
- Svendsen, G., Johnsen, J., Almås-Sørensen, L. and Vittersø, J. (2013) Personality and technology acceptance: the influence of personality factors on the core constructs of the Technology Acceptance Model. Behaviour & Information Technology. Vol.32 (4), pp.323-334.
- Swan, M. (2015) Blockchain: Blueprint for a New Economy. Beijing: O'Reilly.
- Tabachnick, B. and Fidell, L. (2007) Using multivariate statistics. 5th ed. New York: Pearson.
- Talukder, M. (2012) Factors affecting the adoption of technological innovation by individual employees: An Australian study. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.40, pp.52-57.
- Tan, M. and Teo, T. (2000) Factors Influencing the Adoption of Internet Banking. Journal of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.1 (1), pp.1-44.
- Taylor, J. (1974) The Role of Risk in Consumer Behavior. Journal of Marketing. Vol.38 (2), pp.54-60.
- Thatcher, J. B. and Perrewé, P. L. (2002) An Empirical Examination of Individual Traits as Antecedents to Computer Anxiety and Computer Self-Efficacy. MIS Quarterly. Vol.26 (4), pp.381–396.

- The Economic Times (2021) China's role in the 2021 cryptocurrency crash. [Online]. The Economic Times. Available: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/trendspotting/chinas-role-in-the-2021-cryptocurrency-crash/articleshow/83839337.cms> [Accessed 30 Jul 2021].
- The Economic Times (2021). What's driving Indians into cryptocurrency amid all the uncertainty. (2021) [Online]. Available: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/markets/forex/whats-driving-indians-into-cryptocurrency-amid-all-the-uncertainty/articleshow/82239475.cms> [Accessed 28 Apr 2021].
- The Library of Congress (2021) Russian Federation: New Bill Defines Cryptocurrency, Proposes Tax Regulations. [Online]. Available: <https://www.loc.gov/item/global-legal-monitor/2021-01-11/russian-federation-new-bill-defines-cryptocurrency-proposes-tax-regulations/> [Accessed 30 Jul 2021].
- Thong, J., Hong, W. and Tam, K. (2004) What leads to user acceptance of digital libraries?. Communications of the ACM. Vol.47 (11), pp.78-83.
- Treleaven, P., Gendal Brown, R. and Yang, D. (2017) Blockchain Technology in Finance. Computer. Vol.50 (9), pp.14-17.
- Tsai, T., Lin, W., Chang, Y., Chang, P. and Lee, M. (2020) Technology anxiety and resistance to change behavioral study of a wearable cardiac warming system using an extended TAM for older adults. PLOS ONE. Vol.15 (1), article no: e0227270.
- Turan, A. and Kir, M. (2019) User anxiety as an external variable of technology acceptance model: A meta-analytic study. Procedia Computer Science. Vol.158, pp.715-724.
- Turan, A., Tunç, A. and Zehir, C. (2015) A Theoretical Model Proposal: Personal Innovativeness and User Involvement as Antecedents of Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.210, pp.43-51.

- Ulker-Demirel, E. and Ciftci, G. (2020) A systematic literature review of the theory of planned behavior in tourism, leisure and hospitality management research. Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management. Vol.43, pp.209-219.
- Ullman, J. (2001) Structural equation modeling. In: Tabachnick, B. and Fidell, L. Using multivariate statistics. MA: Pearson Education, pp.653-771.
- Ullman, J. and Bentler, P. (2012) Structural Equation Modeling. In: I. Weiner, J.A. Schinka and W.F. Velicer. Handbook of Psychology, Second Edition. New York: Wileys, pp.661-690.
- US News (2021) Young UK Investors Choose Cryptocurrencies Over Stocks: Survey. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usnews.com/news/technology/articles/2021-04-22/young-uk-investors-choose-cryptocurrencies-over-stocks-survey> [Accessed 28 Apr 2021].
- UWS (2017) Regulations for the Assessment of students on Taught Programmes. [Online]. Available: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/2037/regulation-7-assessment.pdf> [Accessed 23 May 2021].
- UWS (2020) Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship. Uws.ac.uk. Available: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/6463/guidelines-for-ethical-practice-in-research-and-scholarship-feb-2020.pdf>
- Venkatesh, Morris, Davis and Davis (2003) User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. MIS Quarterly. Vol.27 (3), pp.425-478.
- Venkatesh, V. (2000) Determinants of Perceived Ease of Use: Integrating Control, Intrinsic Motivation, and Emotion into the Technology Acceptance Model. Information Systems Research. Vol.11 (4), pp.342-365.
- Venkatesh, V. and Bala, H. (2008) Technology Acceptance Model 3 and a Research Agenda on Interventions. Decision Sciences. Vol.39 (2), pp.273–315.

- Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. (1996) A Model of the Antecedents of Perceived Ease of Use: Development and Test. Decision Sciences. Vol.27 (3), pp.451-481.
- Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. (2000) A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. Management Science. Vol.46 (2), pp.186-204.
- Venkatesh, V. and Morris, M. (2000) Why Don't Men Ever Stop to Ask for Directions? Gender, Social Influence, and Their Role in Technology Acceptance and Usage Behavior. MIS Quarterly. Vol.24 (1), pp.115-139.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B. and Davis, F. D. (2003) User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. MIS Quarterly. Vol.27 (3), pp.425–478.
- VISA (2021) The Crypto Phenomenon: Consumer Attitudes & Usage [Online]. Available: <https://usa.visa.com/dam/VCOM/regional/na/us/Solutions/documents/the-crypto-phenomenon-technical-paper.pdf> [Accessed 3 May 2022].
- Vujicic, D., Jagodic, D. and Randic, S. (2018) Blockchain technology, bitcoin, and Ethereum: A brief overview. In: 2018 17th International Symposium INFOTEH-JAHORINA (INFOTEH). [Online]. Presented at the 2018 17th International Symposium INFOTEH-JAHORINA (INFOTEH), East Sarajevo: IEEE, pp.1–6. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8345547/>
- Wallace, B. (2011) The Rise and Fall of Bitcoin. Wired. [Online] Vol.19 (12). Available: <https://www.wired.com/2011/11/mf-bitcoin/>
- Wang, L., Shen, X., Li, J., Shao, J. and Yang, Y. (2019) Cryptographic primitives in blockchains. Journal of Network and Computer Applications. Vol.127, pp.43-58.
- Wang, X., Zha, X., Ni, W., Liu, R., Guo, Y., Niu, X. and Zheng, K. (2019) Survey on blockchain for Internet of Things. Computer Communications. Vol.136, pp.10-29.

- Wang, Y., Wang, Y., Lin, H. and Tang, T. (2003) Determinants of user acceptance of Internet banking: an empirical study. International Journal of Service Industry Management. Vol.14 (5), pp.501-519.
- Weber, E. U., Anderson, C. J. and Birnbaum, M. H. (1992) A theory of perceived risk and attractiveness. Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes. Vol.52 (3), pp.492–523.
- Weng, F., Yang, R., Ho, H. and Su, H. (2018) A TAM-Based Study of the Attitude towards Use Intention of Multimedia among School Teachers. Applied System Innovation. Vol.1 (3), article no: 36.
- Williams, M., Dwivedi, Y., Lal, B. and Schwarz, A. (2009) Contemporary Trends and Issues in it Adoption and Diffusion Research. Journal of Information Technology. Vol.24 (1), pp.1-10.
- World Economic Forum (2021) [Online]. Cryptocurrencies are democratizing the financial world. Available: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/01/cryptocurrencies-are-democratising-the-financial-world-heres-how/> [Accessed 28 Apr 2021].
- Wright, B. (1998) Behavioral Intentions and Opportunities Among Homeless Individuals: A Reinterpretation of the Theory of Reasoned Action. Social Psychology Quarterly. Vol.61 (4), pp.271-286.
- Wu, I. and Chen, J. (2005) An extension of Trust and TAM model with TPB in the initial adoption of on-line tax: An empirical study. International Journal of Human-Computer Studies. Vol.62 (6), pp.784-808.
- Wu, I., Li, J. and Fu, C. (2011) The adoption of mobile healthcare by hospital's professionals: An integrative perspective. Decision Support Systems. Vol.51 (3), pp.587-596.

- Wu, I.-L. and Chen, J.-L. (2005) An extension of Trust and TAM model with TPB in the initial adoption of on-line tax: An empirical study. International Journal of Human-Computer Studies. Vol.62 (6), pp.784–808.
- Wu, T. and Lin, C. (2017) Predicting the effects of eWOM and online brand messaging: Source trust, bandwagon effect and innovation adoption factors. Telematics and Informatics. Vol.34 (2), pp.470-480.
- Xie, Q., Song, W., Peng, X. and Shabbir, M. (2017) Predictors for e-government adoption: integrating TAM, TPB, trust and perceived risk. The Electronic Library. Vol.35 (1), pp.2–20.
- Xu, Q., Schmierbach, M., Bellur, S., Ash, E., Oeldorf-Hirsch, A. and Kegerise, A. (2012) The Effects of “Friend” Characteristics on Evaluations of an Activist Group in a Social Networking Context. Mass Communication and Society. Vol.15 (3), pp.432-453.
- Yadav, N., Goar, V. and Kuri, M. (2020) Crypto Wallet: A Perfect Combination with Blockchain and Security Solution for Banking. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. Vol.24 (2), pp.6056-6066.
- Yang, H. and Yoo, Y. (2004) It's all about attitude: revisiting the technology acceptance model. Decision Support Systems. Vol.38 (1), pp.19-31.
- Yelowitz, A. and Wilson, M. (2015) Characteristics of Bitcoin users: an analysis of Google search data. Applied Economics Letters. Vol.22 (13), pp.1030-1036.
- Yermack, D. (2013) Is Bitcoin a Real Currency? An economic appraisal [Online]. National Bureau of Economic Research. Working Paper No. 19747. Available: <https://www.nber.org/papers/w19747>
- Yermack, D. (2015) Is Bitcoin a Real Currency? An Economic Appraisal. In: Handbook of Digital Currency. Elsevier, pp.31–43.

- Yi, M., Fiedler, K. and Park, J. (2006) Understanding the Role of Individual Innovativeness in the Acceptance of IT-Based Innovations: Comparative Analyses of Models and Measures. Decision Sciences. Vol.37 (3), pp.393-426.
- Yi, M., Jackson, J., Park, J. and Probst, J. (2006) Understanding information technology acceptance by individual professionals: Toward an integrative view. Information & Management. Vol.43 (3), pp.350-363.
- Yildirim, K., Saygili, M. and Yalcintekin, T. (2021) The determinants of purchase intention and willingness to pay for cosmetics and personal care products. Marketing and Management of Innovations. Vol.5 (2), pp.11-24.
- Yoon, S. (2002) The antecedents and consequences of trust in online-purchase decisions. Journal of Interactive Marketing. Vol.16 (2), pp.47-63.
- Yu, T., Lin, M. and Liao, Y. (2017) Understanding factors influencing information communication technology adoption behavior: The moderators of information literacy and digital skills. Computers in Human Behavior. Vol.71, pp.196-208.
- Zhang, X. and Yu, X. (2020) The Impact of Perceived Risk on Consumers' Cross-Platform Buying Behavior. Frontiers in Psychology. Vol.11, article no: 592246.
- Zhao, J., Fang, S. and Jin, P. (2018) Modeling and Quantifying User Acceptance of Personalized Business Modes Based on TAM, Trust and Attitude. Sustainability. Vol.10 (2), article no: 356.
- Zheng, Z., Xie, S., Dai, H., Chen, X. and Wang, H. (2017) An Overview of Blockchain Technology: Architecture, Consensus, and Future Trends. 2017 IEEE International Congress on Big Data (BigData Congress). pp.557-564.
- Zubaydi, H., Chong, Y., Ko, K., Hanshi, S. and Karuppayah, S. (2019) A Review on the Role of Blockchain Technology in the Healthcare Domain. Electronics. Vol.8 (6), article no: 67

Appendix A – Measurement Scales

Measurement Scales		
Personal Innovativeness (PI)		Source
PI1	If I hear about a new technology that I can use, I will look for ways to experiment with it	(Agarwal and Prasad, 1998)
PI2	Among my peers, I am usually the first to try out new technologies	
PI3	In general, I am hesitant to try out new technologies	
PI4	I like to experiment with new technologies	
Proactive Personality (PP)		
PP1	I enjoy facing and overcoming obstacles to my ideas	(Bateman and Crant, 1993); (Kickul and Gundry, 2002)
PP2	I excel at identifying opportunities	
PP3	I love to challenge the status quo of things	
PP4	I can spot a good opportunity long before others can	
Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)		
PEOU1	I think that it is easy to make cryptocurrency transactions	(Lee, 2009); (Cheng, Lam and Yeung, 2006)
PEOU2	I think that interaction with cryptocurrencies does not require a lot of mental effort	
PEOU3	Learning to use cryptocurrencies would be easy	
Perceived Usefulness (PU)		
PU1	Using cryptocurrencies will improve the profitability of my savings	(Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018); (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008)
PU2	Using cryptocurrencies will allow me to send money inexpensively to anyone in the world	
PU3	Using cryptocurrencies will improve my financial performance	
PU4	Using cryptocurrencies will allow me to increase my productivity	

Technology Anxiety (TA)		
TA1	It is frightening that I could face financial losses due to mistakes made while using cryptocurrencies	(Guo et al., 2013); (Thatcher and Perrewé, 2002)
TA2	I am reluctant to make cryptocurrency transactions due to the risk of making mistakes I cannot correct	
TA3	I feel apprehensive about learning the steps associated with cryptocurrency transactions	
TA4	Cryptocurrency usage is somewhat intimidating to me	
Bandwagon Effect (BE)		
BE1	I am likely to buy cryptocurrencies used by most investors	(Kastanakis and Balabanis, 2012)
BE2	I am likely to buy popular cryptocurrencies that everyone would know about	
BE3	I am likely to use cryptocurrencies recognized by many investors	
Perceived Trust (PT)		
PT1	Electronic payments made with cryptocurrencies are trustworthy	(Mendoza-Tello et al., 2019); (Kim et al, 2011); (Lu et al, 2010)
PT2	Using cryptocurrency wallets is reliable	
PT3	I think cryptocurrency transactions are safe	
PT4	Privacy is guaranteed in each cryptocurrency transaction	
Legal Risk (LR)		
LR1	I feel uncertainty when using cryptocurrencies due to the lack of regulations	(Ryu, 2018); (Abramova and Böhme, 2016); (Barakat and Hussainey, 2013)
LR2	The legislation regarding cryptocurrency usage is uncertain	
LR3	It is difficult to access various cryptocurrency e-wallets due to government regulations	
LR4	It is difficult to make cryptocurrency transactions due to the government regulation	
Privacy Risk (PR)		
PR1	I worry about the abuse of my personal data (e.g., transaction and private information) when I use cryptocurrencies	(Ryu, 2018); (Featherman and Pavlou, 2003)

PR2	My financial information might not be secure when I use cryptocurrencies	
PR3	I worry that someone can access my personal or financial information when I use cryptocurrencies	
Attitude towards Cryptocurrency (ATT)		
ATT1	Using cryptocurrencies is a good idea	
ATT2	Using cryptocurrencies would be a wise idea	(Wu and Chen, 2005); (Bhattacharjee, 2000)
ATT3	I enjoy the idea of using cryptocurrencies	
ATT4	Using cryptocurrencies is a pleasant experience	
Intention to Adopt Cryptocurrencies (IA)		
IA1	I intend to use cryptocurrencies	(Arias-Oliva et al, 2019); (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000)
IA2	I think that I will use cryptocurrencies	
IA3	I plan to invest or trade in cryptocurrencies in future	

Appendix C – Cover Letter

Dear Participant,

I am inviting you to participate in this research study by completing this survey. The primary purpose of the study is to understand the behaviour and perceptions of consumers towards cryptocurrency, based on various factors. In order to participate, you require basic familiarity with cryptocurrencies, previous usage experience is preferable but not necessary.

The attached questionnaire shall not take more than 12-15 minutes to complete. Your participation is completely voluntary and you can choose not to participate in part or all of the project. You can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. All the responses are anonymous. All information collected about you will only be considered for the purpose of this study. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured in the collection, storage and publication of the collected data. This study has been analysed by the UWS committee on research ethics and is affirmed to conform with the principles of research ethics and integrity.

Your participation and contribution is extremely valued. Please feel free to contact me for any further information regarding the study at [REDACTED]. You can also contact my supervisor at [REDACTED].

Personal details withheld.

Please consult the Participation Information Sheet for further details regarding the survey.

Sincerely,

Khushboo Mirchandani
Doctoral Researcher
University of the West of Scotland

Appendix D – Participation Information Sheet

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

STUDY TITLE – INVESTIGATING CONSUMER ATTITUDE TOWARDS CRYPTOCURRENCY

INVITATION PARAGRAPH

You are being invited to take part in this research study. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

This research forms part of a doctoral research project. **The purpose of this study is to explore the technological and socio-psychological factors that affect users' intention to adopt cryptocurrencies.**

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You have been invited to take part in the study because you are a current or potential user/investor of cryptocurrencies. This study utilizes a sample size of approximately 200-250 participants. **Your knowledge about cryptocurrencies is important for the purpose of this project.**

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

As a participant your participation is entirely voluntary, hence, you have the option to decide whether you take part or not. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. **In addition, you are free to request to have your data withdrawn from the study within a period of two weeks after the completion of the survey, without giving a reason.**

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

As a participant in this study, you will be asked to fill out a consent form, followed by an online questionnaire survey associated with your adoption to use cryptocurrencies. This will take approximately 15 minutes of your time.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

Apart from the time it takes you to answer to the questions, there are no costs or risks involved in this study.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

Your participation is voluntary and if you do decide to participate, you will contribute towards the understanding of the cryptocurrency market for the consumers as well as the corporates in order to form policies to launch cryptocurrencies. **Academicians, managers and experts will benefit as findings will contribute to the better understanding of what factors contribute to consumers' perception of cryptocurrencies when investing in them.**

WILL MY INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?

The participation is voluntary and participants have no obligation to participate. It takes precautions over ethical principles by enforcing confidentiality and anonymity, ensuring no harm will result in participating this study. It is imperative to consider ethical considerations because human subjects are involved who should not be at risk. Participants will not be asked for their name and only very limited background information, ensuring anonymity. Information gathered during statistical analysis will remain confidential and protected. To prevent the research from being unethical and bias, data will not be altered and analysed based on the original design, thus, enabling a true and accurate reflection of the results. If you decide to participate, all information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential and your confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured in the collection, storage and publication of this research material and not shared with others.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

If you decide to take part in this study, simply click "agree" and sign the consent form.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of the research will be strictly used for the purpose of the specific Research Project. Only aggregate results from the surveys will be published and the results will not

allow the identification of any of the participants. The data collected will be kept confidential.

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

I am conducting this research as a Doctor of Business Administration candidate within the School of Business & Creative Industries at the University of the West of Scotland. The researcher possesses all the relevant resources required to undertake this study.

WHO HAS APPROVED THIS STUDY?

This research has been approved by the Research Ethics Committee within the University of the West of Scotland.

WHO TO CONTACT IN CASE OF INQUIRIES OR CONCERNS?

If you have any questions or queries relating to this research, then please contact University Ethics Committee for the School of Business and Creative Industries (BCIethics@uws.ac.uk)

CONTACT FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

I hope that you will find the survey questions enjoyable. For further information about the way in which the study has been conducted, please refer to the contact list below:

Project Investigator: Khushboo Mirchandani

Email:

[Redacted email address]

[Redacted contact information]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix E – Consent Form

CONSENT FORM FOR PARTICIPANTS

Project title: **INVESTIGATING CONSUMER ATTITUDE TOWARDS CRYPTOCURRENCY**

Project Application 13548: DBA Research Project, Submission Reference 12144

I agree to take part in the above University of the West of Scotland research project. I have had the project explained to me and I have read and understood the Information Sheet, which I may keep for records. I understand that agreeing to take part means that I am willing to:

- Answer the online questionnaire.
- Allow the researcher to have access to my answers of the questionnaire.

I understand that any information I provide is confidential, and that no information that I disclose will lead to the identification of any individual in the reports on the project, either by the researcher or by any other party.

I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way.

I consent to the processing of any information that I provide for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the Data Protection Act 2018.

By continuing with the questionnaire, I give my consent to participating in the research.

Appendix F – Ethics Approval

05/01/2021

Dear Ms. Khushboo Mirchandani,

Your application 13548: DBA Research Project, submission reference 12144, has been approved, with conditions, by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below;**

Title	Comment
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	I would suggest the student to use social media/platforms only to contact the participants. Data should be collected using the questionnaires sent through emails
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	Pls include supervisor's contact details in the PI sheet.

Approved, subject to addressing panel comments from other reviewer

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

Appendix G – Research Questionnaire

INVESTIGATING CONSUMER ATTITUDE TOWARDS CRYPTOCURRENCY

* Required

1. I have read the consent form and I give my consent to participating in the research. *

[View the full Consent Form](#)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I consent to participating in this research
- No, I do not consent to participating in this research

Screening Question

This study is targeted towards people with some familiarity with cryptocurrencies.

2. What is your previous experience with cryptocurrencies? *

Mark only one oval.

- I have extensive experience with trading, using or investing in cryptocurrencies
- I have beginner level experience with trading, using or investing in cryptocurrencies
- I am well informed about cryptocurrencies but have no prior experience with them
- I have no idea about cryptocurrencies

Screening Question

The target age group of this study is 21-60 years.

3. Please select your Age group *

Mark only one oval.

- Below 21
- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- Above 61

**Section A:
Attitude
Towards
Innovation**

On a seven point scale from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, please select the option that most appropriately reflects your opinion about the following statements. (PLEASE SCROLL HORIZONTALLY IF ALL SEVEN OPTIONS ARE NOT VISIBLE ON YOUR DEVICE)

4. *Mark only one oval per row.*

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
If I hear about a new technology that I can use, I would look for ways to experiment with it	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Among my peers, I am usually the first to try out new technologies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
In general, I am hesitant to try out new technologies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I like to experiment with new technologies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

5. *Mark only one oval per row.*

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I enjoy facing and overcoming obstacles to my ideas	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I excel at identifying opportunities	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I love to challenge the status quo of things	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I can spot a good opportunity long before others can	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Section B:
Perceptions
About
Cryptocurrencies'
Usage

On a seven point scale from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, please select the option that most appropriately reflects your opinion about the following statements. (PLEASE SCROLL HORIZONTALLY IF ALL SEVEN OPTIONS ARE NOT VISIBLE ON YOUR DEVICE)

6. *Mark only one oval per row.*

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I think that it is easy to make cryptocurrency transactions	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I think that interaction with cryptocurrencies does not require a lot of mental effort	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Learning to use cryptocurrencies would be easy	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

7. *Mark only one oval per row.*

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Using cryptocurrencies will improve the profitability of my savings	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Using cryptocurrencies will allow me to send money inexpensively to anyone in the world	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Using cryptocurrencies will improve my financial performance	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Using cryptocurrencies will allow me to increase my productivity	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

8. *Mark only one oval per row.*

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
It is frightening that I could face financial losses due to mistakes made while using cryptocurrencies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I am reluctant to make cryptocurrency transactions due to the risk of making mistakes I cannot correct	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I feel apprehensive about learning the steps associated with cryptocurrency transactions	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Cryptocurrency usage is somewhat intimidating to me	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Section C:
Attitude
Towards
Consumption

On a seven point scale from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, please select the option that most appropriately reflects your opinion about the following statements. (PLEASE SCROLL HORIZONTALLY IF ALL SEVEN OPTIONS ARE NOT VISIBLE ON YOUR DEVICE)

9. *Mark only one oval per row.*

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree Nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I am likely to buy cryptocurrencies used by most investors	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I am likely to buy popular cryptocurrencies that everyone would know about	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I am likely to use cryptocurrencies recognized by many investors	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Section D:
Opinions about
Cryptocurrencies

On a seven point scale from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, please select the option that most appropriately reflects your opinion about the following statements. (PLEASE SCROLL HORIZONTALLY IF ALL SEVEN OPTIONS ARE NOT VISIBLE ON YOUR DEVICE)

10.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Electronic payments made with cryptocurrencies are trustworthy	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Using cryptocurrency wallets is reliable	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I think cryptocurrency transactions are safe	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Privacy is guaranteed in each cryptocurrency transaction	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

11.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel uncertainty when using cryptocurrencies due to the lack of regulations	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The legislation regarding cryptocurrency usage is uncertain	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It is difficult to access various cryptocurrency e-wallets due to government regulations	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It is difficult to make cryptocurrency transactions due to the government regulation	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

12.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree Nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I worry about the abuse of my personal data (e.g. transaction and private information) when I use cryptocurrencies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
My financial information might not be secure when I use cryptocurrencies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I worry that someone can access my personal or financial information when I use cryptocurrencies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

**Section E:
Intentions
Towards
Cryptocurrencies**

On a seven point scale from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, please select the option that most appropriately reflects your opinion about the following statements. Some statements might sound similar but they have subtle differences in what is being asked. (PLEASE SCROLL HORIZONTALLY IF ALL SEVEN OPTIONS ARE NOT VISIBLE ON YOUR DEVICE)

13.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Using cryptocurrencies is a good idea	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Using cryptocurrencies would be a wise idea	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I enjoy the idea of using cryptocurrencies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Using cryptocurrencies is a pleasant experience	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

14.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I intend to use cryptocurrencies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I think that I will use cryptocurrencies	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I plan to invest or trade in cryptocurrencies in future	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Demographics

15. Gender

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say
- Other

16. Education

Mark only one oval.

- High School Degree or Equivalent
- Some College Credit, No Degree
- Trade/technical/vocational training
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Professional degree
- Doctorate degree
- Prefer not to say

17. Primary purpose of using cryptocurrencies

Check all that apply.

- Monetary Transactions
- Long Term Trading
- Short Term Trading
- Other

18. No. of different cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, Ethereum, etc) you possess

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 and Above

19. How much money have you invested in Cryptocurrencies?

Mark only one oval.

- USD 0 - USD 500
- USD 500 - USD 2,000
- USD 2,000 - USD 5,000
- USD 5,000 - USD 10,000
- More than USD 10,000

20. If you have any further comments regarding cryptocurrencies please add them here:

Thank you very much for your valuable time. Your response is greatly appreciated.

PLEASE SUBMIT THE FORM TO COMPLETE THE SURVEY